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RESEARCH ARTICLES

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ

CYCLICITY IN ONTOGENY AND AGE DETERMINATION OF *FLEXOPECTEN GLABER* (BIVALVIA, PECTINIDAE) IN THE BLACK SEA

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Flexopecten glaber is an actively fished species in the Mediterranean Sea and a promising candidate for mariculture in the Black Sea. *Flexopecten glaber* is included in the Red Data Books of the Republic of Crimea and Sevastopol city as a species declining in number (Category 2). In this study, over 1500 specimens sampled near the Crimean Peninsula between 2017 and 2023 were analysed to investigate the ontogeny of *F. glaber* and develop a method for determining individual age, based on the relationship between stages of gonadal development and changes in shell surface morphology. The cyclicality of development was assessed by comparing the cycles of gonad formation with the features of the surface morphology of the shell. A correlation was found between the morphology of the surface of shell valves and the stages of the annual cycle of gonad development. On this basis, a scheme for determining the developmental stages and individual age of *F. glaber* specimens from the morphology of shell valves has been developed. The most prominent mark on the shell surface is formed mainly in winter as a result of the physiological restructuring of the organism before the beginning of the annual cycle of gonad formation. However, to determine the age of *F. glaber*, the spawning marks formed mainly in summer need to be considered. The proposed scheme for determining the developmental stages and age of *F. glaber* individuals is a valuable tool for studying the species and can help resolve a variety of ecological and conservation issues.

Key words: annual cycle, gonads, protected species, scallop, shell morphology

Introduction

Interest in the study of mollusks is constantly increasing due to the need to solve problems related to the rational use of marine biological resources, the assessment of productivity, development of monitoring systems and biotechnology for growing commercial species and protecting vulnerable species (Zolotarev, 1989; Gosling, 2004; Marčeta et al., 2016).

Flexopecten glaber (Linnaeus, 1758) is the subject of active fisheries in the Mediterranean, and one of the most promising mariculture species in this area (Lykakis & Kalathakis, 1991; Marčeta et al., 2016; Berik et al., 2017; Yigitkurt et al., 2022) and in the Black Sea (Bondarev, 2019; Revkov et al., 2021). While *F. glaber* had not been found in the Black Sea shelf zone for over two decades, its population is now showing recovery signs (Bondarev, 2018, 2019; Revkov & Revkova, 2023). Recent discoveries of *F. glaber* on the Romanian shelf (Filimon, 2020; Danilov et al., 2024), in the waters of Bulgaria (Todorova et al., 2022), and on the southwestern shelf of Crimea in the Laspi area, where the species forms a community (Revkov & Boltachova, 2022), confirm this trend. Currently *F. glaber* is protected in accordance with the Red Data Books of the Republic of Crimea (Revkov, 2015)

and Sevastopol Region (Revkov, 2018) as a species declining in number (Category 2).

Determining the individual age of mollusks is a crucial aspect of many studies on their biology. The concept of individual age plays a key role in understanding ontogenetic development, morphological and ecological characteristics, and the productivity of species. Accurate information about the age structure of populations is essential for analysing the mechanisms of species-environment interactions, including regulation of abundance, changes in life expectancy, and mortality rates. Although the problem of determining individual age in mollusks is a seemingly narrow topic, it is important to several fields of marine biology. However, it is also one of the least studied characteristics of these organisms, mainly due to the lack of reliable methods for age determination in most marine animals (Zolotarev, 1989).

Sculptural methods form the basis for determining the age of mollusks. These methods identify shell elements formed on the surface of the valve according to daily or seasonal changes in environmental conditions. The growth rings on the external surface of the valve are the most commonly used for this purpose. These external growth rings are sculptural elements formed due to periodic changes in the growth rate of

the mollusks. Their morphology is very diverse, and, in some cases, the outer growth rings are accompanied by changes in the colour of the outer surface of the valve (Zolotarev, 1989; Gosling, 2004).

The determination of the age of *Flexopecten glaber* based on the sculptural elements of the shell surface, interpreted as a result of an annual winter slowdown in growth, was carried out on samples from the Black Sea (Bondarev, 2019, 2020; Filimon, 2020; Todorova et al., 2022; Danilov et al., 2024). The maximum age of Black Sea individuals of *F. glaber* was estimated to be seven (Bondarev, 2019) and nine years (Todorova et al., 2022; Danilov et al., 2024). However, during the study of *F. glaber* reared in cages in a shellfish farm, it was found that individual specimens with an age of less than three years exceeded the previously determined maximum sizes of the Black Sea individuals (Revkov et al., 2021). In the Mediterranean Sea, *F. glaber* can reach a maximum size at 2+ years of age (Lykakis & Kalathakis, 1991). These results cast doubt on the reliability of the determination of maximum age and the method of age determination based on the «annual» growth lines of *F. glaber*.

Understanding the rhythmicity of animal growth is a central aspect of growth research (Mina & Klevezal, 1976). In *Flexopecten glaber*, a distinct annual development cycle is observed in the gonads. The reproductive process of *F. glaber* gonads at commercial size in the Adriatic Sea is categorised into six stages within the annual cycle (Marčeta et al., 2016), which had been previously identified on the basis of the various morphological criteria given for other pectinids (Mason, 1958; Reddiah, 1962; Sause et al., 1987).

The aim of this study is to investigate the cyclicity of development in the ontogeny of *Flexopecten glaber* from the Black Sea and to develop a method for determining individual age based on the relationship between stages of gonadal development and changes in shell surface morphology. Our study is based on the idea that the development of mollusk organs is interdependent during ontogeny in accordance with seasonal rhythms.

Material and Methods

Analysis of long-term variations in the Black Sea population of *Flexopecten glaber* allows categorising the Crimean coastal zone as one of the areas with the most favourable environmental conditions for the smooth scallop to inhabit (Revkov & Revkova, 2023). During the study, *F. glaber* specimens were collected manually using diving equipment off the coast of the Crimean Peninsula at depths rang-

ing from 0.5 m to 17.0 m from 2017 to 2023. The salinity of the water in the study area ranges from 17.5‰ to 18.2‰, which corresponds to the average values in the Black Sea. The water temperature at the bottom surface ranged from 7°C in February to 25°C in August.

A total of more than 1500 *Flexopecten glaber* individuals were analysed, ranging in size from 2.0 mm to 65.0 mm in shell length. The majority of the samples (> 1000 specimens) were collected in 2023, covering all seasons by month.

The surfaces of the *Flexopecten glaber* shell valves were thoroughly cleaned of fouling by mechanical and chemical means to allow detailed analysis of their morphological characteristics. Changes in growth patterns on the valve surface were recorded, and the position of marker concentric growth lines and their correspondence to changes in gonadal structure were noted. The main dimensions of the shell, including height (H), length (L), and width (W) of the valve (Fig. 1a,b), as well as the height of the mesoconch (juvenile scallop – Hmc), and position of the concentric structural markings relative to the umbo (apical point) of the individual, were measured using a caliper SC–11–250–0.1 GOST 166–80 to an accuracy of 0.1 mm.

Each individual was opened with a scalpel and dissected. The viscera of the opened individuals were photographed. The valves were numbered, and then the stage of gonad development was compared with the morphological features of the surface of the cleaned valves.

Fig. 1. Main morphological characteristics of the shell and internal organs of *Flexopecten glaber* sampled 08.06.2022 in the Sevastopol Region, Crimea, Russia. Designations: a – upper (left) valve from inside, b – frontal (anterior) view of the shell, where H – height, L – length, W – width, m – adductor muscle, o – female part of the gonads, t – male part of the gonad.

Flexopecten glaber is a synchronous hermaphrodite, with a bipartite gonad, i.e. male and female (Marčeta et al., 2016). The gonad is located closer to the anterior side of the valve, near the adductor muscle, and is connected to it in a small area on the inner side of the distal part. The distal part of the gonad, which is lighter in colour, contains the oocytes (o), while the testicular part (t) occupies the proximal position (Fig. 1a).

As a basis for dividing the cycle of gonadal development into stages, we used a scheme developed on the basis of the results of examination of *Flexopecten glaber* individuals in the Adriatic Sea, which are commercially available. This cycle was divided into six stages as follows: 1) proliferating, 2) developing, 3) mature, 4) spawning, 5) post-spawning, and 6) spent according to Marčeta et al. (2016).

The age of *Flexopecten glaber* individuals was estimated from spawning marks using the method described in this paper. The graphs and calculations in this study were created using the MS Office Excel ver. 10 software.

Results

The morphology of the gonads of *Flexopecten glaber* at various stages of the annual developmental cycle is shown in Fig. 2. Gonad formation begins at the bend of the intestine during the transition from the juvenile stage or at the beginning of the annual cycle (Fig. 2a). Further development leads to the formation and accumulation of germ cells and primary differentiation of the gonad into female and male lobes (Fig. 2b,c). When the gonads reach maturity, the differentiation is complete, and both parts exhibit characteristic colouration (Fig. 2d–k). The female part of the gonad is usually more colourful, with shades ranging from red-orange (Fig. 2h) to pale creamy pink (Fig. 2i) and milky white (Fig. 2m). In the last two variants, the male part of the gonads may even appear slightly darker than the female part.

A gonadal colour spectrum (see Fig. 2) was found in *Flexopecten glaber* individuals from all studied local populations, and it is unrelated to the colour morph of the species, suggesting that these characteristics are independent. While individuals with a brightly coloured female gonadal portion are more common, there are also those with a pale coloured portion. However, in some habitats, individuals with milky white or slightly creamy coloured female gonads (> 50%) predominate. In most *F. glaber* individuals, the male and female proportions of the mature gonads are approximately equal $\pm 10\%$.

However, in some individuals, either the male (Fig. 2j) or female (Fig. 2k) proportion of the gonads may account for more than 80% of the amount.

In the late stages of spawning, shedding of some of the reproductive products leads to a «loosening» of the gonads in most individuals (Fig. 2l–n). This process results in the formation of residual nuclei of concentrated female and male gametes at the end of spawning (Fig. 3r). Emptying of the male and female parts of the gonads occurs more or less simultaneously (Fig. 2m,n). However, in some cases part of the gonad is emptied at an accelerated rate (Fig. 2o) and may be completely emptied with the remaining of a nearly full part of the opposite sex (Fig. 2p). At the post-spawning stage, the resorption processes dominate, and the size of the gonads decreases considerably (Fig. 2s). In the last stage of the cycle, the gonad is free of reproductive products, and the intestine is visible through the wall of the gonad sac (Fig. 2t).

Fig. 2. *Flexopecten glaber* gonad morphology by stages of the annual development cycle. Designations: a – proliferating, b, c – developing, d–k – mature, l–r – spawning, s – post-spawning, t – spent. Not to scale. Specimens sampled from 18.02.2021 to 20.10.2023 in the Crimea, Russia.

Fig. 3. Frequency plot (%) of gonads development stages of *Flexopecten glaber* sampled in January–December (I–XII) 2023 in the Sevastopol Region, Crimea, Russia. Designations: 1 – proliferating, 2 – developing, 3 – mature, 4 – spawning, 5 – post-spawning, 6 – spent.

The development of the gonads is not synchronous, even in individuals from the same local population. A new annual cycle of gonad development begins mainly in January at a temperature of 8°C, and in mid-February at a temperature of 7°C. Individuals can be found at various stages of development to maturity (Fig. 2a–d, Fig. 3). The gonads in the upper row (see Fig. 2a–d) belong to individuals collected from a local population at a depth of 15–17 m and at a low temperature of 7°C. In May, at a temperature of 12°C, the gonads of more than 50% of the *Flexopecten glaber* individuals were already in the mature stage. The highest number of mature individuals (90%) was recorded in June at a temperature from 17°C to 22°C, when active spawning begins, continuing until September. In October, about 85% of individuals have spent gonads, which remain in this state throughout the entire population from November to December (Fig. 3).

At the end of December to the beginning of January, the organism of most individuals undergoes a changeover, which precedes the beginning of the development cycle of the gonads. This transition results in a severe slowdown or even cessation of shell growth. During this process, a fairly noticeable starting mark forms on the surface of the valve, corresponding to the ventral edge of the shell during growth stoppage (Fig. 4a,b,c,f,h). The shell between the successive start mark is formed over the course of a calendar year. In individuals entering puberty, such a mark delimits the juvenile shell, or mesoconch (Fig. 4). At the mesoconch stage, the gonads of *Flexopecten glaber* are not yet developed, and subsequent formation and maturation of the gonads in individuals within the population do not occur simultaneously.

Fig. 4. *Flexopecten glaber* shell valves of various colour morphs, sizes (mm), ages (year) and the development stages. Designations: a: H = 46.2 mm, L = 48.0 mm, Hmc = 15.5 mm, 3-years; b: H = 33.5 mm, L = 34.2 mm, Hmc = 6.1 mm, 3-years; c: H = 43.2 mm, L = 44.5 mm, Hmc = 11.0 mm, 3-years; d: H = 42.5 mm, L = 44.0 mm, Hmc = 19.5 mm, 2-years; e: H = 36.5 mm, L = 36.3 mm, Hmc = 22.2 mm, 1+year; f: H = 43.5 mm, L = 46.8 mm, Hmc = 8.0 mm, 3-years; g: H = 42.7 mm, L = 46.4 mm, Hmc = 15.2 mm, 2 years; h: H = 58.8 mm, L = 65.0 mm, Hmc = 20.5 mm, 4 years; stm – starting mark, spm – spawning mark. All shells are at the same scale. Specimens were sampled from 18.02.2019 to 23.08.2023 in the Crimea, Russia.

The mesoconch often exhibits varying degrees of protective disruptive colouration (Fig. 4a,b,c,d,g,h). Sometimes the dissecting colouration extends into the zone corresponding to the mature stage of the gonads (Fig. 4b), but this is even less common in subsequent zones of the annual cycle (Fig. 4c).

The growth of the shell and the development of the gonads of mollusks are closely related. However, during the maturation of the gonads (stages 1–3), the growth rate of the shell is lower, and the growing layers form a more uneven surface than in the subsequent developmental stages, as can better be seen in Fig. 4d. These layers, which follow the first starting mark, are often lighter in colour than those that follow the subsequent ones (Fig. 4a,b,c,e). In some specimens, the transition from mesoconch to dissoconch (mature shell) is marked by a white zone (Fig. 4b,c), and this colouration may also follow the starting mark of a new cycle in the second year of life, although less frequently (Fig. 4c).

After reaching maturity with distinguishable male and female parts (Fig. 1a), the gonads of the mollusks continue to grow until the spawning begins. This phase is accompanied by a more rapid growth of the valves and more intense colouration of their surface (Fig. 4a,d,e). The transition from terminal maturity to spawning is often characterised by a change in the surface colour of the shell (Fig. 4a) and/or the appearance of a concentric relief mark to varying degrees (Fig. 4b,c,e,g). This stage of spawning is similarly evident on the upper valve (Fig. 4). The end of the active spawning period is often marked by a distinct concentric line that lies slightly below to the relief of the starting mark at the beginning of the gonadal maturation cycle. This mark, which is more often located in the middle (Fig. 4h), and less often at the end (Fig. 4a,d,g) of the spawning zone on the shell surface, is called the spawning mark. Its occurrence corresponds to the exhaustion of the gonads by more than 60–90%. In some specimens of the orange colour morph, a white stripe marks the middle of the spawning phase, which also indicates significant restructuring processes of the body. This marking indicates approximately the end of the regular year of life (Fig. 4f).

In order to determine the growth stages and ages of individual *Flexopecten glaber* from their shells, it is recommended that the annual cycle be divided into three stages, namely pre-spawning, ongoing spawning, and post-spawning. These stages are reflected on the surface of the shell valve in concentric zones of approximately equal width, often highlighted by differences in colour or tone (Fig. 4). In individuals with more uniformly coloured shells, where the corresponding markings are not as pronounced, growth stages can be determined by comparison with specimens with clear signs of the division. However, determining age and growth stages from external signs becomes difficult when there are individuals with different growth rates in the population, resulting in the presence of individuals of the same age but different size (see Fig. 5a).

Fig. 5. Graphs of the correspondence between the size and age of *Flexopecten glaber*. Designations: a – growth plot by shell height versus age, N = 600 specimens sampled from 18.02.2023 to 20.10.2023 in Crimea, Russia; b – growth plot of a 4-year-old individual (see Fig. 4h) sampled on 30.06.1019 in Crimea, Russia.

The scheme for determining the growth and age of the shell, as shown on the reference samples, is as follows: mesoconch corresponds to juvenile stage of scallop development and age 0(+) years; stage of dissoconch growth (mature stage of shell development) before spawning, i.e. 1(-) year old; spawning, i.e. 1 year; post-spawning, i.e. 1+ years (Fig. 4e). Dissoconch formation in subsequent years is similar (Fig. 4g). The growth rate decreases considerably with age (Fig. 4, Fig. 5), and the division into three stages in subsequent years becomes less pronounced, but the spawning mark is more evident (Fig. 4h), remaining less pronounced than the starting mark, though. An alternative version of age estimation can be performed using the spawning marks, the distance on the valve between which quite accurately corresponds to the individual year of the mollusk life (Fig. 4f,g,h).

The growth potential of an individual is largely determined by the size of its mesoconch, which is influenced by the time it takes for a juvenile to reach puberty, especially in the first year of life. In our sample, the maximum value of mesoconch size is 25.0 mm, while the average value is 13.5 mm. The smallest individual of *Flexopecten glaber* with gonads at the developing stage in our sample measured 12.8 mm in height and length (with mesoconch of 10.2 mm), and the smallest individual at the mature stage measured with a height of 16.0 mm and length of 12.9 mm (with mesoconch of 13.8 mm). The minimal mesoconch size observed in the examined *F. glaber* was 6.0 mm, indicating the possibility of sexual maturity in some individuals with a size less than 8–10 mm.

The largest specimen *Flexopecten glaber* we found had a height of 58.7 mm, a length of 65.0 mm, a width of 17.7 mm, and a mesoconch height of 20.5 mm, and it was over 4+ years old (Fig. 4h, Fig. 5b). The growth pattern of this individual (Fig. 5b) is typical for the *F. glaber* populations we studied. During maturation, the growth rate of the shells decreases considerably with age (Fig. 5). The annual periods of decreased growth rates correspond well with the period of gonadal development from the beginning to the mature stage (Fig. 5b).

Plotting the growth of *Flexopecten glaber* by shell height versus age shows a high degree of fit to the logarithmic curve with R^2 value of 0.8159. Using the method developed in the research, the highest age of *F. glaber* found off the Crimean coast was estimated to be 5 years (Fig. 5a).

Discussion

Diagnosing the developmental stages of *Flexopecten glaber* gonads based on morphological char-

acteristics simplifies field and laboratory work with mass material, as compared to histological studies (Fig. 2). However, the phenomenon of various gonad colours at the same developmental stage within the same population, in individuals of the same age and even the same shell colour morph, requires further investigation. Studies on the total carotenoid concentrations (TCC) responsible for gonad colour and intensity in the scallop predator *Rapana venosa* (Valenciennes, 1846), indicate that the colour intensity increases with age due to the TCC accumulation, which are derived from their dietary spectrum (Bondarev & Malakhova, 2016). Unlike the gonads of *R. venosa*, the gonads of *F. glaber* are emptied annually, and pigments do not accumulate with age. The differences in colour and its intensity in the gonads of *F. glaber* within the population might be related to the local and even individual nutritional conditions of the scallops.

In general, the annual development cycle of the gonads of *Flexopecten glaber* in the Black Sea (Fig. 3) is similar to those described for this species in the Adriatic Sea (Marčeta et al., 2016), despite an almost two-fold difference in water salinity. The range of monthly average temperatures in the sampling areas is similar, ranging from 7°C in March to 22°C in September in the Adriatic Sea and from 7°C in February to 25°C in August in the Black Sea. It is noteworthy that the maturation process of *F. glaber* gonads starts in January at low temperatures (about 8°C) before reaching the minimal temperatures in both the Adriatic Sea and the Black Sea. After a brief slowdown, which may lead to a complete stop, shell growth resumes synchronously with gonad development. Therefore, the trigger for the start of gonadal development and the resumption of scallop growth is not, as one might expect, a rise in temperature. The starting mark, which is formed mainly in winter, does not result from a slowdown of life processes under the influence of low temperatures, but as a result of the organism physiological restructuring on the eve of the beginning of the annual cycle of gonad formation.

The start of the first cycle of gonad formation aligns with the ventral edge of the mesoconch, which can often be distinguished from the dissoconch by its colour and patterns (Fig. 4). Protective camouflage colouration of juveniles is a common phenomenon in the animal kingdom. The various colours and patterns of the mesoconch of *Flexopecten glaber* increase the chances of being detected and captured because there are a number of substrates, on which

the spat can settle and develop an initially thin-walled shell.

Since in *Flexopecten glaber*, 20 hours after fertilisation of the eggs, a growing shell in the form of a bilobed plate is formed, and all larvae enter the D-veliger stage (prodissoconch I) a day later (Pirkova & Ladygina, 2017), the age of *F. glaber* should be identified either by spawning marks or by areas of the shell surface corresponding to the spawning stage (Fig. 4). The shell surface formed from the apex to the first spawning mark, and further between successive spawning marks, is formed during one year of life of *F. glaber*.

Annual seasonal shell surface marks (starting mark and spawning mark) can often be difficult to distinguish one from another and from other markings caused by various factors such as storm damage, engineering activities, dredging, or predation attempts (Richardson, 2001). In previous studies of *Flexopecten glaber* in the Black Sea (e.g. Bondarev, 2019, 2020), the age estimation was based on starting marks and spawning marks, both annual marks, which resulted in some individuals being overestimated in age by up to two times. Understanding the formation of growth zones and marks on the shell surface can help distinguish regularly from randomly generated marks. Using a zonation scheme based on the established cyclicity of development in ontogenesis to determine the age of mollusks can increase the reliability of the results so that they are as accurate as possible.

The wide range of the size values within a single age group in the population (Fig. 5a) makes it difficult to accurately depict the growth curve for the sample to capture important details of the developmental process in ontogeny. However, this limitation can be overcome by using the individual development graph (Fig. 5b), which reveals the presence of cyclical elements in ontogeny. With a considerable amount of data analysed (> 1500 specimens), the proposed developmental scheme can be applied to study developmental periods and accurately estimate the age of *Flexopecten glaber* individuals with a high degree of confidence.

The maximum age of *Flexopecten glaber* individuals in the Black Sea remains uncertain due to the difficulty of interpreting growth lines on the shell edge in old individuals. The largest recorded individual in the Black Sea, with a height of 58.7 mm and length of 65.0 mm, was estimated to be four years old (Fig. 4h, Fig. 5b), and its size at 2+ years was 49 mm. However, larger 2-year-old individuals with a height of up to 57.1 mm (Fig. 5a) suggest that *F.*

glaber may reach even larger sizes in the Black Sea than previously noted. In the Mediterranean Sea, the age of 85-mm *F. glaber* individual was estimated to be 2+ years, suggesting that this may be the age limit for the species (Lykakis & Kalathakis, 1991). These results support the notion that the largest individuals are often relatively young but have a higher growth rate than those in the main part of the population. Therefore, it is important to recognise the potential error in using the method of calculating the age of individuals in a population based solely on the size and age of the largest individual (Zolotarev, 1989).

Conclusions

By comparing the growth stages and developmental cycles of valves and gonads in the ontogeny of *Flexopecten glaber*, correlations between these processes were discovered. The most prominent mark on the shell surface is formed mainly in winter as a result of the physiological restructuring of the organism before the beginning of the annual cycle of gonad formation. However, to determine the age of *F. glaber*, the spawning marks formed mainly in summer should be considered. The scheme for determining the individual age of *Flexopecten glaber* considered in our study can serve as a model for establishing this important biological indicator in related species of Pectinidae and some other Bivalvia.

The proposed scheme for determining the developmental stages and age of *Flexopecten glaber* individuals based on the morphology of their shell valves is a valuable tool for studying the species and can help resolve a variety of commercial, ecological and conservation issues. Moreover, it has the potential to contribute to the development of the theory of animal ontogeny.

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ЦИКЛИЧНОСТЬ В ОНТОГЕНЕЗЕ И ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВОЗРАСТА *FLEXOPECTEN GLABER* (BIVALVIA, PECTINIDAE) В ЧЕРНОМ МОРЕ

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Flexopecten glaber является объектом активного промысла в Средиземном море и перспективным видом для марикультуры в Черном море. *Flexopecten glaber* занесен в Красные книги Республики Крым и города Севастополя как вид, сокращающийся в численности (категория 2). В данном исследовании было проанализировано более 1500 особей, отобранных вблизи Крымского полуострова в период с 2017 по 2023 гг., с целью изучения онтогенеза *F. glaber* и разработки метода определения индивидуального возраста на основе взаимосвязи между стадиями развития гонад и изменениями морфологии поверхности раковины. Цикличность развития оценивали путем сопоставления циклов формирования гонад с особенностями морфологии поверхности раковины. Установлено соответствие между морфологией поверхности створок раковины и стадиями годового цикла развития гонад. На этой основе разработана схема определения стадий развития и индивидуального возраста особей *F. glaber* по морфологии створок раковины. Наиболее выраженная метка на поверхности раковины формируется преимущественно зимой в результате физиологической перестройки организма перед началом годового цикла формирования гонад. Однако для определения возраста особей *F. glaber* необходимо учитывать нерестовые отметины, формирующиеся преимущественно летом. Предложенная схема определения стадий развития и возраста особей *F. glaber* является ценным инструментом для изучения вида и может помочь в решении различных экологических и природоохранных вопросов.

Ключевые слова: годовой цикл, гонады, морской гребешок, морфология раковины, охраняемый вид

POPULATION, NESTING CHARACTERISTICS, AND BREEDING ECOLOGY OF THE CRITICALLY ENDANGERED *GYPS INDICUS* IN MUDUMALAI TIGER RESERVE, SOUTH INDIA

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The species extinction rate has recently accelerated worldwide and is a thousand times higher than through natural processes alone. Small, isolated populations are especially vulnerable to extinction due to deterministic and stochastic threats. Hence, the conservation of such populations is challenging. The present study from 2015 to 2021 aimed to understand the population, nesting characteristics, and breeding ecology of the country's southernmost population of *Gyps indicus* in Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, South India. The population estimation was performed on the roosting and nesting sites of *Gyps indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. To study the nesting characteristics and breeding ecology, each nesting colony was systematically visited four times per month during the breeding season (October to May). Assessments of threats were estimated during the field visits. In 2015–2021, four breeding sites were identified. Two nesting sites were identified in 2016 and two more in 2017 and 2020. The mean altitude of the nesting sites was 1122.25 ± 170.06 m a.s.l., ranging from 821 m a.s.l. to 1600 m a.s.l. In the Protected Area, two nests were located on east-facing exposure, one nest on southeast-facing exposure, and one nest on south-facing exposure. In terms of population composition, the mean number of adult individuals steadily increased from 9.5 ± 0.46 in 2016 to 14.08 ± 0.67 in 2021. Consequently, the mean total number of individuals per colony increased from 13.66 ± 0.56 in 2016 to 27.83 ± 0.62 in 2021. A total of 40 (in average, 6.66 ± 0.49 pairs/year) territorial pairs with occupied nests were observed in 2015–2021. Of them, 31 (in average, 5.16 ± 0.30 pairs/year) breeding pairs had laid eggs. Successful incubation was recorded, and the mean incubation period was 63.64 ± 1.74 days. Out of 31 incubated nests, 23 fledglings (3.83 ± 0.47 individuals/year) successfully came out with 74% breeding success. The entire nesting period was 128.43 ± 1.16 days. In total, out of 17 failed breeding attempts nine (53%) were detected before egg laying, and eight (47%) were found during incubation. There were no significant differences between nests abandoned before and after egg laying ($t = 0.4152$, $p > 0.05$). During the breeding seasons of 2015–2017, a human-made forest fire posed a serious threat to nesting colonies of *Gyps indicus*, resulting in no observed nesting. A species-specific conservation-oriented action programme is necessary to secure this last southernmost wild viable *Gyps indicus* population in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. At this juncture, we highly recommend declaring the buffer zone of the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve as a «Vulture Sanctuary» to provide a legal protection of the *Gyps indicus* population living in the studied area.

Key words: cliffs, colony, egg, fledgling, incubation, roosting, vulture

Introduction

In recent years, the extinction rate of species has increased worldwide and is a thousand times higher than through natural processes alone. Small, isolated populations are especially vulnerable to extinction (Sæther & Bakke, 2000) due to various threats (Boyce, 1992). The conservation of these populations is challenging (Young, 2000). Vultures are obligate scavengers and belong to the most threatened avian guild worldwide (Buechley & Şekercioğlu, 2016; McClure et al., 2021). A variety of factors, including contamination with veterinary pharmaceuticals (Oaks et al., 2004; Hernández & Margalida, 2008; Margalida et al., 2014), poisoning (Hernández & Margalida, 2008, 2009; Oro et al., 2008), habitat destruction (Thiollay, 2006), and low food availability (Thiollay, 2006; Margalida et al., 2010; Margalida & Colomer, 2012), combined with regulations and enactments (Camiña & Yosef, 2012), human persecution (Thiollay, 2006), collisions with wind turbines

(Carrete et al., 2012), electrocution and collisions with power lines (Boshoff et al., 2011), and anthropogenic disturbance (Morán-López et al., 2006), have contributed to the decline of vultures worldwide. During the late 1990s – early 2000s, populations of three *Gyps* species across southern Asia declined by more than 95% (Prakash, 1999; Gilbert et al., 2006; Prakash et al., 2003, 2012; Oaks et al., 2004). These populations were decimated by veterinary use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, particularly diclofenac (Oaks et al., 2004; Pain et al., 2008; Ogada et al., 2012; Margalida & Ogada, 2018). These drugs are nephrotoxic to birds and cause renal failure in vultures (Oaks et al., 2004). Six out of nine species of vultures found in India, have been facing the problem of existence and are, therefore, declared as threatened (Prakash et al., 2007). Of these, three species endemic to South Asia (*Gyps bengalensis* (Gmelin, 1788), *Gyps indicus* (Scopoli, 1786), and *Gyps tenuirostris* Gray, 1844) are at high

risk of global extinction and are listed as Critically Endangered because of rapid population declines within the last decade in the Indian subcontinent (Prakash et al., 2007).

Gyps indicus is one of the three native, resident *Gyps* species in India. It breeds in southeast Pakistan and peninsular India, south of the Gangetic plain, north to Delhi city, east through Madhya Pradesh state, south to the Nilgiris district, and occasionally further south (Collar et al., 2001). The species is classified as Critically Endangered (BirdLife International, 2021) because of a catastrophic decline of 90–98% in the population of *Gyps* species (Prakash et al., 2007) due to diclofenac poisoning (Gilbert et al., 2006; Green et al., 2004). Prakash et al. (2019) estimated the population to be c.12 000 individuals based on road transactions carried out in 2015. This roughly equates to 8000 mature individuals. It is placed in a band of 5000–15 000 mature individuals. It nests almost exclusively in colonies on cliffs and ruins (Naoroji, 2007), although in the deserts and grasslands of the Thar region (western India) they have been recorded as nesting on trees (Kulshreshtha, 2001). The breeding season of *G. indicus* is from October to May – June (Naoroji, 2007). Despite being a priority species for conservation, relatively little is known about their breeding and nesting ecology (Naoroji, 2007). In the southern Indian region, a small population of *G. indicus* in the Ramanagaram Hills of Karnataka and Nilgiri Forest Division in Tamil Nadu is known to remain in inland southern India, and it is rare elsewhere within its former range (Prakash et al., 2007; Venkitachalam & Senthilnathan, 2015, 2016). Regular monitoring breeding populations of threatened vultures is widely recognised as a priority to enable the effective implementation of targeted conservation actions in key areas across their ranges (Buechley et al., 2019; Santangeli et al., 2019).

This study was aimed to assess the population of *G. indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, Tamil Nadu, South India. To achieve this goal, the following objectives were outlined: to examine the nesting habitat characteristics of *G. indicus*, estimate the population structure within nesting colonies, analyse breeding ecology, identify conservation threats, and provide scientific management recommendations for long-term species conservation.

Material and Methods

Study area

Mudumalai Tiger Reserve (11.527828° – 11.716657° N, 76.367281° – 76.750001° E) is situ-

ated in the Western Ghats of South India (Fig. 1). Its area is 688.58 km². Mudumalai Tiger Reserve is bounded by Wayanad Wildlife Sanctuary on the west, Bandipur Tiger Reserve on the north, Nilgiris Forest Division on the south, and Sathiyamangalam Tiger Reserve on the east with an average altitude of 900–1000 m a.s.l. The perennial River Moyar flows eastwards in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. The climate has three marked seasons, namely a dry season (January – April), southwest monsoon (May – August), and northeast monsoon (September – December). The annual rainfall varies from 600 mm in the east to 2000 mm in the west. According to Champion & Seth (1968), the vegetation types in Mudumalai are classified into southern tropical dry thorn forest, southern tropical dry deciduous forest, southern tropical moist deciduous forest, southern tropical semi-evergreen forest, moist bamboo brakes, and riparian forest. Threats to this area include enormous biotic pressure (cattle grazing, cultivations, settlements, collection of fuel wood, non-timber forest products) exerted by the ever-expanding human population.

Breeding sites investigations

In 2015–2021, we found *Gyps indicus* nests by carrying out systematic searches in all areas taking into consideration appropriate for nesting individuals (cliffs, ravines, or large rocky outcrops). These territories were defined priorly based on topography and river systems within the study area (Fig. 1). The same areas were investigated each year, although some sites within the study area were added over the first few years of the study. Nests had remained observed with the use of 10 × 52 binoculars and a 25–75× 70 S3 spotting scope. Nests were identified by the presence of fresh nesting materials and whitewash (excreta) on the cliffs. Each nest was positioned using a GPS-receiver, and numerous photos of the nests and surrounding environment were taken to facilitate recognition of the exact location in subsequent years. A few environmental variables were collected to understand the selection of the nesting site. We categorised each nest as accessible or inaccessible to predators. Nest orientation, exposure, ledge type, and altitude were recorded because of their potential influence on the microclimatic conditions of the nest. We measured nest orientation with a compass. We extracted the information on the slope altitude, distances from neighbouring nesting sites as well as the nearest rivers, roads, and human habitation using Google Earth Pro 7.3.6 1.9345.

Fig 1. Study area with breeding sites of *Gyps indicus* in Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, South India.

Population estimation

The population estimation (72 visits) was done on the roosting and nesting sites of *G. indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve in 2016–2021. The roosting and nesting locations were confirmed. Population estimation was done once a month. We divided the age class of *G. indicus* individuals into three categories based on plumage characteristics, namely adults (> 5 years), sub-adults (2–4 years), and juveniles (< 2 years) (Naoraji, 2007). The population size of *G. indicus* was estimated by counting the individuals in the roosting and nesting sites during the early morning (from 06:30 h to 09:30 h) and late evening (from 17.30 h to 19.30 h) (Dobrev et al., 2020). We assumed fidelity of nesting sites, fixed time of roosting and geographic closure, and no movement into (immigration) or out of (emigration) sites to estimate population size (Samson & Ramakrishnan, 2020).

Breeding ecology and threats

To study the breeding ecology of *G. indicus*, each colony was visited once a week during the breeding season (October to May) to check the status and number of individuals present in each nest. All observations of nesting colonies were made from a distance of 300–600 m from the breeding cliffs. The focal animal sampling method (Altmann, 1974) was used to monitor the status and behaviour of *G. indicus* in nesting colonies (Postupalsky, 1974; Acharya et al., 2009). An active breeding pair (breeding pair) was defined as one that laid an egg, and a non-breeding pair (territorial pair) was confirmed that occupied the nest at least for three weeks but did not lay any eggs (Fernández et al., 1998). Breeding success was calculated based on the number of fledglings divided by the number of

breeding pairs, which had laid eggs. During each visit, active nests were considered occupied by a pair only when a single or two adult vultures were observed in the nest, i.e. one standing and one incubating or one incubating adult was present or one adult with a chick or a young chick alone was presented in the nest. A colony was considered active, only if it contained at least one active nest with an egg (Xirouchakis & Mylonas, 2005; Xirouchakis, 2010). Threat assessments, such as human pressure, predator threat, and man-made threats, were estimated during the field visits.

Results

In 2015–2021, four breeding colonies of *G. indicus* were identified in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. Two of these four nesting sites were identified in 2016, and two more were recorded in 2017 and 2020, respectively. Notably, all nesting sites located on rock cliffs were entirely inaccessible to both humans and wild animals, whether from the ground or the cliff top. The mean altitude of the nesting sites was 1122.25 ± 170.06 m a.s.l, ranging from 821 m a.s.l to 1600 m a.s.l. On nesting sites, the average slope exposure was $37.78^\circ \pm 0.50^\circ$, ranging from 28.37° to 41.99° . On the east exposure, 50% of the nests were located, 25% on the south east-facing exposure and 25% on the south-facing exposure. The nesting habitat ledges comprised an equal distribution between open and closed types, with 50% classified as open-type ledges and 50% as closed-type ledges.

On average, nest sites were located at 2.59 ± 0.30 km from water sources. 75% of the observed nest sites were situated within 2.5 ± 0.45 km of water bodies, and one nest site was located at 3.58 km from the nearest water body. The average distance between a given nest site and its closest neighbour was 11.40 ± 2.15 km. A half of the observed nest sites were within 6.58 ± 1.21 km of a neighbouring site, while all sites were within 18 km from each other. On average, nest sites were located at 3.76 ± 0.32 km away from human settlements; all sites were situated within 3.25 ± 0.49 km. 81% of the nest sites were located less than 4 km from human settlements. 66% of the recorded nest sites within 2.40 ± 0.37 km away of the road network. Furthermore, nest sites were less than 30.25 ± 1.24 km from major towns, while all sites being at least 20.59 ± 1.19 km away from large urban areas.

Table 1 summarises data on the number of colonies, visits, and the mean number of adult,

sub-adult, and juvenile individuals of *Gyps indicus* observed in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve in 2016–2021. Over the study period, the number of colonies increased from two to four, by reflecting the expansion of nesting sites. The total number of visits remained constant at 12 per year throughout the study duration.

Regarding the population composition, the mean number of adults increased steadily from 9.5 ± 0.46 individuals in 2016 to 14.08 ± 0.67 individuals in 2021. Similarly, the mean number of sub-adults showed a consistent increase, reaching 7.25 ± 0.17 individuals by 2021. The t-test results comparing sub-adult and adult populations revealed a statistically significant difference ($t = 7.546$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates a notable distinction between the sub-adult and adult populations within the nesting colonies. Juvenile individuals also displayed an increasing trend, with their mean number escalating from 2.16 ± 0.27 individuals in 2016 to 6.5 ± 0.15 individuals in 2021. Consequently, the total mean number of individuals per colony increased from 13.66 ± 0.56 individuals in 2016 to 27.83 ± 0.62 individuals in 2021. The ANOVA test resulted for the nesting colony population across study years showed a statistical significance ($F = 34.08$, $p < 0.001$). This indicates that there is a significant variation in the population trends within nesting colonies across the study years. During the breeding season, breeding populations exhibited a

significant increase, highlighting a notable disparity between breeding and non-breeding populations within nesting colonies ($t = 8.246$, $p < 0.001$).

A total of 40 territorial pairs, averaging 6.66 ± 0.49 pairs per year, with occupied nests were observed between 2015 and 2021 (Table 2). Among these, 31 breeding pairs, averaging 5.16 ± 0.30 pairs per year, successfully laid eggs, with a noted incubation period of 63.6 ± 1.7 days. Out of the 31 incubated nests, 23 fledglings (in average, 3.83 ± 0.47 individuals per year) successfully fledged from the nest, resulting in a breeding success rate of 74%. The total nestling period was calculated as 128.4 ± 1.16 days. The highest breeding success rate (83%) was observed in the breeding seasons of 2019–2020 and 2020–2021, indicating a considerable progress in *Gyps indicus* breeding success in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve over the study years.

Significant differences were noted in the increase of the number of nests 2015 to 2021 between the occupied and incubated nests ($t = 6.70$, $p < 0.01$), as well as between an incubated and hatched nests ($t = 6.325$, $p < 0.001$). Fledging success was found to be significantly correlated with hatching success ($r = 1.00$, $p < 0.001$), and the incubation was significantly correlated with hatching success ($r = 0.95$, $p < 0.01$). No significant variability was recorded in breeding success and productivity over the study years ($F = 2.012$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 1. The characteristics of *Gyps indicus* population in 2016–2021 in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, South India

Number of colonies	Years	Number of visits	Adult individuals	M ± SE	Sub-adult individuals	M ± SE	Juvenile individuals	M ± SE	Total number of individuals	M ± SE
2	2016	12	114	9.50 ± 0.46	24	2.00 ± 0.27	26	2.16 ± 0.27	164	13.66 ± 0.56
3	2017	12	133	11.08 ± 0.39	34	2.83 ± 0.11	46	3.83 ± 0.24	213	17.75 ± 0.41
3	2018	12	132	11.00 ± 0.40	46	3.83 ± 0.35	61	5.08 ± 0.22	239	19.91 ± 0.57
3	2019	12	139	11.58 ± 0.45	58	4.83 ± 0.11	69	5.75 ± 0.13	266	22.16 ± 0.44
4	2020	12	158	13.16 ± 0.62	70	5.83 ± 0.29	72	5.91 ± 0.11	298	24.83 ± 0.66
4	2021	12	169	14.08 ± 0.67	87	7.25 ± 0.17	78	6.50 ± 0.15	334	27.83 ± 0.62

Note: M – average value, SE – standard error.

Table 2. Reproductive performance of *Gyps indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve (South India) in 2015–2021

Number of colonies	Years	Territorial pairs	Breeding pairs (clutches)	Successful pairs (fledglings)	Nesting rate, %	Breeding success	Productivity	Abandoned nests
2	2015–2016	5	4	2	80	0.50	0.40	3
3	2016–2017	6	5	3	83	0.60	0.50	3
3	2017–2018	6	5	4	83	0.80	0.67	2
3	2018–2019	7	5	4	71	0.80	0.57	3
4	2019–2020	8	6	5	75	0.83	0.63	3
4	2020–2021	8	6	5	75	0.83	0.63	3
In total:		40	31	23	78	0.74	0.58	17
M ± SE		6.66 ± 0.49	5.16 ± 0.30	3.83 ± 0.47	77.83 ± 2.00	0.72 ± 0.05	0.56 ± 0.04	2.83 ± 0.16

Note: M – average value, SE – standard error.

Breeding failures occurred at various stages of the breeding cycle, with the highest proportion of nest failures occurring before the egg-laying stage. Out of a total of 17 failed breeding attempts, nine (53%) attempts were detected before egg laying, and eight (47%) during the incubation period. There was no significant difference observed between nests abandoned before and after egg laying ($t = 0.415$, $p > 0.05$). The analysis of nest abandonment across the studied years revealed a significant difference in month-wise distribution ($H = 5.84$, $p < 0.05$). The abandoned nests were observed in November (ten nests; 59%) and December (seven nests; 41%). Additionally, a significant difference was observed between the number of occupied and abandoned nests ($t = 8.032$, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Raptor populations are limited by the availability of breeding habitats at microscale level (Bever & Flather, 1999). However, macrohabitat characteristics, such as vegetation cover type, topography, human pressure, availability and accessibility of prey are important components in nesting habitat selection (Sergio et al., 2004; Kudo et al., 2005; Rodriguez-Lado & Tapia, 2012). The present study highlights the suitability of the eastern side of the rocky mountainous structures in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve as an optimal breeding habitat for *Gyps indicus*. The nesting colonies in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve were inaccessible to humans as well as terrestrial predators, contributing to their protection and breeding success. The physical characteristics of nesting sites play a crucial role in determining the breeding success by influencing predation risk (Martin, 1993; Verlando & Márquez, 2002; Mainwaring et al., 2014). Specifically, hidden nests or those situated on locations inaccessible to terrestrial predators tend to have higher breeding success rates (Mallory & Forbes, 2011; Haynes et al., 2014; Anderson et al., 2015).

Sunshine and slope orientation appeared to be of low importance in the case of *Aegypius monachus* (Linnaeus, 1766) (Mihoub et al., 2013), but aspects of the cliff location play a role in nest site selection. For example, *Gyps fulvus* (Hablizl, 1783) generally prefers western and southern exposures of slopes due to a larger amount of sunshine (Marinković et al., 2012). Although the present study revealed the use of almost all aspects for nest building, the west and north slopes were the least preferred aspects. As expected, 50% of the nests were located on eastern exposure, 25% on southeast exposure, and 25% on southern exposure. This orientation provides more sunshine for chicks

in a colder climate and typically maintains congenial atmospheric temperatures compared to western- and northern-facing locations. A similar observation was made in the *Gyps indicus* population in Protected Areas of Madhya Pradesh, Central India (Jha et al., 2021). Venkitachalam & Senthilnathan (2015) found that 50% of the nests were located on north-facing exposures, 16% on east-facing exposures, and 17% on south and southeast-facing exposures in the Moyar Valley, Tamil Nadu, India. In some other studies (e.g. Vlachos et al., 1998; Liberatori & Penteriani, 2001; Şen et al., 2017), the southern aspect was preferred, possibly, due to the sunlight availability (Carlson, 1992). The present study also revealed that the preferred nesting site altitude was between 821 m a.s.l. and 1600 m a.s.l. Jha et al. (2021) found that *Gyps indicus* and *Neophron percnopterus* (Linnaeus, 1758) showed preferences for nesting sites ranging from 56 m a.s.l. to 169 m a.s.l. in Protected Areas of Madhya Pradesh, Central India. This indicates that altitude is linked to local topography rather than a species-specific requirement (Mihoub et al., 2013). Notably, the same nests were consistently utilised by *Gyps indicus* throughout the study period in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. Some studies have observed that constructed nests are re-used for years or even decades by the same birds, gradually increasing in size with each breeding season (Rasmussen & Anderton, 2005; Kushwaha & Kanaujia, 2009; Vergara et al., 2010).

In the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, factors contributing to disturbance, such as the average distance to roads and villages (2 km and 4 km, respectively), were notably far away from the nesting habitats. Most road networks have a very low traffic intensity due to the Protected Area status, although the State Highway passing through the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve exhibited a high traffic intensity. Consequently, their impact on vultures remains minimal. However, nesting vultures are highly sensitive to disturbance, to the extent that increased activity along roads may lead to nest site desertion (Bridgeford & Bridgeford, 2003; Monadjem & Garcelon, 2005). In contrast, *Gyps bengalensis*, *G. indicus*, *Sarcogyps calvus* (Scopoli, 1786) and *Neophron percnopterus* have been observed foraging around human settlements (Thakur & Narang, 2012; Samson & Ramakrishnan, 2016, 2020). Similar associations have been documented for other species, such as *Gyps bengalensis*, *Necrosyrtes monachus* (Temminck, 1823), and *Neophron percnopterus* in various parts of the world (Henriques et al., 2018).

Despite the crucial role of water in a vulture survival (Fergusons-Lees & Christie, 2001; Naoroji,

2007), information regarding the vulture nest proximity to water bodies is scarce. In the present study, the distance of *Gyps indicus* nests to water bodies is a few kilometres, indicating that vegetation suitability is prioritised over the water proximity. Jha et al. (2021) observed larger vulture congregations near water bodies and smaller populations at a higher distance from them in Protected Areas of Madhya Pradesh, Central India. Wagley et al. (2020) found that river banks are favourable areas for wild animal carcasses, providing enough food for vultures and increasing the food availability. Moreover, the presence of active and occupied nests near water sources allows the species and their offspring convenient access to water after feeding on carrion. Thakur & Narang (2012) also noted that most nest sites were located near water sources, while Ghimire (2016) observed nests on forest edges in a close proximity to water sources. Ramakrishnan et al. (2014) confirmed the importance of water for vulture nesting, emphasising its significance for all living organisms. Samson et al. (2014) highlighted the importance of waterholes as decisive factors for vulture conservation within their habitat range, a finding supported by similar observations elsewhere. *Gyps africanus* Salvadori, 1865 are known to prefer riparian vegetation for nesting (Monadjem, 2001; Monadjem & Garcelon, 2005), although this preference may vary in the absence of such vegetation (Tarboton & Allan, 1984; Monadjem & Garcelon, 2005).

In the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, the population trend of *Gyps indicus* exhibited significant growth over the study years. Particularly, the number of adult and sub-adult individuals showed a notable association, indicating a promising trend in the survival and transition of sub-adults to adults within the *Gyps indicus* population in the Protected Area. Population variations were observed between breeding and non-breeding seasons, a pattern also noted in studies of Baral et al. (2005) and Samson & Ramakrishnan (2020), investigated *Gyps bengalensis* populations in Nepal and India. This observed variation could be attributed to the behaviour of adult birds during non-breeding seasons, as they tend to fly far away in search for food and may not return to nesting colonies at the same day (Rabenold, 1987). Consequently, the maximum number of vultures was observed in and around nesting colonies only during breeding period in contrast with non-breeding seasons. It was noted that the number of *Gyps indicus* individuals in the population slightly increased during the breeding season compared to the non-breeding season. This phenomenon may suggest a

high survival rate among the birds and/or an influx of non-breeding birds from other areas. However, further investigations are needed to confirm this.

The timing of the breeding and nesting season of *Gyps indicus*, observed in this study from October to May, is consistent with earlier studies (Naoroji, 2007; Misher et al., 2017). *Gyps indicus* lay their eggs in November, i.e. at the beginning of the winter season in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, which is at the end of the rainy season. The incubation takes place in November and December and eggs are being hatched in January. These findings strongly support the suggestion that the egg-laying in *Gyps* genus is generally triggered at the end of the rainy season, irrespective of the latitude (Mundy et al., 1992). Newton (1979) observed that normally the breeding chronology in raptors varies according to the geographic area and is largely defined by food availability and weather conditions. In the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, nesting colonies of *Gyps indicus* are relatively small in number compared to the whole population, and breeding success varies depending on the colony. Some studies suggest that breeding success in group-living birds may be influenced by the colony size (Hunt et al., 1986; Barbosa et al., 1997; Brunton, 1997, 1999; Weaver & Brown, 2005). Furthermore, the optimal group size depends on the definition of fitness (Sibly, 1983; Giraldeau & Gillis, 1985; Kramer, 1985).

During the breeding seasons, spanning from 2016 to 2021, a total of 40 occupied nests, including 31 active nests and 23 chicks, were observed in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, resulting in a breeding success rate of 74%. The average incubation period was recorded at 63.6 ± 1.7 days, while the nestling period was observed to be 128.4 ± 1.16 days in the Protected Area. These findings are consistent with those reported by Misher et al. (2017), observed an incubation period at 62.5 ± 1.5 days and a nestling period of 129.4 ± 1.0 days along the River Chambal in Rajasthan, India. However, the study of Ravikanth & Baskaran (2023) showed that the incubation period ranged at 53–55 days with a mean of 54 ± 1 days, while the observed nestling period was 103 ± 2 days in the Kaghaznagar Forest Division and its adjoining areas on the Deccan Plateau, India.

In the southern Indian states of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, and Telangana, there are only a few number of *Gyps indicus* populations. Venkitachalam & Senthilnathan (2015) reported four breeding pairs and nesting site characteristics of *Gyps indicus* in the Moyar Valley ecosystem, Tamil Nadu, India. Additionally, Samson & Ramakrishnan (2018) recorded an additional nesting site of *G. indicus* in

the Moyar Valley ecosystem with successful breeding. Subramanya & Naveein (2006) documented ten adults of *Gyps indicus* with three occupied nests, resulting in a 75% breeding success rate in the Ramanagaram hills, Karnataka state, India. A recent study of Padma (2018) reported 253 sightings of *Gyps indicus* in 76 visits, with an average of 3.3 vultures per visit in the Ramadevarabetta Vulture Sanctuary over 2015–2017. However, all three nests observed during the breeding seasons of 2015–2017 were unsuccessful. Srinivasulu et al. (2009) observed a total of 17 *Gyps indicus* emerging from nearby rocky outcrops in the Adoni area of the Nagarjunasagar-Srisailem Tiger Reserve, Andhra Pradesh state, India. Stotrabhashyam et al. (2015) documented nesting sites of *Gyps indicus* in the Southern Indian region, with a particular focus on Palarapu Cliffs, Bijjur Reserve Forest, Telangana state, India. Ravikanth & Ram Mohan (2016) reported 19 adults and ten occupied nests with eight chicks, resulting at 80% breeding success rate in Palarapu Cliff, Telangana state, India. Considering the northern part of India, Chhangani (2004) observed that 92 nests of *Gyps indicus* with eggs had chicks from October 1999 to April 2000 at various nesting sites. The nesting success, determined from egg laying to fledging was 90%. Gurjar & Gawande (2011) found eight nests accounting for eight chicks with 100% breeding success on *Gyps indicus* in the Panna Tiger Reserve, Madhya Pradesh state, India. Misher et al. (2017) recorded 22 nests with 17 active ones, of which 16 were successfully hatched (94%) and 14 chicks were successfully fledged (82.25%) out from the nest of *Gyps indicus* in Gapernath, River Chambal, Rajasthan state, India. Chishty & Choudhary (2020) recorded that in the first observation year (July 2017 – June 2018), a successful breeding rate of 60% was recorded. Of the five nests, in three nests successfully developed the chicks and were able to fly while two nests were a failure. In the second year (July 2018 – August 2019), the successful breeding rate was 20% only. In one nest the chick developed successfully and it was able to fly, while the other four nests failed (Chishty & Choudhary, 2020). McClure et al. (2021) observed that *Gyps indicus* had 2397 potential nesting ledges, of which 1183 (49.4%) were in the Rajasthan state and 1214 (50.6%) in Madhya Pradesh state. Of them, 686 (58%) and 723 (60%) ones were occupied at least once in Rajasthan state and Madhya Pradesh state, respectively. Ravikanth & Baskaran (2023) studied the breeding ecology of *Gyps indicus* at Palarapu Cliffs in Kaghaznagar and Sironcha Forest Divisions in 2010–2021. The study documented 84

nests with 58 successfully hatched chicks, resulting in a breeding success rate of 65%.

In the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, all nesting colonies were located quite far away from human habitation on top of cliffs. Thus, both human pressure and terrestrial predators did not pose a threatening factor to the *Gyps indicus* population. Only the largest eagles and vultures were relatively free from predation pressure, although their nests may occasionally be assaulted by carnivores (Tapia & Zuberogoitia, 2018). Forest fires, particularly those caused by humans, posed a serious threat to one of the nesting colonies of *G. indicus* during the years of 2015–2016 and 2016–2017, resulting in no nesting being observed during the breeding seasons. Forest fires, especially those of human origin, represent a significant threat to the *Gyps indicus* population in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. Andalus (1993) observed that forest fires destroyed nests of *Coragyps atratus* (Bechstein, 1793) with chicks in Spain, indicating a potential threat to the only Balkan colony located in Greece.

Conclusions

The present study indicates an increase in the population of *Gyps indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve, India, during 2015–2021. Forest fires posed a serious threat to the nesting colonies of this species. Based on these findings, we suggest continuous monitoring of the population and breeding status of *Gyps indicus* in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve as it is crucial for understanding the population trend of the species. A species-specific conservation-oriented action programme is necessary to secure this last southernmost wild viable *Gyps indicus* population in the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve. At this juncture, we highly recommend declaring the buffer zone of the Mudumalai Tiger Reserve as a «Vulture Sanctuary» to provide legal protection to the *Gyps indicus* population living in this area.

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ПОПУЛЯЦИЯ, ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГНЕЗДОВАНИЯ И ЭКОЛОГИЯ РАЗМНОЖЕНИЯ НАХОДЯЩЕГОСЯ ПОД УГРОЗОЙ ИСЧЕЗНОВЕНИЯ *Gyps indicus* В ТИГРОВИМ ЗАПОВЕДНИКЕ МУДУМАЛАЙ, ЮЖНАЯ ИНДИЯ

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В последнее время скорость вымирания видов увеличилась во всем мире и во много раз выше, чем в результате воздействия только естественных процессов. Небольшие изолированные популяции наиболее уязвимы перед процессом вымирания ввиду обусловленных и случайных угроз. Поэтому сохранение таких популяций является сложной задачей. Настоящее исследование, проведенное с 2015 по 2021 гг. в Тигровом заповеднике Мудумалай (юг Индии), было направлено на изучение популяции, особенностей гнездования и экологии размножения самой южной в стране популяции *Gyps indicus*. Оценка численности особей проводилась на местах ночевки и гнездования *Gyps indicus* в Тигровом заповеднике Мудумалай. Для изучения особенностей гнездования и экологии размножения каждую гнездовую колонию систематически посещали четыре раза в месяц в течение сезона размножения (октябрь – май). Оценки угроз оценивались в ходе выездов на места обитания вида. За период 2015–2021 гг. было выявлено четыре гнездовых участка. Два из них были выявлены в 2016 г. и еще по одному в 2017 г. и 2020 г. Гнездовья располагались в среднем на высоте 1122.25 ± 170.06 м н.у.м., в пределах от 821 м н.у.м. до 1600 м н.у.м. На территории исследования два гнезда располагались на склонах восточной экспозиции, одно – на склоне юго-восточной экспозиции и одно – на склоне южной экспозиции. В отношении состава популяции средняя численность взрослых особей возросла с 9.5 ± 0.46 в 2016 г. до 14.08 ± 0.67 в 2021 г. Следовательно, среднее значение общей численности особей в колонии увеличилось с 13.66 ± 0.56 в 2016 г. до 27.83 ± 0.62 в 2021 г. В общей сложности в 2015–2021 гг. наблюдалось 40 (в среднем 6.66 ± 0.49 пар/год) территориальных пар с занятыми гнездами. Из них 31 (в среднем 5.16 ± 0.30 пар/год) гнездящаяся пара отложила яйца. Было отмечено успешное высидывание яиц со средним инкубационным периодом в 63.64 ± 1.74 дня. Из 31 гнезда с кладками 23 птенца (3.83 ± 0.47 особей/год) успешно вышли из гнезда; успех размножения составил 74%. Полный период гнездования составил 128.43 ± 1.16 суток. Из 17 неудачных попыток гнездования девять (53%) были обнаружены до откладки яиц, а восемь (47%) – во время периода высидывания яиц. Статистически значимых различий между количеством гнезд, покинутыми до и после откладки яиц, не было выявлено ($t = 0.4152$, $p > 0.05$). В сезоны размножения в 2015–2017 гг. серьезную угрозу нескольким гнездовым колониям *Gyps indicus* представляли лесные пожары антропогенного происхождения, в результате чего гнездования там не наблюдалось. Для сохранения изученной единственной сохранившейся и самой южной жизнеспособной популяции *Gyps indicus* в Тигровом заповеднике Мудумалай необходима программа действий, ориентированная на сохранение данного вида. В этой связи рекомендуется представить охранную зону Тигрового заповедника Мудумалай в качестве «Заказника грифов» («Vulture Sanctuary») для обеспечения легальной охраны популяции *Gyps indicus*, обитающей на территории исследования.

Ключевые слова: высидывание, гнездование, гриф, колония, птенец, скалы, яйцо

OPTIMISING *JUNIPERUS EXCELSA* (CUPRESSACEAE) GERMINATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ECOSYSTEM RESTORATION IN THE PRESPA AREA (WESTERN MACEDONIA, GREECE)

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In the Mediterranean Region, species of the genus *Juniperus* face conservation challenges due to human activities and climate change threats. *Juniperus* species are reported to present low regeneration rate, while their seeds often exhibit physical and physiological dormancy. Viability and germination of mature *Juniperus excelsa* seeds from population originating from the Prespa area (Florina, Greece), alongside with seedling survival were investigated to study the reproduction dynamic of species population known to represent a EU priority habitat type of limited distribution and with low regeneration rate. The seed cut test of an uncleaned seed lot revealed a high percentage of empty seeds (90.03%) and a low embryo viability (2%). Cleaned seeds were subjected to a total of 44 pretreatments, categorised into eight groups targeting physical and physiological dormancy, along with combinations of these techniques. Despite most treatments showing limited success in enhancing germination, three pretreatments exhibited promising results (germination between 22.22% and 39.40%). Subsequent germination tests involving these treatments in controlled chambers, as well as in field conditions, along with hydration-dehydration cycles, were conducted using newly collected seeds. Seed germination rates in controlled chambers remained low, suggesting a deep primary dormancy. Pretreated seeds, under controlled field conditions, passed two winter periods fully saturated, with 13 hydrating-dehydrating cycles in-between. Germination was maximised during the second year of the field experiment, reaching almost 100% after mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by immersion in 3% H₂O₂ for 2 h. However, seedling survival was low, reaching approximately 38.26%. The findings emphasise the challenges in germinating *Juniperus excelsa* seeds and highlight the importance of the optimised protocols for reforestation in order to conserve this habitat type.

Key words: climate resilience, Greek juniper restoration, seedling production, seedling survival, embryo viability, hydration-dehydration

Introduction

Juniperus species have a high ecological, cultural, and economic importance in the Mediterranean region. However, they are facing conservation threats due to habitat loss, over-logging, forest fires and other human activities (Ciesla, 2002; Carus, 2004; Giannakis et al., 2010). Moreover, their conservation is further challenged by projected climate change scenarios threats (Fatemi et al., 2018). This is recorded for several Mediterranean *Juniperus* species, such as *Juniperus thurifera* L., *J. communis* L., *J. excelsa* M.Bieb., and *J. foetidissima* Wild. (Vrahnakis et al., 2011; Broome et al., 2017).

Germinating seeds of *Juniperus* species is a crucial and challenging aspect for ecosystem restoration. Successful germination and subsequent growth of seedlings, which can then be reintroduced into their natural degraded habitats, contribute to their restoration. Many *Juniperus* species have seeds with a low viability (Wesche et al., 2005) or specific germination requirements (Broome, 2003). Understanding and addressing these requirements are critical to develop effective

methods for breaking dormancy and successful germination.

In general, *Juniperus* species, including *Juniperus excelsa*, present a high proportion of empty seeds (Juan et al., 2006; Bonner, 2008; Gruwez et al., 2014; Pinna et al., 2014). This is probably due either to sub-optimal climatic conditions (Hedhly et al., 2009; Verheyen et al., 2009), which affect pollination, or due to inbreeding depression amongst the fragmented populations (García & Zamora, 2003; Castilleja-Sánchez et al., 2016). Moreover, seed viability of the genus *Juniperus* is generally low (García & Zamora, 2003) and it is intricately linked to ecological factors, and habitat suitability, and thus, it is minimised in the outer distribution limits or its geographical boundaries, beyond which the species is less likely to thrive due to environmental constraints (García et al., 2000).

Seeds of *Juniperus* species are under a strong combination of physical and physiological dormancy caused by both hard testa and embryo immaturity, which requires some time to develop (after-ripening) before germination (Baskin & Baskin,

2001; Bonner, 2008). The outer layer of the seed coat results in physical dormancy, while chemical components in the embryo cause physiological dormancy, both of which prevent seed germination (Tilki, 2007). Usually, seeds with such a complex type of dormancy require long periods of stratification in order to germinate (Baskin & Baskin, 2001; Feurtado & Kermode, 2011).

However, germination can be highly improved through pretreatments that can release seed dormancy. Seed coat-imposed dormancy is a type of dormancy, in which the seed coat restricts water uptake and prevents the embryo from germinating. Several pretreatments are proposed to overcome this, such as mechanical or chemical scarification and hot water (Piotto et al., 2003). Sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid are the most commonly used acids for chemical scarification (Hartmann et al., 2010), while hydrogen peroxide is also referred. Both sulfuric and hydrochloric acids can act as scarifiers by softening hard seed coats, promoting water absorption and enhancing germination (Baskin & Baskin, 2001). Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) also plays a role in scarification, but its action is more complex. Although it can contribute to scarification of the seed coat tissues, its multifaceted role extends beyond scarification. When dissolved, it releases oxygen promoting cellular respiration and providing the energy required for germination. It can also act as a signaling molecule, potentially triggering the activity of enzymes involved in breaking down inhibitors present in the seed or initiating biochemical changes necessary for germination (Fontaine et al., 1994; Liu et al., 2010; Wojtyla et al., 2016; Gammoudi et al., 2021). Hot water treatment of seeds with hard or impermeable seed coats is also a method used in scarification to break seed dormancy and enhance germination (Hartmann et al., 2010).

On the other hand, overcoming physiological dormancy typically involves specific treatments to trigger the necessary physiological changes for germination such as cold-moist stratification or two periods of cold stratification separated by warm stratification or hormone application (Grzesik & Joustra, 1990; Broome, 2003; Daneshvar et al., 2016). Plant hormones can be used to promote or enhance seed germination. Gibberellic acid is often used to overcome dormancy in seeds with hard coats. It stimulates the synthesis of enzymes that break down stored nutrients in the seed, facilitating the mobilisation of reserves and promoting the growth of the embryo (Gupta & Chakrabarty, 2013).

Hydration-dehydration cycles play also a crucial role in breaking seed dormancy in many plant species (Hegarty, 1978). These cycles mimic natural environmental conditions, particularly the fluctuation in soil moisture levels that seeds experience in their native habitats. The process of hydration and dehydration involves the uptake and loss of water by seeds, triggering physiological changes that lead to the breaking of dormancy and the initiation of germination. Natural environmental conditions, such as seasonal changes, rain, and dry periods, often contribute to these hydration-dehydration cycles. The seeds may go through several cycles before dormancy is fully broken (Bai et al., 2015).

The Lake Prespa basin is one of the few areas in the Balkan Peninsula with well-preserved forests of *Juniperus excelsa* that form the *9562 «Grecian juniper woods (*Juniperetum excelsae*)» (GJWs), an EU-priority habitat type of limited distribution. Vrahnakis et al. (2011), in the frame of LIFE12 NAT/GR/539 project, documented the near absence of natural regeneration in the Lake Prespa *Juniperus excelsa* forests.

The current research targeted in clarifying the key factors influencing the seed biology of *Juniperus excelsa*. The outcomes of this investigation have significant implications for the ecological restoration efforts of its population within its natural habitat. The aim of the paper was to investigate the reproduction dynamics of a Greek *J. excelsa* population, known to represent a priority habitat type where natural regeneration is found to be rather low. Furthermore, the results of the study can be useful for national forest services to follow the protocols developed in the study and to produce seedlings for targeted plantings.

Material and Methods

Study area

The Greek juniper woods cover an area of 21.921 km² in Greece, situated at an altitude ranging from 900–1300 m a.s.l., on various exposures and inclines. The forest features a loose structure with an open crown canopy predominantly composed of *Juniperus excelsa* (Vrahnakis et al., 2011). Occasionally, these woods form poorly developed shrublands. The trees reach a maximum height of 20 m and a diameter at breast height (DBH) of 1.5–2.5 m in mature specimens. The primary branches spread out or ascend and become crooked in older trees, while the higher-order branches in younger trees are generally more ascending. The crown of young trees is broad-pyramidal, becoming broader as the trees mature.

Berry-shaped cones were collected from a natural population of *Juniperus excelsa* located in the area of Prespa, Florina, Greece (21.0191° N, 40.8254° E). These cones were harvested in early September from mature trees, approximately 10 m in height, from 50 trial plots (10 × 10 m, one tree was selected in each plot) scattered throughout the juniper forests to represent the total population. The trees were grown in the same altitudinal zone. The trial plots were spaced approximately 325 m apart to cover most of the study population. A total of 50 parental trees were selected as the seed source, and seeds were collected (Ivetić et al., 2016). Seed germination was monitored for two years, from 2016 to 2018.

Experimental procedures

The collected cones were slightly cut with a scalpel and placed for two days in tap water changed twice a day. Afterwards, the fleshy part was removed and seeds were collected. A batch of seeds from all trees (equal number of 100 seeds per tree from 50 trees in total) were mixed and formed a composite sample, which was shaken many times in a bucket in order to distribute the seeds evenly and randomly inside the sample. The initial seed moisture content (26.8%) was calculated according to ISTA (1999) specifications. A seed cut test was further performed according to ISTA (1999) in order to assess the internal characteristics of seeds quality. The test involved cutting seeds open and making observations to distinguish various categories based on their internal features. Three distinct seed categories were distinguished, namely empty, filled with resin, and seeds with fully developed embryo.

A viability test was also performed using 1% (w/v) of 2,3,5-Triphenyl-tetrazolium chloride (hereinafter – TTC). Characterisation of embryos as viable (hereinafter – stained) and non-viable (hereinafter – unstained) was performed by taking into account ISTA (1999) specifications (Fig. 1).

The rest of the initial seed lot (individually per tree) was subjected to a cleaning procedure through air blowing followed by imbibition in tap water for the empty seeds to remove. Then, an equal number of 150 cleaned seeds per tree were chosen and the new composite sample was re-shaken inside the bucket again many times for creating a uniform seed distribution.

A total of 44 pretreatments (including a control), were employed to overcome seed dormancy, categorised into eight distinct groups. The purpose

of these pretreatment groups was to elucidate the type of seed dormancy and explore methods to enhance germination rates. All the seeds used in germination experiments have been surface sterilised for 2 min., with 1% (v/v) sodium hypochlorite and thoroughly washed.

These pretreatments included mechanical and chemical scarification, to overcome physical dormancy, with diverse acids and durations, and varying stratification periods, as well as stratification, hormone applications and hydrating-dehydrating cycles to address physiological dormancy. Additionally, combinations of these techniques were employed to target the combination of both dormancy types. In addition to the aforementioned pretreatments, the study was aimed to explore the impact of high temperature and smoke as cues for germination related to forest fire. These factors were examined both individually and in various combinations (Table 1).

Following this, a standard germination test was conducted in a germination chamber (SANYO Inc., Japan), with alternating temperatures of +25°C/+15°C for 8 h in light and 16 h in darkness. The outcomes of the pretreatments were largely disappointing, with less than 5% germination observed over an 8-month period. However, three pretreatments showed promise, exhibiting a 20–30% germination percentage: i) Mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by a 2 h. immersion in 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) (abbreviated as MSH); ii) Immersion in 10% hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h. (abbreviated as HW); iii) Immersion in 10% hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm gibberellic acid (GA₃) (abbreviated as HGA) for 48 h.

Fig. 1. *Juniperus excelsa* embryos after staining with 1% (w/v) 2,3,5-Triphenyl-tetrazolium chloride.

Table 1. Groups of treatments in *Juniperus excelsa* seeds before they were placed for germination

№	Group of pretreatments	Description
1	Mechanical scarification	Seed mechanical scarification for 4 sec. or 6 sec. using mechanical scarifier.
2	Chemical scarification	Immersion of seeds in various chemical solvents separately (not in combination) as follows: Sulfuric acid (H ₂ SO ₄) (98%) for 30 min. and 45 min. respectively; Hydrochloric acid (HCl) (37%) for 20 min., 40 min., and 60 min., respectively; Hydrogen peroxide (H ₂ O ₂) in two distinct concentrations 3% or 5% (v/v) for 2 h.
3	Stratification	Seeds were subjected to either warm (two months duration) or cold (three months duration) stratification as well as to combined cold-warm and cold-warm-cold stratification for the same intervals as above.
4	Hormone treatments	Imbibition for 48 h. in 400 ppm of gibberellic acid (GA ₃) under dark.
5	Combination of each of the treatments №1, №2, and №3 with treatment №4	Combination of scarification treatment and imbibition in GA ₃ treatment as above.
6	Hydrating-dehydrating cycles	Seeds immersion in tap water for four days, then left to dry for six days. The seed were subjected to a total number of four cycles of hydrating-dehydrating at room temperature and then placed in the germination chamber.
7	Combination of each of the treatments №1, №2, and №3 with treatment №6	Combination of scarification or stratification treatment with hydrating-dehydrating cycle treatment as above.
8	Simulated forest fire	Exposure to 200°C temperature, 2.5 h in a box full of smoke, 48 h. in smoke water and combination of the aforementioned.

A second germination test was conducted aiming to explore the potential for enhancing seed germination. This involved implementing the three aforementioned treatments followed by exposure to fluctuating temperature field conditions and undergoing repeated cycles of seed dehydration and rehydration. The selection of these particular combinations of dormancy-breaking treatments was predicated on the hypothesis that employing the aforementioned methods, along with subjecting seeds to hydration-dehydration cycles, would effectively address both physical and physiological dormancy. This approach aimed at creating conditions favourable for germination to occur.

A new completely randomised block experimental design was applied that began the following October and lasted 18 months in total. A new seed lot was collected with the same procedure as the previous year. Seeds were extracted from berry-shaped cones and subjected to a cleaning procedure. In each of the three selected pretreatments, four repetitions of 100 seeds were used. Control treatment was also included. Pretreated and control seeds were fully imbibed in tap water for four days to reach a maximum saturation and placed under field conditions. Seed moisture content was monitored once a week according to ISTA (1999) specifications. The pretreatments HGA, MSH, and HW underwent a re-evaluation in controlled chambers. This re-testing was aimed to compare germination outcomes independent of the experimental design involving hydration-dehydration cycles and the field conditions. Untreated seeds were additionally exposed to hydration-dehydration cycles (control).

During the first winter period (November – February) moisture was maintained above 90%

by covering seeds with moist woolen sacks in order to simulate winter moist chilling. In order to prevent any possibility for mold to appear, the woolen sacks were changed every day. In addition, the germination substrate was sprayed once every ten days with a Captan solution of low concentration (0.5% w/v). From March to mid-October, as temperatures began to rise and air moisture decreased, the treated seeds underwent a series of 13 alternating cycles. Each cycle involved hydration for four days followed by dehydration, during which the seeds were left to dry for 14 days, reaching a moisture content of approximately 10%. These cycles were conducted under field conditions inside insect rearing cages (24 × 24 cm with a 1350-µm mesh) and were sheltered to protect from rain. However, in mid-April, mid-May and mid-June, germination tests were conducted to assess the release of dormancy. Throughout the subsequent winter period from mid-October to March, the same procedure was replicated. Monitoring of the germination process occurred on a weekly basis. Germination was finally detected in June. The germinated seeds were counted, recorded by pretreatment and put in trays with sand. In December, when no germination was observed, all the non-germinated seeds were manually cut and separated as belonging to one of the following categories: empty, filled with resin, and seeds with fully developed embryo. When an embryo was found, it was excised and subjected to a viability staining test to evaluate treatment effectiveness. Seed viability was calculated using the following formula:

$$TI = IG + SE,$$

where TI – total viability, IG – initial germination (%), SE – stained embryos (%).

Seed germination percentage was corrected according to an embryo viability staining test as follows:

$$CG = \frac{NGS}{NGS + SE} \times 100\%$$

where CG – corrected germination (%), NGS – number of germinated seeds, SE – stained embryos.

Statistical analysis

Seed cut test results were expressed on percent basis of the total seed sample used. Germination was calculated on a percent basis as mentioned above. Viability results were also calculated on a percent basis of the embryos stained by the TTC test. Since normality of data could not be achieved any differences among treatments were assessed with Kruskal-Wallis analysis of variance using STATISTICA v. 10 software (StatSoft GmbH, Germany). Additionally, due to non-normal distribution of data, except for the results of the initial seed cut test, their dispersion around the mean was estimated by calculating Interquartile Range. For the results regarding the initial seed cut test the coefficient of variation was used as a measure of data distribution around the mean values of seed categories.

Results

The seed cut test revealed a remarkably high percentage of empty seeds, with 90.03% and

90.01% recorded for both collection years (Table 2). Additionally, nearly 5% of seeds lacked embryos but were instead filled with resin. Consequently, only a minimal fraction of seeds contained embryos (4.72% and 5.10%, respectively). Subsequent embryo viability testing indicated that only 2% of the embryos were viable, as evidenced by TTC.

The seed germination rates in the chambers, following the pretreatments HGA, MSH, and HW, were relatively low in both collection years, ranging from approximately 22% to around 40%, whereas control exhibited minimal germination, with recorded germination below 4% (see Table 3). The results of the TTC tests of the non-germinated seeds for chamber experiments, at the end of the experiment in terms of mean values and variability, are shown in Table 3 and Table 4.

As far as the field experiment is concerned, a low seed germination (15% in MSH and HGA and 9% in HW) was recorded in March, i.e. eight months after the beginning of the experiment, while no germination was recorded in the control (Fig. 2). No germination was recorded in the following autumn in any treatment (Fig. 2). Seed germination was finally recorded after a total of 18 months and when corrected according to seed cut test reached almost 100% (Table 5).

Table 2. Various categories of *Juniperus excelsa* seeds in percent basis of the two collection years (%) from the initial seed cut test (format: mean value ± standard error)

Seed category	1 st collection year		2 nd collection year	
	Mean value	Coefficient of variation	Mean value	Coefficient of variation
Empty	90.03 ± 1.80	4.00	90.01 ± 0.88	1.96
Seeds containing embryo (seeds containing viable embryo, TTC test)	4.72 ± 0.57 (1.72 ± 0.19)	24.30 (23.11)	5.10 ± 0.07 (1.75 ± 0.10)	3.01 (11.71)
Seeds with resin	5.25 ± 0.38	14.63	4.89 ± 0.62	25.40
Total	100.00	–	100.00	–

Table 3. Germination and cut-test results of non-germinated *Juniperus excelsa* seeds at the end of the experiment inside chambers (cleaned seed lot) (mean values ± standard error)

Treatment	1 st collection year						
	Initial germination, %*	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total, %	Total viability, %**	Corrected germination, %
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(1)+(2)	(1)/(1)+(2)
HGA	4.07 ± 0.44 ^{ab}	14.65 ± 1.38 ^{ab}	32.84 ± 1.90 ^a	48.45 ± 1.89 ^a	100.00	18.72 ± 0.98	22.27 ± 3.43
MSH	6.97 ± 0.24 ^a	13.72 ± 0.45 ^{ab}	30.92 ± 1.68 ^a	48.38 ± 1.58 ^a	100.00	20.70 ± 0.43	33.73 ± 1.26
HW	7.39 ± 0.70 ^a	11.36 ± 0.86 ^a	30.83 ± 2.19 ^a	50.42 ± 2.35 ^a	100.00	18.75 ± 0.26	39.52 ± 4.11
Control	0.74 ± 0.46 ^b	17.37 ± 0.27 ^b	32.02 ± 1.91 ^a	49.88 ± 1.63 ^a	100.00	18.11 ± 0.54	3.89 ± 2.42
Treatment	2 nd collection year						
	Initial germination, %*	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total, %	Total viability, %**	Corrected germination, %
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(1)+(2)	(1)/(1)+(2)
HGA	5.19 ± 0.86 ^{ab}	13.30 ± 1.15 ^{ab}	31.52 ± 1.19 ^a	49.99 ± 1.45 ^a	100.00	18.49 ± 0.36	28.29 ± 4.98
MSH	6.10 ± 0.43 ^{ab}	13.85 ± 0.48 ^{ab}	30.04 ± 1.32 ^a	50.01 ± 1.15 ^a	100.00	19.95 ± 0.40	30.55 ± 2.01
HW	6.95 ± 0.83 ^b	11.40 ± 0.83 ^b	33.52 ± 1.27 ^a	48.12 ± 1.36 ^a	100.00	18.36 ± 0.92	37.81 ± 3.85
Control	0.49 ± 0.51 ^a	17.37 ± 0.32 ^a	35.01 ± 1.73 ^a	47.13 ± 1.56 ^a	100.00	17.86 ± 0.33	2.63 ± 2.91

Note: * – values were calculated in total of seeds with embryo (stained or unstained) as well as those with resinous filling; ** – values were calculated by summing up the percentages of germinated seeds plus non-germinated ones but with viable embryo. Designations of treatments: HGA (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm of gibberellic acid (GA₃), MSH (mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by 2 h. immersion in 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), HW (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h.); values within columns followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at 0.05 p-level of significance for each parameter separately.

Table 4. Interquartile range for means of germination, viability and resinous *Juniperus excelsa* seeds at the end of the experiment inside chambers (cleaned seed lot)

1 st collection year						
Treatment	Initial germination, %	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total viability, %	Corrected germination, %
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(1)+(2)	(1)/(1)+(2)
HGA	1.38	4.52	5.11	5.97	3.14	11.19
MSH	0.86	1.39	4.82	5.10	1.39	3.68
HW	1.71	2.52	6.61	7.41	0.80	10.95
Control	1.47	0.90	5.64	4.24	1.39	7.77
2 nd collection year						
Treatment	Initial germination, %	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total viability, %	Corrected germination, %
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(1)+(2)	(1)/(1)+(2)
HGA	2.70	3.23	3.58	4.71	1.12	15.26
MSH	0.87	1.53	4.41	3.75	1.22	5.25
HW	2.60	2.45	3.13	3.77	2.73	8.40
Control	0.98	1.07	5.98	5.25	0.90	5.26

Note: Designations of treatments: HGA (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm of gibberellic acid (GA₃), MSH (mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by 2 h. immersion in 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), HW (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h.).

Table 5. Germination and cut-test results of non-germinated *Juniperus excelsa* seeds at the end of the outdoor experiment (cleaned seed lot)

Treatment	Initial germination, %*	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total, %	Total viability, %**	Corrected germination, %
HGA	20.01 ± 0.91 ^a	1.71 ± 0.46 ^{ab}	31.16 ± 0.54 ^{ab}	47.11 ± 0.87 ^{ab}	100.00	21.72 ± 1.21 ^{ab}	92.75 ± 1.71 ^a
MSH	10.46 ± 0.52 ^{ab}	0.00 ^a	32.35 ± 1.28 ^{ab}	57.19 ± 0.78 ^a	100.00	10.46 ± 0.52 ^a	100.00 ^a
HW	19.56 ± 1.08 ^a	15.58 ± 1.36 ^{ab}	34.96 ± 0.41 ^a	29.90 ± 1.25 ^b	100.00	35.13 ± 2.23 ^b	55.21 ± 1.61 ^b
Control	4.56 ± 1.47 ^b	27.42 ± 0.93 ^b	23.44 ± 0.58 ^b	44.58 ± 0.63 ^{ab}	100.00	31.99 ± 0.95 ^b	16.28 ± 4.22 ^c

Note: * – values were calculated in total of seeds with embryo (stained or unstained) as well as those with resinous filling; ** – values were calculated by summing up the percentages of germinated seeds plus non-germinated ones but with viable embryo. Designations of treatments: HGA (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm of gibberellic acid (GA₃), MSH (mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by 2 h. immersion in 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), HW (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h.); values within columns followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at 0.05 p-level of significance for each parameter separately.

In general, a profound number of stained (viable) embryos was recorded in the non-germinated treated seeds, kept in the chamber, while the relevant percentage in the non-germinated treated seeds under field conditions was very low (Table 3, Table 5). Regarding the variability of germination and viability data of the outdoor experiment the control treatment had generally a larger variability than the other treatments (Table 6).

A notable number of seedlings dried in 1–5 months’ time after germination. The reasons for that were various and not always directly explicable as the seedlings were fully protected. In the first stage of cotyledon unfolding, it was observed that many seedlings (up to 20%) did not physically discard the seed coat. These seedlings did not grow and dried very quickly. Another considerable number of seedlings dried either before expanding the first needles or soon after the appearance of the first needles. Also, a little later, it was observed that a number of seedlings did not take height and formed a rather «spherical» crown and they gradually dried (Fig.

3). The recorded percentage of seedling establishment was approximately 38.26%, taking into account the percentage of germinated seeds that unfold cotyledons.

Fig. 2. Germination course of *Juniperus excelsa* seeds in the outdoor experiment. Designations: MSH – mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by a 2 h. immersion in 3% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), HW – immersion in 10% hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h., HGA – immersion in 10% hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm gibberellic acid (GA₃) for 48 h.

Table 6. Interquartile range for means of germination and viability of *Juniperus excelsa* seeds in the outdoor experiment (cleaned seed lot)

Treatment	Initial germination, %	Stained embryos, %	Unstained embryos, %	Resinous seeds, %	Total viability, %	Corrected germination, %
HGA	2.99	1.35	1.30	2.90	3.64	5.55
MSH	1.25	0.00	4.40	2.60	1.25	0.00
HW	3.10	4.15	1.10	4.00	6.25	4.10
Control	4.90	2.95	1.60	1.85	2.05	14.36

Note: Designations of treatments: HGA (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in 400 ppm of gibberellic acid (GA₃), MSH (mechanical scarification for 6 sec., followed by 2 h. immersion in 3% of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), HW (immersion in 10% of hydrogen peroxide for 20 min., followed by immersion in water for 48 h.).

Fig. 3. A newly emerged seedling of *Juniperus excelsa* with spherical crown that did not evolved into normal seedling.

Discussion

Juniperus species generally exhibit low regeneration rates and a high ratio of empty seeds (García et al., 2002; Wesche et al., 2005). In consistency with these findings, our research revealed a significant percentage of seed lacking embryos or gametophytic residues during the seed cut test, indicating a low fertilisation success. The literature data suggest that the main causes of this issue may be self-incompatibility, incomplete pollen development, or a high homozygosity ratio (Williams, 2009; Gruwez et al., 2013). For instance, Castilleja-Sánchez et al. (2016) documented similar challenges in endangered species, *Pinus rzedowskii* Madrigal & M.Caball., in Mexico, where high inbreeding levels were linked to low germination and seedling establishment issues, such as undeveloped primary needles and deformed stems.

In the Prespa area, there is strong evidence of inbreeding depression. Karapatzak et al. (2019) observed poor fertilisation linked to pollen viability and germination issues in Prespa's *Juniperus excelsa*. Additionally, our preliminary data indicate that embryo viability declines over time; immature seeds (green, 1-year-old) showed nearly double the embryo viability compared to mature seeds. The reason for this decline remains unclear.

Future research on the duration and microphenology of the reproductive cycle (i.e. from the initiation of macrostrobil primordia to the complete morphological differentiation of the embryo) in *Juniperus excelsa* within the study area might help identify the stages of embryonic development where degeneration occurs. Supplementary genetic research is also essential for obtaining more robust results.

Apart from the high percentage of empty seeds, a profound number of seeds were filled with resin, drastically increasing the proportion of non-viable seeds. Resinous seeds are associated with resin canals, common in the Cupressaceae family, which are used for damage repair (Lin et al., 2002). Increased resin production might also be a response to insect infestation, as plants often activate defense mechanisms, such as resin production, to deter further insect feeding and protect against infection (Bracalini et al., 2013). In coniferous trees, insect infestations can lead to an increased resin production, protecting the seeds and cones from damage and potentially resulting in a higher ratio of resinous seeds. However, the high ratio of resinous seeds observed in this study requires further investigation.

The sum of empty and resinous seeds accounted for almost 95% of the total seeds, supporting *in situ* findings by Vrahnakis et al. (2011), reported an almost total absence of regeneration in the Prespa area. Seed germination under controlled conditions was generally low despite various pretreatments applied during the first collection year, such as mechanical or chemical testa rupture, hormone imbibition, and various combinations of these. This suggests the presence of deep primary dormancy in the seeds (Lee et al., 1995; Tilki, 2007; Khalofah, 2022). However, three treatments involving hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) combined with either mechanical scarification or gibberellic acid (GA₃) or water imbibition showed more effective germination results. Hydrogen peroxide can have both an abrasive action in medium or high concentrations and can stimulate germination in low con-

centrations (Rosner et al., 2003; Statwick, 2016). The increased germination observed with HGA and HW treatments indicates that seeds with hard testa are likely being ruptured by H₂O₂, suggesting physical dormancy (Baskin & Baskin, 2001). Similarly, mechanical scarification increased the germination percentage, further indicating physical dormancy.

Germination of HGA pretreated seeds was notably higher than those pretreated with HW, both under controlled conditions and in the field. The application of exogenous GA₃ appears to stimulate germination more effectively, suggesting the presence of physiological dormancy in the seeds (Baskin & Baskin, 2001). Mechanical scarification followed by low-concentration (3%) H₂O₂ imbibition also showed an increased germination, indicating a combination of physical and physiological dormancy.

Despite the deep primary dormancy of *Juniperus excelsa* seeds, a small percentage (approximately 15–30%) appeared to have shallower dormancy and germinated relatively easily, possibly due to a bet-hedging strategy (van Klinken et al., 2008). This strategy helps populations facing strong environmental pressures by distributing germination across years, ensuring population persistence even under suboptimal conditions.

Regarding the experimental conditions, the treatments did not significantly increase the total germination beyond the mentioned percentages. Field seed stratification for one winter period was insufficient to maximise germination, while a second winter stratification period significantly increased final germination percentages. This confirms the strong dormancy status of *Juniperus excelsa* seeds, though it is unclear whether the increased germination was due to the second stratification period alone or its combination with hydration-dehydration cycles. Nonetheless, it appears that a combination of two winter stratification periods with intermediate summer hydration-dehydration cycles effectively breaks seed dormancy.

The production of a high ratio of empty seeds combined with low ratios of seeds with viable embryos, as well as the low survival rates of produced seedlings, strongly suggest the need for further management actions to preserve this priority habitat. An extensive reforestation approach, utilising the seed dormancy break protocol described here, could be beneficial. This approach would not only enhance germination success but also improve the overall regeneration potential of *Juniperus excelsa*

in the Prespa area. Additionally, understanding the ecological and genetic factors contributing to seed viability and dormancy will be crucial for developing effective conservation strategies. Therefore, continued research and adaptive management practices are essential to ensure the long-term survival and regeneration of this species and its habitat.

Conclusions

The study on *Juniperus excelsa* from the Prespa area (Florina, Greece) highlights significant challenges in the species' regeneration, with particularly low natural seed germination and survival rates, largely due to low embryo viability. A high percentage of seeds were found to be empty, and only 2% of embryos were viable, underscoring the low reproductive success of *Juniperus excelsa*. Despite applying a wide range of pre-treatments to overcome physical and physiological dormancy, only three treatments showed moderate improvement in germination rates. Further tests involving hydration-dehydration cycles and field experiments revealed that germination improved significantly (up to nearly 100%) after mechanical scarification and hydrogen peroxide treatment. While the optimised pretreatment protocols significantly improved germination, the low seedling survival emphasises the need for more effective strategies in reforestation and conservation efforts. This research provides valuable insights for preserving the limited-distribution habitat of *Juniperus excelsa*, but further studies are necessary to enhance seedling survival and ensure sustainable regeneration of the species.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПРОРАЩИВАНИЯ *JUNIPERUS EXCELSA* (CUPRESSACEAE) ДЛЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОСИСТЕМ В РЕГИОНЕ ПРЕСПА (ЗАПАДНАЯ МАКЕДОНИЯ, ГРЕЦИЯ)

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В Средиземноморском регионе виды рода *Juniperus* сталкиваются с проблемами их сохранения из-за деятельности человека и угроз изменения климата. Известно, что виды рода *Juniperus* демонстрируют низкую скорость регенерации, в то время как их семена часто проявляют физический и физиологический покой. Жизненность и всхожесть зрелых семян *Juniperus excelsa* из популяции в регионе Преспа (Флорина, Греция), а также выживаемость сеянцев были изучены с целью изучения динамики размножения популяции этого вида, который формирует приоритетный в ЕС тип местообитания с ограниченным распространением и низкой скоростью регенерации. При исследовании среза неочищенной партии семян была выявлена высокая доля пустых семян (90.03%) и низкая жизненность зародышей (2%). Очищенные семена были подвергнуты в общей сложности 44 предварительным обработкам, которые были разделены на восемь групп, нацеленных на физический и физиологический покой, а также комбинации этих методов. Несмотря на то, что большинство обработок показали ограниченный успех в повышении всхожести, три предварительные обработки показали многообещающие результаты (всхожесть от 22.22% до 39.40%). Последующий анализ прорастаний, включающий эти обработки в контролируемых камерах, а также в полевых условиях вместе с циклами гидратации-дегидратации были проведены с использованием недавно собранных семян. Скорость прорастания семян в контролируемых камерах оставалась низкой, что предполагает глубокий первичный покой. Предварительно обработанные семена в контролируемых полевых условиях прошли два зимних периода полностью насыщенными, с 13 циклами увлажнения-дегидратации между ними. Всхожесть была максимальной во второй год полевого эксперимента, достигнув почти 100% после механической скарификации в течение 6 с. с последующим погружением в 3% раствор H₂O₂ на 2 ч. Однако выживаемость саженцев была низкой и достигала в среднем 38.26%. Полученные результаты показывают трудности проращивания семян *Juniperus excelsa* и подчеркивают важность оптимизированных протоколов лесовосстановления для сохранения этого типа экосистем.

Ключевые слова: восстановление греческого можжевельника, выживаемость саженцев, гидратация-дегидратация, жизнеспособность зародыша, производство саженцев, устойчивость к климату

WOLF-UNGULATE INTERACTIONS WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF WOLF'S MAIN PREY POPULATION DECLINE IN CENTRAL RUSSIAN UPLAND

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Canis lupus (hereinafter – wolf) is a top predator specialised on large ungulates. In a community of multiple ungulate species, carnivores may exhibit a preference for one. Due to the decreasing availability of preferred species, interactions between wolves and other ungulates can change. We conducted our research from 2014 to 2019, which included an abrupt decline in the population of the wolf's main prey, *Sus scrofa*, in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve, Russia. We ascertained the wolf diet (scats content analysis) and evaluated preferences using Jacobs' index. The proportion in the diet of two ungulate species, *Capreolus capreolus* and *Alces alces*, increased after the *Sus scrofa* population declined, but the main prey became a non-ungulate species, namely *Castor fiber*. Wolves did not hunt *Bison bonasus*, and changes in *Sus scrofa* populations did not affect interactions between them. The presence of this species in the wolf diet is negligible and related to scavenging. Wolves showed a strong preference for *Sus scrofa* after decreasing its abundance. Dynamic interactions estimated from camera-trap data, using the coefficient of sociality, partly confirmed with analysis of preferences but also depending on other factors. The coefficient of sociality showed attraction species hardly presented in the diet only in the peripheral part of the wolf home range, where ungulates more frequently encounter subadult wolves. The decreasing population of wolf's main prey influenced interactions with other ungulates to some extent since wolves increased the proportion of them in their diet to substitute *Sus scrofa*. In the absence of *Sus scrofa*, wolves tend to prefer middle- and small-sized prey.

Key words: *Canis lupus*, dynamic interactions, diet, interspecific relationships, food habits, large carnivores, predation, wild prey

Introduction

The presence of a predator is a crucial factor that affects the ungulate population and its spatial distribution. Deaths caused by predators are part of the natural mechanism of population regulation (Filonov & Kaletskaya, 1985; Messier & Crête, 1985; Kojola et al., 2004). In addition to direct killing the predator causes non-consumptive effects on prey (Preisser et al., 2005; Creel & Christianson, 2008; Anson et al., 2013; MacLeod et al., 2018). Sometimes non-consumptive effects have even more influence on prey than direct predation (Preisser et al., 2005). Non-consumptive effects include the impact of a predator on prey spatial distribution (Sih, 1987; Mech, 1994; Lima, 1998; Gehr et al., 2018). A high abundance of prey remains in places where the abundance of the predator is low or even totally absent. As an example, this can be caused by intraspecific interactions of predators as in «buffer zones» described by Mech (1977, 1994) in *Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – wolf). Trying to avoid predators is one of the anti-predator mechanisms of prey (Caro et al., 2004; Creel & Christianson, 2008; Gehr et al., 2018). When prey and predator coexist, it triggers a game of prey anti-predator strategies refinement, and

an improvement of predator hunting strategies (Sih, 2005). Predators affect their prey, just as prey affects predators. Predators are often attracted to areas with a high concentration of prey (Sih, 2005; Kittle et al., 2017). At the same time, prey chooses places with feeding resources. Therefore, the distribution of prey's feeding resources affects the distribution of predator-prey interactions (Fraker & Luttbeg, 2012). Prey also can choose among two strategies for using feeding resources: to stay at the place and spend more time on vigilance or to move between resource patches avoiding predators (Fraker & Luttbeg, 2012). Besides, if it is possible, prey prefers to occupy places where it is easier to hide from predators (Lull, 1904; Fuller & Keith, 1980; Caro et al., 2004; Baruzzi et al., 2017). Choosing an anti-predator strategy depends on both predator's behaviour and environmental features such as the type and the distribution of feeding resources, the availability of shelters (Lull, 1904; Fuller & Keith, 1980; Caro et al., 2004; Baruzzi et al., 2017).

Decreasing prey abundance causes a response in a predator population. Sometimes the predator population declines following a decline in the prey population; in other cases, predation shifts to other types

of prey (Messier & Crête, 1985; Dale et al., 1994; Mech, 2007). Alteration in a predator-prey system can affect relationships between a predator and other prey species, if they are present.

Studies on predator-prey interactions in nature often include only prey selection. The predator's reaction to prey density or availability changes in nature is rarely an object of a study since it requires a combination of the certain situation and an opportunity to carry out the research. There are various ways to assess the influence of prey density on a predator. The comparison of the areas with various prey densities (Messier, 1985; Capitani et al., 2004) does not allow us to understand how a predator can respond to alterations in a prey population. Evaluation of numerical and functional response (Dale et al., 1994; Mech & Boitani, 2003) is helpful in that case. Meanwhile to evaluate wolf predation, it is also important to take into account some important factors: a) the role of secondary food, b) the time lag of the wolf population dynamics from that of prey species, c) the variable speed of switching to other types of prey (Gasaway et al., 1983; Theberge, 1990). That is why the mutual influence of prey and predator space use is also important. There are two ways to assess interactions between animals: to assess overlap in home ranges (static interaction) and to analyse the simultaneous presence of animals (dynamic interaction) (MacDonald et al., 1980). The GPS-telemetry allows us to estimate space-time interactions between individual animals. However, it is hardly possible to tag a large part of the populations of a prey and a predator, which causes problems in the interpretation of results (Eriksen et al., 2009).

Camera trapping is one of the methods commonly used in ecological studies of predator-prey interactions. One of the ways to analyse interactions between species is to compare certain indexes calculated for each species (Keim et al., 2019; Phumanee et al., 2021; Ogurtsov & Zheltukhin, 2022). Another way is to assess interactions directly using a single index showing the interaction of both species. Using models in analysing spatio-temporal interactions allows accounting for other factors, which can influence interactions between species such as habitat (Dormann et al., 2018), but requires a large sample size (Amir et al., 2022). In our study, we tried to apply the coefficient of sociality (Kenward et al., 1993) by analysing data from camera traps without linking to individuals. This coefficient was applied by Eriksen et al. (2009) in a study of prey-predator interactions to telemetry data, but this is the first time we apply it here to camera-trap data.

This article considers predator-prey interactions using the example of wolf and its prey. The wolf's main prey in most cases are large ungulates (Bibikov, 1985; Fuller, 1991; Mech & Boitani, 2003; Anderson & Ozoliņš, 2004; Capitani et al., 2004; Smith et al., 2004; Barja, 2009; Wagner et al., 2012; Zlatanova et al., 2014). In some ecosystems, the wolf's diet consists primarily of ungulates of smaller sizes (Salvador & Abad, 1987; Valdmann et al., 1998; Barja, 2009; Nowak et al., 2011; Wagner et al., 2012), and large ungulates, such as *Cervus canadensis* Erxleben, 1777, *C. elaphus* Linnaeus, 1758 or *Alces* spp. are the main prey species in many habitats (Fritts & Mech, 1981; Bibikov, 1985; Mech, 1995; Kojola et al., 2004; Smith et al., 2004; Śmietana, 2005; Wikenros et al., 2009). In multi-prey ecosystems, the wolf tends to specialise in certain species, sometimes regardless of population density (Mech & Boitani, 2003; Capitani et al., 2004; Kojola et al., 2004; Stahler et al., 2006; Wikenros et al., 2009). Therefore, predators can respond to a decreasing availability of prey in two ways. The first is looking for the same species, expanding the search area, thereby increasing the home range. Such a reaction was shown for wolves (Messier, 1985; Jędrzejewski et al., 2007) as well as for non-social predators (Schmidt, 2008). Increasing of their mobility by using linear features of the landscape also helps predators to locate prey with low density (Kittle et al., 2017). The second way is by switching to new prey species, if there is such an opportunity (Messier & Crête, 1985; Dale et al., 1994).

A great chance to study the reaction of a predator, i.e. wolf, on the decline of abundance in its main prey appeared in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve (hereinafter – Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR). The scat analysis showed that the wolf reliable preferred *Sus scrofa* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – wild boar) among several available species of ungulates (Hernandez-Blanco & Litvinova, 2003). However, at the beginning of 2015, the African swine fever (hereinafter – ASF) epizootic broke out in Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR (Petrova et al., 2018; Zakharova et al., 2023) resulting in a sharp decline in the wild boar population. Thereby, new conditions could influence wolf interactions with other potential prey species.

Our working hypothesis is the assumption that a sharp decline of the main prey population may influence interactions of wolves with other present ungulates, including *Bison bonasus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (hereinafter – European bison). Hence, the research aims to investigate interactions between the wolf and ungulates before and after ASF epizootic. We considered two aspects of this problem, namely (1) dy-

namic interactions between the wolf and ungulates and (2) contents of the wolf's diet and its preferences.

Material and Methods

Study area

The study area (53.50–53.65° N, 35.63–35.90° E) covers the south cluster of the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR (117.8 km²) and its surroundings, with a total area of 200 km². It is located in the northwest part of the Central Russian Upland, in the Kaluga Region (Russia), near the border with Tula Region and Orel Region. The study period was from 2014 to 2019.

The study area contains mostly broadleaf forests (*Quercus* spp., *Acer* spp., *Fraxinus* spp., *Populus tremula* L., *Betula* spp.) but also coniferous forests. Overgrown meadows and arable lands cover 9% of the study area (Hansen et al., 2013). The study area is characterised by a high level of habitat mosaicism (Melnik et al., 2007).

The landscape includes a rolling plain with a developed river net comprising gully terrain. The climate is temperate continental with a mean annual temperature of +4.4°C. The average annual precipitation is 662 mm (with a range of 450–700 mm). A stable snow cover remains till the late March on average. The snow depth varies from 5 cm to 50 cm (Smirnova et al., 1997).

Four species of wild ungulates are constantly present in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR, namely wild boar, *Capreolus capreolus* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – roe deer), *Alces alces* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – moose), and European bison. Two others (*Cervus elaphus* and *Cervus nippon* Temminck, 1838) are rare and known only on basis of single registrations. The European bison was released in Orlovskoye Polesie National Park, an adjacent Protected Area, during the 1990s in the framework of the species restoration project (see Belousova et al., 2002) and it reached Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR in 2001 (Pererva & Pererva, 2003; Chistopolova et al., 2009), and now it is the most abundant ungulate species, being a part of the Srednyeruskaya Wisent population (Raczynsky, 2021). Wild boar was the most abundant species till 2014, but after the ASF epizootic, its density decreased and now it is relatively low. Medium-sized mammals, such as *Castor fiber* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – beaver), *Lepus timidus* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – hare), *Nyctereutes procyonoides* Gray, 1834, *Meles meles* Linnaeus, 1758, and *Vulpes vulpes* Linnaeus, 1758, also present and constitute a potential prey for wolves. Along with the wolf, large carnivore species comprise *Lynx lynx* Linnaeus, 1758 (1–3 individuals per 100 km²) and *Ursus arctos* (the den-

sity is impossible to count since the registrations are rare). The population of *Lynx lynx* in the study area ranged from one male and two females to three males and four females during the study period. One wolf pack permanently uses the area of the south cluster of the Kaluzhskiye Zaseki SNR with up to 14 individuals presented, and the density of wolf was 7.6–11.9 individuals per 100 km².

Wolf diet

We estimated the wolf diet by analysing the composition of wolf scats. We collected scats during walking routes, which we conducted in all seasons for each year. We conducted the routes in both snow and snowless periods. Therefore, the sample reflects an average wolf diet for a year. Scats were disinfected in 70% ethanol, washed, and dried (Rozhnov et al., 2019). We identified species of mammals by hairs, using keys and standards of mammal hairs from atlases (Teerink, 1991; Chernova & Tselikova, 2004). If necessary, we analysed an imprint of a hair cuticle on polishing under a light microscope (Rozhnov et al., 2011). We registered the presence of birds, insects, or plant remains without identification of species. We calculated the proportion of identified species using the following formula:

$$PA_i = \frac{N_i}{s} \times 100\%,$$

where N_i – number of identifications of certain species; s – total number of all identifications.

For estimating the wolf diet, we used scat analysis without considering the size of prey, which could distort the results to some extent. However, we suppose this method gives enough information for assessment preferences in the diet.

To estimate preferences in the wolf diet, we used Jacobs' index (D) representing modified Ivlev's electivity index (Jacobs, 1974). This index ranges from -1 to 1, where negative values show avoidance and positive values show preference. When the index is 0, it means using the food item proportionally to its ratio in the environment. We analysed significance with Fisher's exact test using Bonferroni correction. Necessary information about the population of prey species was gained from winter route counts (Priklonskiy, 1973) (for ungulates except for the European bison) and beaver counts, which started in 2018. We assessed the beaver population in late October – early November by a statistical method, based on the estimation of the number of beaver colonies and the proportion of colonies with juveniles (Yemelyan et al., 2009). We evaluated the European bison population using various

methods including visual observations on feeding grounds, tracking, synchronous photo registration by camera traps during the total European bison counts in Russia. We did not estimate preferences for other prey species due to a lack of data on their population; besides their proportion in the wolf diet was negligibly small.

Dynamic interactions

We used data from camera traps to evaluate dynamic interactions between the wolf and the European bison. Each camera trap location was distributed per 1–2 km² (Fig. 1). We placed camera traps in places most frequently visited by animals such as streams, roads, crossroads, and trails. We installed camera traps at a height of 60 cm above the ground so that snow cover, plants, and rising water levels on the steams would not interfere with detecting animals. We attached camera traps to the trees, where we also avoided getting plants into focus to prevent triggering the motion sensor (Rozhnov et al., 2019).

In total, we used 38 camera trap stations with Bushnell Trophy Cam HD, Spromise s108, Spromise S308 and Reconyx PC900. We installed only one camera trap per station. After 2016, we changed the location of some camera traps so that each camera worked half of the season (1.5 months) at one station and half at another to increase the number of locations. We removed cameras four times per year in the middle of each season between two locations in order to allow cameras of each location to work half of each season. We analysed these locations as independent ones. Capturing efforts were of 53 987 trap-nights during the study period. The total number of stations increased from 27 to 66, resulting in adding new cameras and seasoning some station's working schedules.

Fig. 1. The distribution of camera traps in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve (Russia) and the border of the wolf home range in 2019.

We estimated dynamic interactions by the coefficient of sociality (Kenward et al., 1993) using the geometric mean distance. We analysed four diads, i.e. pairs of predator-prey species, where one of the members was a wolf, and another was one of four ungulate species. Extreme values of the coefficient show a difference from the expected distance between analysed members of the diad. A positive value (or «attraction») means a lesser observed distance, whereas a negative value (or «avoidance») means a higher observed distance.

Values of the coefficient close to 0 mean indifference in using space in members of diad (there is no difference from random spatial distribution). We chose this coefficient because it does not require polygons (i.e. home ranges of animals), and it can be applied to the analysis of data from camera traps. Also, it showed good results in testing indices of dynamic interactions, since it is capable of identifying presence or absence of dynamic interactions and showed a high significance of results (Long et al., 2014). This is the most complex and multifactorial index that we analyse. Its values reflect the mutual tendencies of distance and approach of predator and prey. This index can record not only direct impacts, but also manifestations of research interest, and other forms of indirect interaction between species, including those mediated by another species of prey for a predator or a competitor for the prey.

We calculated this coefficient in Ranges8 software, using a 6-hour time threshold. In addition to coefficients for the whole study area, we estimated coefficients for various zones (sub-units) of the wolf home range (Hernandez-Blanco et al., 2005). As the wolf is a social predator, which lives in packs (Bibikov, 1985; Mech & Boitani, 2003), here and further we use term «wolf home range» for the home range of the whole pack. Calculating the coefficient of sociality for sub-units we do not submit the results for the home core and for all sub-units in roe deer due to the small number of fixed diads (less than five or absent), which does not allow us to interpret the results appropriately. Due to a small number of fixed diads in separate sub-units, we used a longer time threshold (12 h) in its analysis. We did not use a longer time threshold because of the larger distances, which the animals can move during this time and, therefore, the longitude of the distance between the animals in the analysed diad can be caused not by their interdependence. The number of camera trap locations in sub-units of the wolf home range was proportional to its area.

We established the inner structure of the wolf pack home range with the data gained from snow tracking (in winter) and registrations of wolf traces. We follow the concept of three sub-units constraining the wolf pack home range: (1) the home core, a functional centre of the wolf home range which includes dens and rendezvous sites; (2) the vital space, a hunting ground for the mating pair with pups in the autumn–winter period; (3) the spatial shell occupying the space between the external border of the vital space and the boarder of the pack home range, where subadult wolves stay during the period after the pups' birth (Hernandez-Blanco et al., 2005). We used the term «home core» instead of the commonly used «core area» (Kaufmann, 1962).

We determined the boundaries of the wolf pack home range and sub-units using the minimal convex polygon method (MCP) with 100% of the locations (Hayne, 1949). For a home core, we used locations of dens and rendezvous sites used by an adult female with pups during summertime after leaving the den. For a vital space, locations of the hunting behaviour of the mating pair with pups were used. For estimating the boundaries of a spatial shell and total wolf home range we used the locations of all members of the pack (Hernandez-Blanco et al., 2005). To estimate the area of each sub-unit and to attribute camera trap locations to one of the sub-units, we cut the overlapped area of the inner sub-units as follows: the spatial shell was the wolf home range without vital space and home core, the vital space was the polygon determined by MCP 100% without overlapping with the home core area.

We consider the presence of adult wolves except the mating pair in a wolf pack to be possible since offspring can stay in the pack after maturing (Mech & Boitani, 2003). The cases of multiple breeding described in the literature also confirm the possibility of having more than two mature wolves in the pack (Murie, 1944; Mech & Boitani, 2003; Hernandez-Blanco et al., 2005). We determined the composition of the wolf pack by the podometry method (Hernandez-Blanco et al., 2005) and by camera-trap data.

Results

Wolf pack composition and home range

During the study period the wolf pack size was nearly constant except for the last year. Immediately after the ASF epizootic in 2015, the size of the wolf pack decreased to a small extent (twice less than before), and in 2019 it dropped to

only nine wolves in the whole pack (Table 1). The number of pups changed slightly. In 2016, when the density of the wild boar was minimal, the number of wolf pups was also minimal. However, the next year more pups were born than in previous years. During the study period the birth rate did not change significantly, but by 2019 the number of sub-adult and adult wolves staying in the pack decreased, which led to a reduction of the size of the pack.

The area of the wolf home range varied from 100 km² to 159 km² during the study period. The average area was 136 km². The area of the home core during the study period was 14 km². This sub-unit constituted on an average of 10% of the home range, and it had the smallest area during most of the study period. The vital space covered on average 27 km², ranging from 13 km² to 57 km². It constituted 20% of the wolf home range. The largest sub-unit was the spatial shell, its area ranged from 65 km² to 132 km², which was about 70% of the wolf home range. Since the home core had a small area, the number of camera trap locations was small, leading to a small number of registrations of wolves and ungulates within this sub-unit.

Ungulate population density

We used data from annual counts of ungulates in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR firstly to ascertain preferences in the wolf diet. However, these results reflect the situation in the study area well, so they are necessary to present (Table 2).

Wolf diet

During the study period, we analysed 531 wolf scats. Ungulates made up 32% to 69% of the wolf diet. Among non-ungulate prey, the most often was beaver, with participation of *Lepus timidus*, *Nyctereutes procyonoides*, and *Vulpes vulpes* (Fig. 2). The remains of birds, insects, and plants (usually *Malus* sp. and *Prunus* sp.) constrain «Other» category. We did not identify species of small rodents and fixed only their presence.

In 2015, when the ASF epizootic happened, the proportion of wild boar was still high. But in the following years its occurrence in the wolf diet decreased. Since the next year, 2016, the beaver has constituted most of the wolf diet. In 2016, the proportion of beaver and wild boar in diet was comparable, but further, the proportion of beaver increased. The proportion of each ungulate species and beaver with Jacobs' index calculated is presented in Table 3.

Table 1. Wolf pack size and density of wolves (individuals per 100 km²) in the south cluster of the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve (Russia) in winter, 2014–2019

Year	Density	Wolf pack size	Adult	Sub-adult	Juvenile
2014	11.9	14	4	6	4
ASF epizootic					
2015	10.1	12	3	5	4
2016	10.1	12	4	5	3
2017	10.1	12	2	5	5
2018	10.1	12	5	4	3
2019	7.6	9	2	3	4

Note: ASF – African swine fever.

Table 2. Population density (individuals per 100 km²) of main ungulate species in the southern cluster of the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve (Russia)

Year	Wild boar	Roe deer	Moose	European bison
2014	362.5	10.2	80.6	89.1
ASF				
2015	51.8	108.7	59.4	96.8
2016	2.5	62.0	71.3	113.8
2017	28.9	26.3	77.2	123.1
2018	41.6	23.8	87.4	140.9
2019	44.1	58.6	112.9	174.0

Note: ASF – African swine fever.

Table 3. The proportion of ungulates in the wolf diet and Jacobs’ index (D) with p-value from Fisher’s exact test (N – number of analysed scats) in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve, Russia

Species	Variable	2014	ASF	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
		N		183	65	56	69	80
Wild boar	Proportion in diet, %	57.4		66.2	28.6	20.3	17.5	3.9
	D	0.82		0.98	1.00	0.91	0.44	-0.40
	p-value in Fisher test	< 0.001		< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	0.008	0.184
Roe deer	Proportion in diet, %	1.6		1.5	3.6	7.2	12.5	16.7
	D	0.19		-0.92	-0.45	0.51	0.51	0.22
	p-value in Fisher test	0.712		< 0.001	0.260	0.049	0.007	0.190
Moose	Proportion in diet, %	0.5		1.5	0.0	0.0	10.0	9.0
	D	-0.90		-0.82	-1.00	-1.00	-0.30	-0.48
	p-value in Fisher test	< 0.001		0.005	0.0106	0.007	0.132	0.009
European bison	Proportion in diet, %	0.5		0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.41
	D	-0.91		-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-1.00	-0.77
	p-value in Fisher test	< 0.001		< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001
Beaver	Proportion in diet, %	16.4		12.3	32.1	46.4	36.3	53.8
	D	–		–	–	–	0.44	0.78
	p-value in Fisher test	–		–	–	–	0.001	< 0.001

Note: ASF – African swine fever.

Fig. 2. The proportion of identifications in wolf scats in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve (Russia) during 2014–2019. Designations: ASF – African swine fever epizootic.

The wild boar constituted more than half of the wolf diet before the ASF epizootic (in 2014) and in 2015. In the subsequent years, the proportion of wild boar decreased gradually in the wolf diet. The proportion of roe deer and moose in the wolf diet increased after the decrease of the wild boar population; however, moose began to occupy a significant part of the wolf diet only three years after the ASF epizootic, in 2018. The proportion of the European bison hairs was negligible small (< 1%). This situation did not change significantly after the wild boar population decline, except for 2019, because all the samples with the European

bison hairs in 2019 (five samples) were collected within less than one month, and the whole number of collected scats was small (54 samples). The beaver constituted a significant part of the wolf diet, and after the ASF epizootic it occupied the major part of wolf diet. Before the ASF epizootic Jacobs' index showed only preference for the wild boar. In the following years, it revealed preference for the wild boar (only four years after the ASF epizootic), roe deer (in one year) and beaver (both two years with index calculated).

Dynamic interactions

The results of the analysis of dynamic interactions for the whole wolf pack home range are presented in Fig. 3. We also estimated the coefficient of sociality for separate sub-units where it was possible: the vital space and the spatial shell (Fig. 4).

Wild boar

The coefficient of sociality for the wolf-wild boar diad was positive or negative, but negative values appeared only after the ASF epizootic (Fig. 3A). In the vital space, the coefficient was above 0 (except 2016 and 2017, when there were no fixed diads at all). However, in 2018 and 2019 there were only three and two fixed pairs due to a small area of the sub-unit and low values of the wild boar population (Fig. 4A). In the spatial shell values of the coefficient differed between years. Except for 2014 and 2019, the sign of the value of the coefficient in the spatial shell matches with the one for the total home range.

Roe deer

The coefficient of sociality for the wolf-roe deer diad was mostly positive (in 2015, 2016 and 2018) (Fig. 3B). In 2017 there was a negative value, while the value of the coefficient was close to 0 in 2019. Since there was a low number of fixed wolf-roe deer diads in all study periods, we did not perform the analysis for sub-units.

Moose

High positive values in the wolf-moose diad appeared after the ASF epizootic (Fig. 3C). Except 2015, values of the coefficient increased gradually from negative value in 2014 to high positive value in 2019. The high positive value in 2015 might be due to the low number of wolf-moose fixed diads in that year. In the vital space, the number of fixed diads was too small. In the spatial shell, there was not any pattern either (Fig. 4B).

Fig. 3. The coefficient of sociality (S_j) in the total wolf pack home range in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve, Russia. Designations: A – for wolf-wild boar diad; B – for wolf-roe deer diad; C – for wolf-moose diad; D – for wolf-European bison diad; * – the number of diads was less than five, which is not enough for an adequate result; ASF – African swine fever epizootic.

Fig. 4. The coefficient of sociality (S_j) in sub-units of wolf pack home range in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki State Nature Reserve, Russia. Designations: A – for wolf-wild boar diad; B – for wolf-moose diad; C – for wolf-European bison diad; * – the number of diads was less than five, which is not enough for an adequate result; ASF – African swine fever epizootic.

European bison

The coefficient of sociality for the wolf-European bison diad did not show any reaction to the wild boar population decline (Fig. 3D). In 2014, this coefficient took a negative value, and avoidance is shown for vital space. But in the spatial shell we found high attraction in the wolf-European bison pair (Fig. 4C). In 2015, the total coefficient is close to 0, which shows an independent use of space between these two species. There was no attraction or avoidance in vital space. Nevertheless, this is the only year where

the coefficient was above 0. The coefficient of sociality took a high positive value only in 2016, but attraction was found only in the spatial shell among the sub-units. In 2017, 2018, and 2019, the number of pairs in the vital space was too low to give adequate results. The coefficient for the whole wolf pack home range shows a weak attraction in 2017 and near independence in 2018, with the attraction being in the spatial shell in both periods. In 2019, the coefficient shows weak avoidance in the wolf pack home range and also in the spatial shell.

Discussion

The wild boar is often one of the main prey species for wolves at places where it is presented (Salvador & Abad, 1987; Kübarsepp & Valdmann, 2003; Andersone & Ozoliņš, 2004; Capitani et al., 2004; Imbert et al., 2016; Ståhlberg et al., 2017). In the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR, this species had been the main prey species for several decades (Hernandez-Blanco & Litvinova, 2003). That is why such an abrupt decline in its population could not pass without consequences for wolves. On a large scale decreasing prey abundance can lead to a decline in predator population (Mech, 2007). But in our case, this did not happen. Since we carried out a long-time wolf monitoring, we gained an opportunity to assess the consequences for a certain wolf pack. According to the results of scat analysis, wolves were compelled to switch to other species.

When the density of the wild boar was still high in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR, it was the main prey species for wolves. Therefore, wolves often and successfully pursued wild boars. In that case, the coefficient of sociality reflects the situation well. After the ASF epizootic appeared, the density of wild boar decreased drastically. At the same time, there were a lot of carcasses in the forest. Wolves tend to eat carrion as well (Mech, 1995), and it should decrease their need to hunt. That explained the high proportion of wild boar in the wolf diet and the negative value of the coefficient of sociality. However, in the vital space, the value of the coefficient of sociality was above zero. It can imply that adult wolves tend to pursue remaining wild boars, showing a high preference for them (Capitani et al., 2004). In 2016, the year after the ASF epizootic, the population density of the wild boar was the lowest, and there were only single adult animals. All fixed diads were in the spatial shell, with the number of camera traps three times more than in vital space because of its larger area. Despite the low density of the wild boar, the coefficient of sociality showed successful pursuit of wild boars by wolves

in the periphery of the home range. The high proportion of the wild boar in the diet confirmed this and pointed to the fact that wolves were still able to find their preferred prey. We suggest that in the nearest hunting grounds recovery of the wild boar population might occur faster with the help of feeding. A part of the spatial shell overlapped with the area of hunting grounds. In 2017, the density of the wild boar was increasing but not significantly. With the rising proportion of other prey species in the diet, especially the beaver, the interest towards wild boars might have decreased. It allowed wild boars to avoid hunting successfully. In 2018, a high positive value of the coefficient of sociality accorded with a high preference in wild boar by wolves and the considerable proportion of wild boar in the wolf diet. Despite the low density of the wild boar, wolves successfully hunt them. In contrast with 2018, in 2019 the interest of wolves towards wild boars decreased, according to Jacobs' coefficient. The wild boar's frequency of occurrence in samples was much lower, and the spatial distribution of wild boar and wolf relative to each other was close to random. The general dynamics in these relationships came to a gradual decrease in preference. Even under conditions of low abundance of the wild boar, wolves preyed primarily them, but compensated the lack of food by other prey species.

First of all, the decline in the wild boar population increased predation on beavers. The presence of the beaver in the wolf diet is noticed in previous studies (Kübarsepp & Valdmann, 2003; Andersone & Ozoliņš, 2004; Nowak et al., 2011; Newsome et al., 2016; Sidorovich et al., 2017; Gable et al., 2018). The situation of increasing predation pressure on beavers under conditions of decline in large- and medium-sized prey has already been described in the literature (e.g. Frenzel, 1974; Shelton & Peterson, 1983; Messier, 1985; Milne et al., 1989; Andersone, 1999). In our case, the beaver played the most important compensatory role for wolves. Wolves tend to choose smaller-sized prey in the presence of large ungulates. Wolves are often specialised in a particular species, independent of their abundance, which is medium-sized ungulates among potential prey (Mech & Boitani, 2003; Capitani et al., 2004; Gazzola et al., 2005; Śmietana, 2005; Barja, 2009; Nowak et al., 2011). Thus, wolves tend to choose species that require fewer efforts to kill (Cowan, 1947; Mech & Boitani, 2003), though the choice does not always depend on size (Wikenros et al., 2009). It appeared that the beaver was the most available prey in our case.

In case of roe deer, there is a need to take into consideration one more predator, *Lynx lynx*, which

can also hunt roe deer. At some places, the roe deer is the main prey for *L. lynx* (Sidorovich, 2006; Schmidt, 2008). The influence of *L. lynx* on the roe deer population has not been analysed in the study area, but we suppose this predator to influence it to a lesser extent than the wolf.

Mostly wolves used proportionally the roe deer to its population. But after the decrease in wild boar availability, the proportion of this food item increased. The population of the roe deer fluctuated during the study period. The results showed avoidance of the roe deer only in 2015, when the highest density was registered, and there was a large number of carcasses of wild boars, which died from the ASF epizootic. The roe deer also became an important substitute prey for wolves. The coefficient of sociality showed attraction only in two years. In 2016, there were few registered fixed diads, and a relatively high density of roe deer was observed, and in 2018, a high preference in the wolf diet was fixed. High mobility and frequent changes of the sign in the sociality index in the wolf-roe deer pair, in our opinion, clearly demonstrate a race in the strategy of wolves searching for roe deer and the latter avoiding wolves.

The moose is a large ungulate, and hunting this species can be risky for wolves since it can cause serious injuries (Mech & Boitani, 2003). Hence, if middle-sized ungulates are available, they are often more preferable for wolves than moose (Pimlott, 1967; Fritts & Mech, 1981; Potvin et al., 1988; Kunkel et al., 1999; Stahler et al., 2006). Nevertheless, in many regions of both North America and Eurasia, moose is the main prey of wolves (Mech, 1966; Peterson, 1977; Poyarkov, 1980; Bologov, 1981; Filonov & Kaletskaya, 1985; Messier, 1985; Mech & Boitani, 2003; Kojola et al., 2004; Wikenros et al., 2009; Bondarev, 2013). Moose hunting appears to require behavioural traditions passed down from generation to generation. It is interesting that in the zone of the southern taiga and deciduous forests, it is not typical for wolves to hunt moose, which is widely practised in more northern latitudes (Poyarkov et al., 2022). That can explain the near absence of moose in the wolf diet. Till 2018, when moose began to occupy a considerable part of the wolf diet, positive values of the coefficient of sociality were only in the spatial shell. It can also testify to the possibility of attempts by sub-adult wolves to pursue moose. New behaviour forms, including hunting, are often introduced into populations by young individuals since their behaviour is more plastic and not subject to rigid stereotypes. However, only in 2018, i.e. three years after the ASF epizootic, wolves began to hunt mooses successfully to a significant ex-

tent. The coefficient of sociality conformed with these suggestions, taking positive values in 2018 and 2019. Wolves used the moose as substitute prey, but they did not start hunting it earlier, when the population of the wild boar decreased. The trigger might be the fact that in 2018 and 2019 the density of the moose in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR was higher than in previous years. It also explains the lack of interest towards mooses in these years, which is why the most vulnerable part of the moose population (young and old individuals) could increase.

Analysis of scats revealed that the European bison was rare in the wolf diet in our research despite it is the most common among ungulate species in the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR. The decline in wild boar population did not change the situation. *Bison bison* Linnaeus, 1758, the closest relative of the European bison, was reported to be an important food resource for wolves at several places elsewhere (Carbyn & Trotter, 1988; Smith et al., 2000; Shave et al., 2020). Therefore, the European bison is a potential prey for wolves. However, at other places wolves rarely prey upon the European bison (Śmietana & Klimek, 1993; Jędrzejewski et al., 2000, 2012; Nowak et al., 2011; Sidorovich et al., 2017; Kaczor et al., 2019). Carrion is also an acceptable source of food for wolves (Mech, 1995), and scavenging on European bison is not an exception. In the Białowieża Primeval Forest and the Bieszczady Mountains (both in Poland), wolves are one of the most frequent scavengers on European bison carcasses (Selva et al., 2003; Jankowski et al., 2019). In our study, we suppose both cases of the presence of European bison hair in scats (in 2014 and 2019) to be the result of scavenging, since we have not found evidence of successful hunting on the European bison during snow tracing. Jacobs' index confirmed the avoidance of using European bison as a prey by wolves in all years except one.

The only period when the coefficient of sociality had a positive value was 2016 year. The attraction was shown only in the spatial shell. Differences between vital space and spatial shell can be a result of the distinct hunting behaviour of adult and sub-adult wolves. Sub-adults' pursuit distance is supposed to be longer than that of adult ones. Sub-adult wolves are interested in European bison and try to pursue them, in the wolf-pack home range periphery, which causes more disturbances of European bison and their avoidance of wolves. Also, the population of the European bison is steadily growing owing to the successful programme of conservation and re-introduction (Belousova et al., 2002). European bisons expand the space used and go further beyond

the border of the southern cluster of the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR. Therefore, more European bison appeared in the spatial shell, including mixed groups with calves (Kraśńska & Kraśński, 2013). The presence of calves and young animals can attract sub-adult wolves. Adult wolves are more experienced and do not take the risk of hunting European bison, using more habitual species. In total, the coefficient shows some dynamics of increasing attraction with the highest attraction in 2016 and the following decreasing. The highest attraction matched with the lowest wild boar population density. In the following years, the wild boar population density slowly increased, and the other prey species, beaver, occupied the largest part of the wolf diet. It can explain the lack of interest in wolves towards the European bison. In addition, till 2015 (when AFS happened), the European bison population density was less than 100 individuals/km². Under those conditions, there were few separate groups during most of the year except the calving period. Since its population density grew, the number of separate groups during the whole year increased. Hence, the probability of a close encounter of the European bison and the wolf also increased. It should shift the coefficient of sociality to a positive value, but this did not happen in our case. The decline in the main prey population did not cause noticeable changes in dynamic interactions between the wolf and the European bison. However, with the increasing density the European bison can become a prey species for the wolf in future.

The coefficient of sociality is the modification of the Jacobs' index which is usually applied to telemetry data with the diads of two analysed individuals (Kenward et al., 1993; Eriksen et al., 2009). We adapt this coefficient to data gained with camera traps to assess dynamic interactions between two species. Telemetry data include information about separate individuals and that is only a small part of the population (Eriksen et al., 2009). Using data from camera traps gives the information about spatial distribution of all the animals fixed by cameras, and this better reflects the spatial distribution of the whole population. However, the use of camera traps creates another problem, namely the lack of fixed diads. In some cases, the number of fixed diads was either small, or absent, which did not allow us to perform a correct analysis. Also spotted fixation of animals can lead to some bias, since the absence of fixation on the camera trap does not mean the absence of the animal in this area. However, we believed it was possible to minimise these problems by expanding of the camera trap matrix.

When applied to two individuals of one species, the coefficient of sociality gives a clear result, where positive values point to an attraction between individuals, and negative values show avoidance between them (Kenward et al., 1993). As for predator-prey interactions, we cannot interpret the gained results as mutual attraction or avoidance.

Prey tends to avoid places where predators are present whereas predators prefer areas with more prey. This is a constant behavioural response race between prey and predator (Sih, 2005), and negative or positive spatial association between species may provide only the result of this race. Although field studies of the factors affecting predator-prey space use are not very numerous, there is evidence that different factors influence the outcome of the space use race (Sih, 2005), including the density of species, the spatial distribution of resources, landscape, presence of refuges for prey, presence of other species of prey or other predators (Bouskila, 2001; Heithaus, 2001), the activity of both prey and predator (Luttbeg & Schmitz, 2000). The presence of behavioural adaptations against predators is also important. A low level of anti-predator behaviour will shift the result of the predator-prey race on the predator's behalf. In our case, this result changes year after year. Which exact factor affected the coefficient value in every single case is hard to say. Of all the types of wolf prey, the beaver has virtually no ability to avoid wolf predation by moving to another place, since it is rigidly attached to its habitats and shelters. In this respect, *Meles meles* and *Nyctereutes procyonoides* are close to beavers, although this limitation is less pronounced for them. On the contrary, such mobile ungulates as roe deer and moose can actively move around the home site, avoiding predation by wolves.

Our results imply that the coefficient of sociality applied to predator-prey interactions did not get an unambiguous output. There is some consistency between this coefficient of dynamic interaction and preferences in prey, but it cannot be explained to the full extent. The «attraction» towards the main prey is not always present. The same result was gained in the study of telemetry data as well (Eriksen et al., 2009). We tried to explain the results of dynamic interactions analysis using factors we were able to assess, such as prey density, density of other prey species, and spatial distribution of prey and predator. The population of predators, i.e. wolves, was stable during the study period, and for three of the four ungulate species the wolf is the only predator in the study area.

The proportion of prey species in the diet changes immediately according to feeding needs.

The same situation has been described in Belarus (Sidorovich et al., 2017). In Germany, Wagner et al. (2012) showed that resettled wolves, originating from Poland, reduced the proportion of initially preferred prey two years after resettlement, whereas the proportion of another prey species, which was more available in the new place, had been growing for five years. In our case, according to Jacobs' index, the preference for wild boar in the diet changed to avoidance four years after its population decline. Hence, changes in preferences in our study proceeded gradually. First of all, wolves substitute an unavailable prey species with those, which has a high density. However, it takes more time to change specialisation.

A sharp decline in the wild boar population did not significantly impact the wolf pack size for at least four years after the ASF epizootic (Table 1). The number of pups does not deviate from the common number for this pack. In 2019, the number of adult wolves in the pack sharply reduced compared to the breeding pair only. That could be the consequence of the replacement of the breeding pair, but we cannot confirm it without genetic analysis and individual identification. According to these results, the decrease in the main prey population did not reflect the demographic situation in the wolf pack and its spatial structure. During the period when switching prey species, wolves did not expand their home range and did not start to hunt on dogs or livestock in the nearest settlements. The available ungulate species and smaller prey species were enough to sustain the wolf pack after the decreasing of their main prey population. This means the natural system of the Kaluzhskie Zaseki SNR is fully functional with rich trophic levels.

In our study, we demonstrate and analyse three important indicators characterising the relationships in the predator-prey system, namely a) the proportion of prey in the predator's diet, b) the Jacobs' index for various types of prey, c) the sociality index in predator-prey dyads. The first indicator demonstrates the direct load of the predator on the prey. This is a very important parameter, but in itself, it has little predictive value, since interaction at the population level depends on the ratio of population densities and several other indirect impact factors. The Jacobs' index shows the level of selectivity of a predator towards a prey species. In a predator-prey system, there may be situations where the predator's primary prey may have a neutral or even negative Jacobs' index. This means that the predator does not have a critical limiting effect on the prey population and the system is regulated from the bottom up. On the contrary, high

positive values of the Jacobs' index indicate a high degree of influence of the predator on the prey population, and in these situations the system with a high degree of probability moves to the level of top-down regulation. The integrated use of three indicators opens up opportunities for an in-depth analysis of complex structural relationships in the predator system in a multispecies prey community.

Conclusions

It is difficult to reveal changes in dynamic interactions between wolves and ungulates since there are too many factors affecting them. Under conditions of unavailability of the wild boar, the main prey of wolves in the Kaluzhskiye Zaseki SNR, they switched to other prey species but saved preference for wild boar for four years. The role of two ungulate species, roe deer and moose, in the wolf diet increased to some extent; however, they did not constitute most of it. The beaver became the main prey of wolves. Wolves used substitute prey species mostly according to their density. Wolves did not start actively hunting European bison despite its high population.

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ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ВОЛКА И КОПЫТНЫХ В УСЛОВИЯХ СНИЖЕНИЯ ЧИСЛЕННОСТИ ОСНОВНОГО ВИДА ДОБЫЧИ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ СРЕДНЕРУССКОЙ ВОЗВЫШЕННОСТИ

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Canis lupus (далее – волк) – хищник, специализирующийся на крупных копытных. В сообществе с несколькими видами копытных хищники могут отдавать предпочтение одному из них. Снижение численности предпочитаемого вида добычи может изменить взаимоотношения волка с другими видами копытных. Данное исследование проведено в государственном природном заповеднике «Калужские засеки» в период с 2014 по 2019 гг., в который произошло резкое сокращение численности *Sus scrofa* – основного вида добычи волка. Мы определили спектр питания этого хищника по анализу экскрементов и выявили предпочтения с помощью индекса Якобса. После снижения численности *Sus scrofa* возросла доля *Capreolus capreolus* и *Alces alces* в питании волка, но основным видом добычи стал *Castor fiber*. Волки не охотились на *Bison bonasus* как до, так и после падения численности *Sus scrofa*. Присутствие этого вида в питании волка незначительно и связано с поеданием падали. Индекс Якобса показал, что волки предпочитают *Sus scrofa* другим видам после снижения его численности. Динамические взаимодействия, анализированные с помощью коэффициента социальности по данным фотоловушек, частично согласуются с выявленными предпочтениями, но также зависят и от других факторов. Коэффициент социальности показал привлечение для видов, занимающих малую часть спектра питания на периферической части участка, где копытные чаще сталкиваются с волками-перевояками. Снижение численности основного вида добычи волка повлияло на отношения с другими видами копытных, так как волки стали активнее включать их в рацион. При этом волки предпочитают в качестве замещающего корма не крупные виды добычи.

Ключевые слова: *Canis lupus*, дикие виды добычи, динамические взаимодействия, крупные хищные млекопитающие, межвидовые взаимоотношения, пищевые предпочтения, спектр питания, хищничество

ФАУНА И БИОТОПИЧЕСКОЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЖУКОВ-ЛИСТОЕДОВ (COLEOPTERA: CHRYSOMELIDAE) ЗАПОВЕДНИКА «ШАЙТАН-ТАУ» (РОССИЯ)

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Исследования таксономически богатых групп насекомых – важная составляющая работ по изучению биоразнообразия на ООПТ разного ранга. В статье, на основе результатов оригинальных исследований (2017–2020 гг.), впервые с высокой степенью полноты установлен видовой состав и проведена характеристика фауны семейства Chrysomelidae (далее – жуки-листоеды) государственного природного заповедника «Шайтан-Тау». Территория исследований расположена на юге лесостепной зоны низкогорий Южного Урала в Оренбургской области. В настоящее время данная фауна является одной из наиболее изученных локальных фаун жуков-листоедов заповедных территорий Южного Урала. Здесь зарегистрировано 180 видов жуков-листоедов (51% состава фауны этого семейства Оренбуржья). 86 видов впервые отмечено в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау», в том числе, восемь видов впервые указывается для фауны Оренбургской области. Кроме того, на этой территории ранее был обнаружен новый для науки вид рода *Altica*. По уровню видового богатства фауна заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» сопоставима или заметно превосходит другие локальные фауны эталонных особо охраняемых природных территорий Южного Урала и при этом несколько беднее фаун заповедников и национальных парков лесостепи Приволжской возвышенности. К особенностям зоогеографической структуры фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» относятся довольно большое число (23; 12.8%) западнопалеарктических видов, у многих из которых здесь проходят восточные пределы ареалов, и низкая доля центральнопалеарктических форм (3.9%). Обнаружены некоторые виды сибирской природы (*Labidostomis sibirica* и *Gonioclena flavicornis*), на Урале находящиеся в реликтовых островных частях своих ареалов. Это заметно отличает изученную фауну от фаун жуков-листоедов степных заповедных участков юга Оренбуржья, в которых весомую долю составляют представители казахстано-туранского происхождения. Изученная фауна характеризуется сочетанием в ее составе богатых группировок степных, лугово-степных, неморальных и, в меньшей степени, бореальных форм (значительная часть из которых находится здесь на границах своих ареалов), а также выраженной пространственной мозаичностью биотопических комплексов (например, лесных, степных, пойменных). В целом, полученные данные объективно характеризуют фауну заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» как эталонную для уральской дубравной лесостепи, что подчеркивает его важную роль в сохранении природных комплексов, а также познания современного состояния и исторических этапов становления биоты западного макросклона Южного Урала.

Ключевые слова: видовой состав, зоогеографический анализ, Оренбургская область, особо охраняемая природная территория, растительные жесткокрылые, трофические связи, энтомокомплекс, Южный Урал

Введение

Семейство Chrysomelidae (далее также – жуки-листоеды) – одна из самых разнообразных групп жесткокрылых-фитофагов. Они являются важным компонентом всех наземных и многих пресноводных экосистем (Jolivet & Verma, 2002; Lopatin et al., 2004; Konstantinov et al., 2009; Лопатин, 2010; Беньковский, 2011). Поэтому они часто используются в крупных эколого-фаунистических исследованиях (Лопатин, 2010; Gavrilović et al., 2014; Дедюхин, 2018; Сергеев, 2020; Japoshvili & Aslan, 2020). Инвентаризация фауны жуков-листоедов осуществляется и в рамках изучения биоразнообразия на заповедных территориях (Лагунов, Новоженев, 1996; Gavrilović & Ćurčić, 2011, 2013; Гуськова, Куфтина, 2015; Aslan et al., 2017; Сергеев, 2018; Дедюхин, 2019а, 2021а,б,в, 2023а,б). Перспективным видит-

ся использование их в работах по уточнению ранга биогеографических барьеров. Особый интерес в данном отношении представляет познание фауны жуков-листоедов Урала, меридионального хребта, разделяющего две части света Евразии, в том числе путем сравнительного анализа локальных фаун эталонных природных объектов его территории, важнейшими из которых являются заповедники.

Изучение жуков-листоедов Южного Урала и сопредельных территорий имеет длительную историю. Но исследований семейства Chrysomelidae на хребте Шайтантау, в пределах которого расположен заповедник «Шайтан-Тау», до последнего времени практически не проводилось. Лишь недавно появился ряд публикаций (Дедюхин, 2019а, 2021а,б), посвященных инвентаризации фауны жуков-фитофагов надсемейства Curculionoidea и семей-

ства Chrysomelidae заповедников Оренбуржья, в которых в том числе содержатся первые сведения о составе фауны жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» и кратко освещены наиболее характерные ее черты. В частности, впервые был составлен предварительный фаунистический список жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», в котором было приведено 93 вида (Дедюхин, 2019а). В следующих работах известное видовое богатство семейства этой локальной фауны оценивалось уже в 127 видов, но без опубликования обновленного списка (дополнительно был указан только вид *Smaragdina flavicollis* (Charpentier, 1825)) (Дедюхин, 2021а,б). Цель настоящей статьи – на основе материалов многолетних целенаправленных исследований жуков-листоедов на данной территории установить близкий к полному видовой состав локальной фауны семейства Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», а также провести ее сравнительный анализ.

Материал и методы

Государственный природный заповедник «Шайтан-Тау» (51.73–51.64° N, 57.40–57.48° E) расположен на севере Кувандыкского района Оренбургской области на южной оконечности лесостепных южноуральских низкогорий (Чибилев, 2015). Здесь на юго-восточном пределе распространения находятся европейские широколиственные леса и дубравная лесостепь, сходная с лесостепью Русской равнины, но имеющая характерные черты в составе, структуре и распределении сообществ, что определяется горным характером местности (Калмыкова и др., 2016).

«Шайтан-Тау» – один из самых молодых заповедников России (создан в 2014 г.). Его площадь составляет 65.76 км². Северная и северо-западная граница совпадает с границей Оренбургской области и Республики Башкортостан. Восточная и южная части границы охватывает преимущественно облесенную правобережную пойму р. Сакмары, в некоторых местах огибая используемые земли сельскохозяйственного назначения и базы отдыха (Чибилев, 2015).

В геологическом отношении для сопок хребта Шайтантау (как и Южного Урала в целом) характерно преобладание силурийского офиолитового комплекса темноокрашенных (от зеленовато-серых до почти черных) горных

пород (кремнистые сланцы, серпентиниты, подушечные лавы основного состава). Среди интрузивных магматических пород наиболее широко распространены поверхностные выходы серпентинитов (Чибилев, 2015).

Рельеф заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» представляет собой контрастное приречное низкогорье Уральской горноскладчатой страны с перепадами высот от 208 м н.у.м. у берегового уреза р. Сакмары до 578 м н.у.м. на хребте Шайтантау. На его территории выражены три яруса рельефа: верхнее плато (реликт пенеплена), лабиринт приречного мелкосопочника со склонами разной степени крутизны и экспозиции, обрывами, горными грядами и скалистыми останцами, и пойма р. Сакмары и впадающих в нее небольших рек (Чибилев, 2015). В растительном покрове этой территории преобладают восточно-европейские широколиственные (дубовые и кленово-липовые) леса в мозаичном сочетании с луговыми, злаково-разнотравными и петрофитными степями (Романова, 2011). Леса главным образом располагаются в средней и нижней части склонов, поднимаясь до верхнего плато в виде сужающихся языков по распадкам. Каменистые вершины сыртов, верхние части южных склонов и высокое плато остепнены (Романова, 2011; Чибилев, 2015) (рис. 1).

Рис. 1. Типичные ландшафты заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (Россия). Обозначения: А – дубравная лесостепь на горе Каран-Турай и залесенная пойма р. Сакмары; В – ковыльная степь на возвышенном плато и дубравы в горных распадках; С – петрофитная растительность г. Караман; D – кустарниковые степи северного склона г. Каран-Турай.

Fig. 1. Typical landscapes of the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia. Designations: A – oak forest-steppe on the Karan-Turai Mount and forested River Sakmara floodplain; B – *Stipa*-dominated steppe on an elevated plateau and oak forests in mountain valleys; C – petrophytic vegetation on Karaman Mount; D – shrub steppes of the northern slope of Karan-Turai Mount.

В горных лесах основные площади занимают формации ксеромезофильных дубрав из *Quercus robur* L. (с примесью *Populus tremula* L. и *Betula pendula* Roth), а также липняков с *Tilia cordata* Mill. (при участии *Acer platanoides* L. и *Ulmus glabra* Huds.), которые перемежаются с зарослями степных кустарников и степями. В состав кустарникового яруса разреженных дубрав входят *Prunus fruticosa* Pall., *Caragana frutex* (L.) K. Koch, *Chamaecytisus ruthenicus* (Fisch. ex Woloszcz.) Klásk., *Rosa glabrifolia* C.A. Mey. ex Rupr. В травяном подлеске наблюдается совместное присутствие лесных, луговых, опушечных и степных видов, что характерно для светлых дубрав лесостепной зоны. В лесах и на их опушках произрастают уральские лесные эндемики и субэндемики (например, *Lathyrus rotundifolius* Willd. (= *Lathyrus litvinovii* Iljin) и *Knautia tatarica* (L.) Szabó). В узких долинах рек произрастают умеренные леса в комплексе с кустарниковыми и луговыми сообществами. Для поймы р. Сакмары характерны ивняки (*Salix alba* L.), тополевики (с преобладанием *Populus nigra* L.) и черноольшаники (с доминированием *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn.). По берегам рек обычны заросли кустарниковых ив (например, *Salix viminalis* L., *S. triandra* L.) (Романова, 2011; Шаповалов, 2011; Чибилев, 2015).

Петрофитные степи характерны для вершин горных гряд, скалистых и осыпающихся склонов с выходами серпентинитов и других магматических пород. Травяной покров петрофитных степей разрежен. Наиболее характерные виды этих сообществ *Ephedra distachya* L., *Helictotrichon desertorum* (Less.) Pilg., *Orostachys spinosa* (L.) Sweet, *Phedimus hybridus* (L.) 't Hart, *Thymus mugodzhariensis* Klokov & Des.-Shost., *Allium saxatile* M.Bieb., *Clausia aprica* (Stephan) Korn.-Trotzky, *Silene baschkirorum* Janisch., *Dianthus acicularis* Fisch. ex Ledeb., *Astragalus helmii* Fisch. ex DC., *Hedysarum razoumovianum* Fisch. & Helm ex DC., *Onosma guberlinensis* Dobroc. & V.M.Vinogr., *Aster alpinus* L., *Artemisia salsoloides* Willd. и др. Местами формируются горные петрофитно-кустарниковые степи и заросли степных кустарников с *Caragana frutex*, *Prunus tenella* Batsch, *P. fruticosa*, *Spiraea hypericifolia* L., *Cotoneaster laxiflorus* J.Jacq. ex Lindl., которые контактируют либо с каменистыми степями, либо с разреженными горными дубравами. На выходах горных пород часты заросли *Juniperus sabina* L. Своеобразие флоры заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» заключается в наличии здесь на границах ареалов ряда неморальных, бореальных и сухостепных

видов, а также большого числа реликтовых и эндемичных видов (Романова, 2011; Калмыкова и др., 2016; Кин и др., 2016).

В основу работы положены сборы автора статьи, осуществленные в рамках комплексных эколого-фаунистических исследований жуков-фитофагов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» в течение пяти последовательных экспедиций (июнь 2017, май 2018, июнь 2019, июнь 2020 и июль 2021 гг.). Кроме того, использованы небольшие материалы, полученные в 2016 и 2017 гг. В.А. Немковым (Оренбург, Россия) и в мае 2018 г. С.Л. Есюниным (Пермь, Россия).

Исследованиями были охвачены все ландшафтные части, наиболее интересные урочища (степное водораздельное плато, лесостепные мелкосопочники гор Караман и Каран-Турай, балка Каркабар, пойма р. Сакмары) и весь спектр типов биотопов, представленных в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау». Основными методами при полевых работах были энтомологическое кошение в разных типах биоценозов и стряхивание в сачок и ручной сбор имаго на потенциальных кормовых растениях. Кроме того, проводились поиски жуков под камнями и другими укрытиями. Всего было собрано и изучено свыше 1400 экземпляров жуков-листоедов. Весь материал хранится в коллекции автора статьи. Иллюстрации, использованные в статье оригинальные, за исключением фотографии (рис. 1А), сделанной А.В. Одинцовым (Удмуртская Республика, Воткинск).

Определение видов проводилось с использованием ряда источников (Медведев, Шапиро, 1965; Беньковский, 1999; Warchałowski, 2003; Bieńkowski, 2004; Исаев, 2007; Kippenberg & Mikhailov, 2020), а также сравнения с достоверно определенными экземплярами из коллекции автора. Когда это необходимо для точного определения, изучалось строение гениталий самцов. Состав и объем семейства Chrysomelidae, как и в ряде аналогичных работ (Дедюхин, 2018; 2019а, 2021в, 2023а,б), принят в традиционном понимании (Медведев, Шапиро, 1965; Беньковский, 1999; Warchałowski, 2003; Bieńkowski, 2004), включая подсемейство Orsodacninae (в последнее время обычно рассматриваемое в составе отдельного семейства – Orsodacnidae), но без Bruchinae. Для корректного сравнения таксономической структуры фауны Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» с другими фаунами в списке отмечены также трибы Clytrini и Alticini, ранг которых ранее принимался на

уровне подсемейств. Номенклатура видов и общие данные по ареалам жуков-листоедов приняты по каталогу Chrysomeloidea Палеарктики (Löbl & Smetana, 2010) с учетом последующих изменений и дополнений. Для детализации картины распространения видов на Урале и в прилегающих регионах были взяты сведения из перечисленных выше определителей, около 20 работ по фауне Среднего Поволжья, Урала и Западной Сибири, а также еще не опубликованные материалы многолетних исследований автора статьи на востоке Русской равнины, на Урале, и в Западной Сибири.

При характеристике таксономической структуры фауны использовался индекс фауны жуков-листоедов, который составляется из названий трех наиболее богатых подсемейств (наименования таксонов, включающие в общей сложности 50% видового богатства и более, выделяются курсивом) (Медведев, 1993). При установлении ареалогических комплексов для зоогеографического анализа фауны применялся принцип построения схем ареалов по Городкову (1984). Схема и объем групп видов по широте трофического спектра приняты по работе Dedyukhin (2016). Для сравнения видового состава фаун жуков-листоедов горной и пойменной частей заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», а также состава изученной фауны с фаунами ряда других особо охраняемых природных территорий (ООПТ) Южного Урала и Среднего Поволжья, использовался коэффициент Жаккара (Jaccard, 1901).

Состав фаун других ООПТ для сравнительного анализа, устанавливался на основе детального анализа фаунистических сводок и обобщающих работ: национальный парк «Хвалынский» (Беньковский, Орлова-Беньковская, 2013а,б; Дедюхин, 2021в, 2023в; Sazhnev et al., 2022), Жигулевский заповедник (Краснобаев и др., 1994; Розенберг, 2007; Дедюхин, 2023а),

геопарк «Торатау» (Дедюхин, 2019б, 2021б; Dedyukhin, 2020; Dedyukhin & Martynenko, 2020); Ильменский заповедник (Лагунов, 1992; Лагунов, Новоженев, 1996; Чашина, 2002; Chashchina, 2008; Guskova, 2010; Mikhailov, 2018; Михайлов, 2020, 2021; Kippenberg & Mikhailov, 2020), Ащисайская степь (Дедюхин, 2019а, 2023б). Широта трофической специализации видов преимущественно устанавливалась, исходя из обобщенных оригинальных данных по фауне востока Русской равнины и Южного Урала, а также путем критической оценки данных из большого числа источников. Поэтому в соответствующем разделе оценивается региональный, а не локальный трофический спектр видов.

Ранее была опубликована аналогичная работа по фауне заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» другой крупной группы растительноядных жуков – надсемейству Curculionoidea (Дедюхин, Филимонов, 2020). Это позволило сравнить зоогеографическую и экологическую структуру фаун Chrysomelidae и Curculionoidea одной и той же территории.

Результаты и обсуждение

Видовое богатство и таксономическая структура фауны

К настоящему времени в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» зарегистрировано 180 видов жуков-листоедов (табл. 1; Электронное приложение 1). Из них 86 видов впервые отмечены в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау», в том числе восемь видов впервые указываются для фауны Оренбургской области. Кроме того, был обнаружен неописанный вид рода *Altica* Geoffroy, 1762. На основе оценки распространения жуков-листоедов и представленного на территории исследований спектра биоценозов, можно предположить обитание еще около 30–40 видов этого семейства.

Таблица 1. Таксономический состав и видовое богатство семейства Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (Россия)
Table 1. Taxonomic composition and species richness of the Chrysomelidae family in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia

Таксоны	Число видов	Доля в фауне, %
Orsodacninae	1	0.5
Donaciinae	6	3.3
Criocerinae	7	3.9
Cryptoccephalinae (триба Clytrini)	12	6.7
Cryptoccephalinae (триба Cryptoccephalini)	29	16.1
Eumolpinae	2	1.1
Chrysomelinae	21	11.7
Galerucinae (без трибы Alticini)	15	8.3
Galerucinae (триба Alticini)	75	41.7
Cassidinae	12	6.7
Всего видов	180	100.0

В таксономическом плане основу изучаемой фауны составляют три группы: триба Alticini (75 видов; 41.7%), триба Cryptocephalini (29 видов; 16.1%) и подсемейство Chrysomelinae (21 вид; 11.7%). Таким образом, индекс фауны листоедов (Медведев, 1993) в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» имеет вид *Alt-Cry-Chr*. Сходную таксономическую структуру имеют и другие фауны южнолесостепных и степных ландшафтов востока Русской равнины (Дедюхин, 2016б), в том числе фауна Жигулевского заповедника (Дедюхин, 2023а).

В целом, уровень разнообразия жуков-листоедов в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» следует считать высоким. Учитывая, что к настоящему времени в Оренбургской области зарегистрировано 351 вид этого семейства (включая еще неопубликованные оригинальные данные автора статьи), то на небольшой территории заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» обитает не менее половины (51%) видов фауны Оренбургской области. Фотографии некоторых из видов жуков-листоедов, сделанные в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау», показаны на рис. 2.

Для оценки уровня видового богатства фауны жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» наглядно сравнение с другими относительно хорошо изученными локальными фаунами крупных ООПТ Южного Урала и Среднего Поволжья (табл. 2). Видовое богатство этой фауны сопоставимо с фауной геопарка «Торатау», расположенного в южной лесостепи Предуралья, где на трех известняковых рифовых шиханах близ г. Стерлитамак и в пойменных сообществах долины р. Белой к настоящему времени зарегистрировано 198 видов жуков-листоедов (Дедюхин, 2019б, 2021б; Dedyukhin, 2020; Dedyukhin & Martynenko, 2020). При этом фауна заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» несколько богаче фауны Ильменского заповедника (лесные низкогорья восточного макросклона Южного Урала с участками степной растительности), где в ходе многолетних стационарных исследований известно 164 вида (Лагунов, 1992; Лагунов, Новоженков, 1996; Чашина, 2002; Chashchina, 2008; Guskova, 2010; Mikhailov, 2018; Михайлов, 2020; Kirpenberg & Mikhailov, 2020). Хотя сборы жуков-листоедов неоднократно осуществлялись и на других уникальных природных объектах лесной и лесостепной зон Южного Урала (в частности, в заповеднике «Шульган-Таш», в национальных парках «Башкирия» и «Таганай») степень инвентаризации фауны в них далека

от полноты, что пока не позволяет проведение корректных сравнений. Например, для музея-заповедника «Аркаим» приведено 70 видов (Михайлов, 1999), для Троицкого комплексного заказника (Есюнин, Козьминых, 1992) указано 55 видов этого семейства.

В нашем распоряжении имеются репрезентативные данные по фаунам заповедных территорий кластерного степного заповедника «Оренбургский», изучение фауны жуков-листоедов в которых нами осуществлялось параллельно с исследованием фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» и с применением тех же методов и подходов (Дедюхин, 2019а, 2021а,б). Сравнение этих данных показывает, что видовое богатство жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» заметно выше такового в заповедных участках Оренбуржья, расположенных в степной зоне и сопоставимых с ним по площади. Так, в Айтурской и Буртинской степях, также характеризующихся мелкосопочным и грядово-балочным рельефом, но в целом несколько меньшей мозаичностью ландшафта, известно лишь по 140–145 видов. При этом фауна заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» почти в два раза богаче фауны Ащисайской степи (опустыненные засоленные степи равнинного Тургайского плато Зауралья), где в ходе аналогичных исследований отмечено лишь 96 видов жуков-листоедов (Дедюхин, 2023б) (табл. 2). Показательно, что самое большое число видов среди локальных фаун Оренбуржья в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» зарегистрировано в двух других крупнейших группах растительных жуков – Cerambycidae (Шаповалов, 2011) и Curculionidea (Дедюхин, Филимонов, 2020; Дедюхин, 2021а,б).

Напротив, фауны эталонных природных территорий лесостепи Приволжской возвышенности (Жигулевский заповедник и национальный парк «Хвалынский») заметно богаче фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (включают по 230–240 видов) (табл. 2). Вероятно, это обусловлено комплексом причин: более мягким климатом Среднего Поволжья (в сравнении с Южным Уралом), долинным эффектом крупнейшей европейской реки, сложным и древним (останцово-балочным) рельефом этих ООПТ, известняковыми и меловым подстилающими породами (отсутствующими в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау»), а также существенно более высоким флористическим богатством этих территорий, что особенно важно для трофически специализированных групп насекомых-фитофагов.

Таблица 2. Соотношение видового богатства и ареалогических комплексов в фаунах жуков-листоедов некоторых крупных ООПТ Южного Урала и Поволжья (Россия)**Table 2.** The ratio of species richness and areal complexes in the Chrysomelidae fauna in some large Protected Areas of the Southern Urals and River Volga Region, Russia

Комплексы	ООПТ					
	Национальный парк «Хвалынский»	Жигулевский заповедник	Геопарк «Торатау»	Заповедник «Шайтан-Тау»	Ильменский заповедник	Оренбургский заповедник (участок Ащисайская степь)
Широтные комплексы						
Голарктический	11 (4.5%)	14 (6.1%)	10 (5.1%)	11 (6.1%)	14 (8.5%)	3 (3.1%)
Транспалеарктический	58 (24.0%)	69 (30.0%)	51 (25.8%)	55 (30.6%)	58 (35.4%)	24 (25.0%)
Западно-центрально-палеарктический	107 (44.2%)	103 (44.8%)	90 (45.5%)	70 (38.9%)	60 (36.6%)	32 (33.3%)
Западнопалеарктический	35 (14.5%)	21 (9.1%)	18 (9.1%)	22 (12.2%)	13 (7.9%)	7 (7.3%)
Центральнопалеарктический	22 (9.1%)	11 (4.8%)	17 (8.6%)	7 (3.9%)	3 (1.8%)	25 (26.0%)
Центрально-восточнопалеарктический и субтрансевразиатский	9 (3.7%)	11 (4.8%)	12 (6.1%)	14 (7.8%)	13 (7.9%)	5 (5.2%)
Условные эндемики и субэндемики	–	1 (0.4%)	–	1 (0.6%)	3 (1.8%)	–
Долготные комплексы						
Бореальный и арктобореальный	6 (2.5%)	12 (5.2%)	9 (4.5%)	16 (8.9%)	24 (14.6%)	–
Полизоональный (включая температурный)	105 (43.3%)	122 (53.0%)	91 (46.0%)	91 (50.6%)	103 (62.8%)	28 (29.2%)
Южнобореально-суббореальный	46 (19.0%)	43 (18.7%)	37 (18.7%)	36 (20.0%)	19 (11.6%)	15 (15.6%)
Суббореальный	85 (35.1%)	53 (23.0%)	61 (30.8%)	37 (20.6%)	18 (11.0%)	53 (55.2%)
Число видов:	242	230	198	180	164	96

Рис. 2. Виды Chrysomelidae на кормовых растениях в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» (Россия). Обозначения: А – *Cryptosephalus sericeus* (Linnaeus, 1758) и *C. violaceus* Laicharting, 1781 на цветочной корзинке *Tragopogon* sp.; В – *Gonioctena flavicornis* Suffrian, 1851 на листе *Salix caprea* L.; С – *Xanthogaleruca luteola* (Müller, 1766) на листе *Ulmus glabra* Huds.; D – *Altica* sp. на листе *Rosa* sp.

Fig. 2. Chrysomelidae species on host plants in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia. Designations: *Cryptosephalus sericeus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *C. violaceus* Laicharting, 1781 on the flower head of *Tragopogon* sp.; В – *Gonioctena flavicornis* Suffrian, 1851 on a leaf of *Salix caprea* L.; С – *Xanthogaleruca luteola* (Müller, 1766) on a leaf of *Ulmus glabra* Huds.; D – *Altica* sp. on a leaf of *Rosa* sp.

Зоогеографический анализ фауны

В фауне жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» преобладают широко распространенные виды транспалеарктического и западно-центрально-палеарктического (включая евро-сибирский) комплексов (69.5%), что характерно для равнинных и низкогорных фаун внутренних областей Евразии. Обращает на себя внимание довольно большое число (и весомая

доля) в фауне западнопалеарктических (включая европейские) форм (22 вида; 12.2%) (табл. 2), которые находятся здесь вблизи своих восточных границ ареалов. Показательно, что их значительно больше, чем в Ильменском заповеднике (13 видов), расположенном на восточном макросклоне Южного Урала. С другой стороны, в изученной фауне жуков-листоедов очень немного представителей центральнопалеарктического комплекса (всего семь видов; 3.9%). Это особенно наглядно, в сравнении с фаунами степных заповедных участков Оренбуржья. Например, в фауне Ащисайской степи, расположенной на юго-востоке Оренбургской области, доля центральнопалеарктических видов составляет 26% (Дедюхин, 2023б).

Черты своеобразия фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (как и фауны Южного Урала в целом) проявляются также в наличии здесь реликтовых популяций видов сибирского происхождения: (*Labidostomis sibirica* (Germar, 1823) (в петрофитно-кустарниковых степях) и *Gonioctena flavicornis* (Suffrian, 1851) (в горных лесах)), которые отсутствуют в лесостепной фауне востока Русской равнины. При этом оба этих вида на Южном Урале известны и несколько севернее (в заповеднике «Шульган-Таш») (Mikhailov, 2000). *Gonioctena flavicornis* – бореомонтанный вид ангарского генезиса, широко распространенный в Южной Сибири и на Дальнем Востоке, а в Европе представленный островными анклавами в Альпах, Карпатах, Фенноскандии и Балтии. На Урале он также имеет дизъюнктивное распространение. Помимо двух южноуральских заповедников, он локально встречается на Северном

Урале: в горном массиве «Конжаковский Камень» (Свердловская область) (Михайлов, 2008) и в подзоне средней тайги Республики Коми (пос. Югыдъяг) (Долгин, Беньковский, 2011), а также в южной тайге Зауралья (Тюменская область) (Сергеева, Дедюхин, 2021).

Южносибирско-монгольско-казахстанский *Labidostomis sibirica* в регионе достоверно известен только из лесостепной и степной зон уральской горной страны в пределах Башкирии, Челябинской и Оренбургской областей (Немков, 2011; Шаповалов, 2012; Лагунов, Новожезов, 1996; Mikhailov, 2000; Дедюхин, 2021a), где он также повсеместно локален, хотя местами нередок (жуки обычно встречаются по опушкам горных дубрав и в кустарниковых степях на цветущей *Caragana frutex*). Обитание этого вида на Западносибирской равнине (Тобольск) (Медведев, 2013) и в степной зоне востока Русской равнины (запад Оренбургской области) (Bieńkowski, 2004; Беньковский, 2011; Немков, 2011) требует подтверждения материалом. О том, что *Labidostomis sibirica* в Оренбургской области известен только из лесостепи хребта Шайтантау, а указания на другие районы этого региона (Немков, 2011) ошибочны, отмечал Шаповалов (2012). Лишь недавно еще одна локальная популяция этого вида была обнаружена в южной части Оренбургской области в степной части зауральского пенеplена (Домбаровский район, балка Сазды) (Dedyukhin, 2022), где жуки также были собраны на *Caragana frutex*.

Особо следует отметить, что в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» обнаружен еще не описанный вид рода *Altica* (рис. 2D). Большая его серия, включая редких для видов этого рода самцов, собрана на тенистой опушке горного смешанного леса на *Rosa* sp. (были зарегистрированы и факты питания). Второй известный локалитет этого вида – Айтуарская степь (южноуральский кластер Оренбургского заповедника), где несколько экземпляров также были собраны на *Rosa* sp. во влажном участке на опушке осинового колка (Дедюхин, 2021a). Интересно, что в России виды рода *Altica*, трофические связанные с *Rosa* sp., не известны (Медведев, Дубешко, 1992; Bieńkowski, 2004), хотя таковые есть в фауне Казахстана (Лопатин, 2010). Но новый вид четко отличается от них по строению генитального аппарата самцов (главный диагностический признак видов этого рода). Из других розоцветных виды этого рода известны на *Filipendula* Mill. (*Altica engstroemi* J. Sahlberg, 1893) и *Sanguisorba*

L. (Altica) helianthemii (Allard, 1859)) (Bieńkowski, 2004; Дедюхин, 2018).

Специфичность фауны жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», а также ее генетические связи, довольно наглядно подчеркиваются результатами сравнения видового состава с таковым в ряде других ООПТ Южного Урала и Поволжья (табл. 2). При общем невысоком уровне сходства с фаунами всех сравниваемых эталонных природных территорий, большее сходство фауна заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» выявлено с богатыми фаунами Поволжья и Предуралья (Жигулевский заповедник, геопарк «Торатау» и национальный парк «Хвалынский») (коэффициенты Жаккара – 0.55, 0.51 и 0.46, соответственно). Кардинальные различия наблюдаются при сравнении с фаунами восточного макросклона Южного Урала (Ильменский заповедник) (коэффициент Жаккара – 0.34) и особенно южностепного Зауралья (Ащисайская степь) (коэффициент Жаккара – 0.24). Конечно, это связано с большим сходством ландшафтов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» с анализируемыми ООПТ Поволжья и Предуралья (возвышенности или низкогорья Восточноевропейской лесостепи), но также может служить дополнительным свидетельством существенного значения Уральского хребта как зоогеографической границы.

В зональном отношении половину фауны Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» составляют виды с полизональными типами ареалов (50.6%), также довольно богато представлены южнобореально-суббореальный (36; 20.0%) и суббореальный (37; 20.6%) комплексы (табл. 2). Интересно, что фауна листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» в целом имеет более северный облик, чем фауны эталонных объектов южной лесостепи Поволжья и Предуралья. Так, доля суббореальных видов здесь ниже, чем в Жигулевском заповеднике (53 вида; 23%) и в геопарке «Торатау» (61 вид; 30.8%). Напротив, видов бореального комплекса заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» заметно больше (16, 12 и девять, соответственно) (табл. 2). Это довольно неожиданно, так как Стерлитамакские шиханы и Жигулевские горы расположены в меридианальном направлении примерно на 200 км севернее заповедника «Шайтан-Тау». Данный факт, вероятно, является следствием более холодных и влажных климатических условий в низкогорьях западного макросклона Южного Урала в сравнении со Средним Поволжьем и Предуральем, что, в частности, и обуславливает сдвиг природных зон на

Урале в южном направлении по сравнению с сопредельными равнинами.

К видам бореального происхождения, находящимся в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» вблизи южных границ ареалов, относятся *Donacia antiqua* Kunze, 1818, *Labidostomis lepida* Lefèvre, 1872, *Cryptocephalus nitidulus* Fabricius, 1787, *C. quinquepunctatus* (Scopoli, 1763), *Chrysomela cuprea* Fabricius, 1775, *C. vigintipunctata* (Scopoli, 1763), *Gonioctena quinquepunctata* (Fabricius, 1787), *Altica engstroemi* J. Sahlberg, 1893, *Hippuriphila modeeri* (Linnaeus, 1760). В заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» они локализируются по тенистым берегам р. Сакмары, старицам и уремам в ее пойме. Только *Gonioctena quinquepunctata* повреждает *Prunus padus* L. и во влажных балках нагорной части. Показательно, что все они отсутствуют в степных ландшафтах Оренбуржья.

С другой стороны, в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» зарегистрирована сравнительно богатая группа неморальных форм (14 видов), распространенных преимущественно в зонах широколиственных лесов и дубравной лесостепи (некоторые на север – до юга подтаежной зоны). Большинство неморальных видов имеют европейские и западнопалеарктические ареалы, например, *Cryptocephalus querceti* Suffrian, 1848, *Pachybrachis tessellatus* (Olivier, 1791), *Luperus xanthopoda* (Schrank, 1781), *Altica quercetorum* Foudras, 1860, *Crepidodera lamina* (Bedel, 1901), *Aphthona pygmaea* Kutschera, 1861, *Psylliodes brisouti* Bedel, 1898. В заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» они встречаются в нагорных широколиственных лесах и на их опушках. Сюда же мы относим *Labidostomis humeralis* (D.N. Schneider, 1792), недавно обнаруженный в Зауралье (Сергеева, Дедюхин, 2021). Вероятно, неморальным по происхождению видом является *Cryptocephalus chrysopus* Gmelin, 1790, кроме Европы, местами встречающийся также в Средней Азии, а островной участок ареала этого вида есть в Саянах (Беньковский, 2011; Romantsov & Moseyko, 2023). Этот редкий вид на Южном Урале, помимо заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», известен только в межгорной балке в Айтуарской степи заповедника «Оренбургский» (Дедюхин, 2019а), а на востоке Русской равнины найден только в отдельных местах Приволжской лесостепи (Исаев, 2005; Дедюхин, 2021б; Romantsov & Moseyko, 2023). В заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» он довольно обычен в разреженных дубравах. Жуки встречаются на *Quercus robur*, а также на кустарниковом подлеске. К неморальным по про-

исхождению видам относится и развивающийся исключительно на *Ulmus* spp. транспалеарктический *Xanthogaleruca luteola* (Müller, 1766) (рис. 4С). Этот вид в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» обычен в нагорных лесах, но в степной зоне Оренбургской области сильно повреждает в посадках и населенных пунктах интродуцированный из Восточной Сибири *Ulmus pumilla* L. Неморальный характер распространения имеют несколько околородных видов, отмеченных в пойме р. Сакмары (*Epitrix caucasica* (Heikertinger, 1950), *Altica palustris* (Weise, 1888), *A. lythri* Aubé, 1843, *Phyllotreta dilatata* (Thomson, 1866)).

В целом, неморальных видов в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» в два раза больше, чем в фауне Ильменского заповедника (где только семь видов можно условно отнести к этому комплексу), что вполне ожидаемо, так как на территории Ильменского заповедника нет широколиственных лесов. Самое примечательное, что таких видов в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» обнаружено не меньше, чем в фауне Жигулевского заповедника (Дедюхин, 2023а), расположенного на 500 км западнее (на Самарской Луке в дубравной лесостепи Среднего Поволжья). Показательно в этом плане, что аналогичными особенностями (некоторое повышение разнообразия неморальных форм на Южном Урале в сравнении с прилегающими с запада равнинными территориями) характеризуется и флора, что объясняется сложной историей флорогенеза уральской горной страны (Коржинский, 1894; Крашенинников, 1939; Горчаковский, 1968; Камелин и др., 1999). Подобная закономерность отмечена и в сообществах пауков дубрав Урала и Предуралья (Есунин et al., 1993, 1994). Высокая концентрация западнопалеарктических неморальных видов, находящихся на хребте Шайтантау на восточных границах своих ареалов, отмечена также среди Cerambycidae (Шаповалов, 2011) и Curculionoidea (Дедюхин, Филимонов, 2020). Таким образом, данные по разным группам растительноядных жуков служат весомым доводом в пользу наличия на западном макросклоне Южного Урала позднеплейстоценового неморального рефугиума биоты.

Зоогеографическую структуру анализируемой фауны жуков-листоедов наглядно сопоставить с аналогичной структурой фауны надсемейства Curculionoidea, еще одной хорошо изученной в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» группы жуков-фитофагов. Ранее был опубликован видовой список, включающий 289 видов

из четырех семейств этой группы (Дедюхин, Филимонов, 2020). К настоящему времени известное видовое богатство Curculionoidea в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» составляет 294 вида (Дедюхин, 2021а,б). В публикациях освещены и главные зоогеографические черты фауны Curculionoidea заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», но соотношение ареалогических комплексов этой локальной фауны в данной статье приводится впервые (табл. 3).

Анализ показывает заметные различия в хорологической структуре фаун семейства Chrysomelidae и надсемейства Curculionoidea заповедника «Шайтан-Тау». Обращает на себя внимание более высокая доля среди Chrysomelidae видов с очень широкими ареалами – транспалеарктическими и западно-центрально-палеарктическими (69.5% против 57.8%) и, напротив, гораздо меньшее участие западно- (12.8% против 19.7%) и, особенно, центральнопалеарктических (3.9% против 12.2%) форм. Аналогичные различия между двумя группами были установлены и для фауны Жигулевского заповедника (Дедюхин, 2023а), а также при сравнительном анализе их фаун на востоке Русской равнины в целом (Дедюхин, 2016а). Так, на центральнопалеарктический комплекс в фауне востока Русской равнины среди Curculionidae (центральное семейство Curculionoidea) приходится 16.5% видов, тогда как в фауне Chrysomelidae лишь 9.5%. То есть данные различия имеют общий характер и обусловлены специфическими чертами в экологических предпочтениях этих двух групп жуков-фитофагов, а также историческими причинами. В частности, большим

значением востока Древнего Средиземья как важного центра разнообразия богатых ксерофильных групп Curculionidae (в частности, подсемейство Lixinae и триба Tychiini) (Тер-Минасян, 1967, 1988; Байтенов, 1974; Alonso-Zarazaga et al., 2023). Хотя среди Chrysomelidae также есть группы древнесредиземноморского происхождения (например, подрод *Asionus* рода *Cryptocephalus* Geoffr., род *Pachybrachis* Chev. (Лопатин, 2010). Но в целом в фауне Северной Палеарктики преобладают мезофильные и гигрофильные формы европейского, ангарского и восточноазиатского генезиса (Медведев, Дубешко, 1972; Лопатин, 1979; Дубешко, Медведев, 1989).

При сравнении долготных комплексов обращает на себя внимание, что среди Curculionidae гораздо меньше доля полизональных (40.5% против 50.6%) и бореальных видов (3.7% против 8.9%). При этом более трети фауны (34%) приходится на суббореальный комплекс. Это также согласуется с результатами сравнительного хорологического анализа жуков-фитофагов востока Русской равнины (Дедюхин, 2016а).

Биотопические группы

Анализ экологических групп, выделенных по ландшафтно-биотопическому преферендуму (табл. 4), показал, что основу изученной фауны составляют виды, населяющие открытые биотопы (в общей сложности 103 вида; 57.2%), в том числе представители степной (22 вида), лугово-степной (21 вид), луговой (19 видов), и пионерной (включая рудерально-степную) (14 видов) групп. Заметную долю составляют также эврибионты травянистых местообитаний (28 видов).

Таблица 3. Соотношение ареалогических комплексов в фаунах Chrysomelidae и Curculionoidea заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (Россия)

Table 3. The ratio of the areal complexes of Chrysomelidae and Curculionoidea in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia

Комплексы	Chrysomelidae		Curculionoidea	
	Число видов	Доля в фауне, %	Число видов	Доля в фауне, %
Широтные комплексы				
Голарктический	11	6.1	13	4.4
Транспалеарктический	55	30.6	57	19.4
Западно-центрально-палеарктический	70	38.9	113	38.4
Западнопалеарктический	22	12.2	58	19.7
Центральнопалеарктический	7	3.9	36	12.2
Центрально-восточнопалеарктический и субтрансевразиатский	14	7.8	16	5.4
Условные эндемики Урала	1	0.6	1	0.6
Долготные комплексы				
Бореальный и арктобореальный	16	8.9	11	3.7
Полизональный (включая температурный)	91	50.6	119	40.5
Южнобореально-суббореальный	36	20.0	64	21.8
Суббореальный	37	20.6	100	34.0

Таблица 4. Соотношение биотопических групп в фауне Chrysomelidae некоторых крупных ООПТ Южного Урала и Поволжья (Россия)**Table 4.** The ratio of biotopic groups in the Chrysomelidae fauna in some large Protected Areas of the Southern Urals and River Volga Region, Russia

Биотопические группы	Национальный парк «Хвалынский»	Жигулевский заповедник	Геопарк «Торатау»	Заповедник «Шайтан-Тау»	Ильменский заповедник	Оренбургский заповедник (участок Ащисайская степь)
Степная	54 (22.3%)	42 (18.3%)	43 (21.7%)	22 (12.2%)	13 (7.9%)	39 (40.6%)
Луговая	38 (15.7%)	24 (10.4%)	34 (17.2%)	19 (10.6%)	33 (20.1%)	9 (9.4%)
Лугово-степная	17 (7.0%)	20 (8.7%)	14 (7.1%)	21 (11.7%)	11 (6.7%)	8 (8.3%)
Пионерная (рудеральная)	17 (7.0%)	11 (4.8%)	8 (4.0%)	5 (2.8%)	10 (6.1%)	4 (4.2%)
Рудерально-степная	8 (3.3%)	13 (5.6%)	5 (2.5%)	9 (5.0%)	1 (0.6%)	6 (6.3%)
Лесная	30 (12.4%)	42 (18.3%)	26 (13.1%)	31 (17.2%)	37 (22.6%)	1 (1.0%)
Околоводная	52 (21.5%)	40 (17.4%)	35 (17.7%)	39 (21.7%)	38 (23.2%)	15 (15.6%)
Эврибионты травянистых биотопов	22 (9.1%)	32 (13.9%)	26 (13.1%)	28 (15.6%)	15 (9.1%)	13 (13.5%)
Широкие эврибионты	4 (1.7%)	6 (2.6%)	6 (3.0%)	6 (3.3%)	6 (3.7%)	1 (1.0%)
Всего видов	242	230	198	180	164	96

Степные виды концентрируются в разнотравных, петрофитных и петрофитно-кустарниковых степях. К этой группе относятся, например, *Labidostomis sibirica*, *Clytra atraphaxidis* (Pallas, 1773), *Cryptocephalus flavicollis* Fabricius, 1781, *C. apicalis* Gebler, 1830, *C. violaceus* Laicharting, 1781, *C. virens* Suffrian, 1847, *C. elongatus* Germar, 1823, *C. elegantulus* Gravenhorst, 1807, *Luperus kiesenwetteri* Joannis, 1865, *Phyllotreta erysimi* Weise, 1900, *P. praticola* Weise, 1887, *Aphthona gracilis* Faldermann, 1837, *A. nigriscutis* Foudras, 1860, *Longitarsus absynthii* Kutschera, 1862, *Argopus nigritarsis* (Gebler, 1823), *Dibolia carpathica* Weise, 1893). Обращает на себя внимание гораздо меньшее разнообразие видов степной группы, чем в большинстве других ООПТ лесостепной и степной зон (22 против 39–54 видов; 12% против 18–22%). Только в Ильменском заповеднике доля видов степной группы гораздо меньше (13; 7.9%) (табл. 4).

К лесной группе фауны Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» относится 32 вида (17.8%). В нее входят почти исключительно обитатели лиственных деревьев и кустарников, в том числе семь видов рода *Cryptocephalus* (большая часть полифаги), *Pachybrachis tessellatus* и *Altica quercetorum* (на *Quercus robur* L.), *Chrysomela populi* Linnaeus, 1758, *Gonioctena decemnotata* (Marshall, 1802) и *Crepidodera lamina* (на *Populus tremula*), *Gonioctena flavicornis* (на *Salix caprea*) (рис. 2B), *Gonioctena quinquepunctata* (на *Prunus padus*), *Xanthogaleruca luteola* (рис. 2C) и *Luperus xanthopoda* (на *Ulmus glabra* и *U. laevis* Pall.). Некоторые жуки-листоеды встречаются в лесах на травянистом ярусе, но большинство из них относится к эврибионтам. Лишь единичные виды из них предпочитают лесные биотопы. Доля лесных видов равна или выше, чем в большинстве анализируемых локальных фаун, уступая лишь

Жигулевскому заповеднику (42 вида; 42%) (где также обширные площади в Жигулевских горах и пойме Волги покрыты лесами) и Ильменскому заповеднику (37 видов; 22.6%), расположенному на южной границе лесной зоны Зауралья.

С водной и околоводной растительностью поймы р. Сакмары тесно связано 39 видов. Это шесть видов подсемейства Donaciinae, развивающихся на водных и амфибионтных растениях, хортобионты, обитающие в заболоченных и прибрежных биотопах (*Chrysolina polita* (Linnaeus, 1758) и *Longitarsus lycopi* (Foudras, 1860) (на *Mentha* spp. и *Lycopus* spp.), *Prasocuris phellandrii* (Linnaeus, 1758) (на *Caltha palustris* L. и околоводных Apiaceae), *Phaedon cochleariae* (Fabricius, 1792), *Phyllotreta dilatata* и *Phyllotreta tetrastigma* (олигофаги Brassicaceae, в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» собраны на *Rorippa palustris* (L.) Besser), *Galerucella pusilla* (Duftschmid, 1825), *Lythriaria salicariae* (Paykull, 1800) и *Aphthona lutescens* (Gyllenhal, 1813) (на *Lythrum salicaria* L.), *Phyllotreta quadrimaculata* (Linnaeus, 1758) (на *Scutellaria* spp.), *Hippuriphila modeeri* (на *Equisetum fluviatile* L.), *Epitrix pubescens* (Koch, 1803) и *Psylliodes dulcamarae* (Koch, 1803) (на *Solanum* spp.), *Altica engstroemi* (на *Filipendula ulmaria* (L.) Maxim.), *Altica lythri* (на *Epilobium hirsutum* L.)). Преимущественно в прибрежных ивняках и ольшаниках встречается ряд дендробионтов, например, *Labidostomis lepida*, *Smaragdina flavicollis* (Charpentier, 1825), *Chrysomela cuprea*, *C. vigintipunctata*, *Gonioctena linnaeana* (Schrank, 1781), *Crepidodera plutus* (Latreille, 1804), *Altica tamaricis* Schrank, 1785, *Chaetocnema semicoerulea* (Koch, 1803).

Обращает на себя внимание низкая представленность в фауне заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» видов нарушенных местообитаний (рудеральная и рудерально-степная группы) (14 против 24 видов в Жигулевском заповеднике). Это подчеркивает

слабую степень антропогенной трансформации этой локальной фауны. При этом не зарегистрировано ни одного инвазионного вида.

Трофические связи

По широте регионального трофического спектра наиболее богатая группа Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» – широкие (включая умеренных) олигофаги (82 вида; 45.6%). Довольно большая доля и узкоспециализированных форм (60 видов; 33.3%). Среди них преобладают узкие олигофаги (48 видов). Гораздо меньше региональных монофагов (12 видов). К многоядным формам относятся 38 видов (21.1%). Это в целом типично для жуков-листоедов, среди которых преобладают виды, трофически специализированные на уровне семейств растений (Беньковский, 2011; Dedyukhin, 2016). При этом доля полифагов и широких олигофагов несколько выше, чем в среднем для фауны востока Европейской России (Dedyukhin, 2016), что характерно для лесных зон и северной лесостепи. Это дополнительно подчеркивает специфику фауны низкогорий Южного Урала, где даже на самом юге лесостепной зоны обширные площади занимают лесные ландшафты.

Трофически специализированные виды (олигофаги и монофаги) фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» связаны с растениями из 30 семейств. Самые крупные группы представлены на Asteraceae (22 вида) и Salicaceae (21 вид), далее по убыванию следуют группировки на Brassicaceae (16 видов), Lamiaceae (девять видов), Euphorbiaceae (семь видов), Poaceae и Rosaceae (по шесть видов), Betulaceae (пять видов). На остальных 23 семействах растений встречаются от одного до четырех видов. В фауне Жигулевского заповедника (Дедюхин, 2023а) общий спектр заселяемых жуками-листоедами семейств растений гораздо шире (38 видов), а на Asteraceae обитает гораздо больше видов, чем на Salicaceae (28 видов и 23 вида, соответственно). Кроме того, богатые группировки там связаны также с семействами Plantaginaceae s.l. (восемь видов против четырех в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау») и Boraginaceae (шесть видов против трех в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау»). Эти различия обусловлены более низкими разнообразием Chrysomelidae и таксономическим богатством флоры хребта Шайтантау в сравнении с таковыми в Жигулевских горах.

Анализ связей жуков-листоедов с основными типами жизненных форм растений показал резкое преобладание в фауне заповедника «Шайтан-Тау»

хортобионтов (118 видов; 65.6%). На древесных и кустарниковых растениях обитают 46 видов дендробионтов и тамнобионтов (25.6%). Семь видов могут питаться на деревьях и на травах (дендрохортобионты). Такая доля хортобионтов в целом характерна для фаун лесостепных ландшафтов при том, что процент дендробионтов среди Chrysomelidae заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» соответствует фаунам лесных зон (Dedyukhin, 2016). Еще одной особенностью изученной локальной фауны является низкое разнообразие видов, развивающихся на водных или амфибионтных растениях (гидатобионты) (девять видов; 5% против 9% в фауне лесостепной зоны востока Русской равнины). Вероятно, это связано с отсутствием на территории заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» открытых и сильно заросших растительностью мелководных водоемов, выступающих основными местами концентрации таких форм. Например, в богатом озерами Ильменском заповеднике встречаются 14 видов подсемейства Donaciinae, тогда как в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» отмечено всего пять видов.

Ландшафтно-биотопические комплексы

Анализ ландшафтно-биотопического распределения жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (табл. 5; Электронное приложение 1) показал, что наибольшее их разнообразие сосредоточено в нагорной части ООПТ (в общей сложности 126 видов) с максимумом в разнотравных степях и на остепненных лугах (72 вида). Заметно меньше (46 видов) отмечено в петрофитно-степных местообитаниях, включая горные обнажения. Для этого комплекса характерны, например, *Clytra atraphaxidis*, *Cryptocephalus flavicollis*, *C. virens*, *C. connexus* Olivier, 1807, *Luperus kiesenwetteri*, *Phyllotreta erysimi*, *P. praticola*, *Aphthona nigriscutis*, *A. gracilis*, *Longitarsus absynthii*. При этом видовое богатство и специфичность комплексов жуков-листоедов в горных степях заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» заметно ниже, чем в каменистых степях на известняковых или меловых останцах возвышенностей востока Русской равнины и Предуралья, в частности, в аналогичных местообитаниях Жигулевских гор (Дедюхин, 2023а) и Стерлитамакских шиханов (Дедюхин, 2019б; Dedyukhin, 2020; Dedyukhin & Martynenko, 2020). Вероятно, это обусловлено неблагоприятными условиями для многих петрофитно-степных жуков-листоедов, складывающимися в горных степях на серпентинитах, при отсутствии здесь карбонатных обнажений, что заметно обедняет и петрофитно-степную флору.

Таблица 5. Видовое богатство Chrysomelidae в основных типах биотопов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (Россия)
Table 5. Species richness of Chrysomelidae in the main biotope types in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia

Типы биотопов	Общее число видов	Число видов, отмеченных только в одном типе биотопов
Петрофитные степи, скалы и осыпи	46	6
Разнотравные степи и остепненные луга	72	11
Широколиственные леса и опушки	53	14
Заросли степных кустарников	40	3
Пойма р. Сакмары	113	54
Всего	180	88

В петрофитно-кустарниковых степях и в зарослях степных кустарников зарегистрировано 40 видов жуков-листоедов. Очень характерными для этих биотопов являются *Labidostomis sibirica*, *Cryptocephalus elongatus*, *C. laevicollis*, *C. schaefferi*, *Pachybrachis tessellatus*. Нередки в кустарниковых степях и некоторые типичные степные формы, например, *Cryptocephalus flavicollis* и *C. violaceus*.

В широколиственных лесах заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» (включая редколесья и опушки) в общей сложности встречается 53 вида. Большая часть из них дендробионты. Характерной чертой сообществ жуков-листоедов горных дубрав выступает большая доля видов, населяющих кустарниковый и травянистый ярусы, что обусловлено разреженностью этих лесов и непосредственным контактом со степными и кустарниковыми биотопами. Характерными видами травянистого яруса лесов являются *Lilioceris lili* (Scopoli, 1763) (на *Lilium pilosiusculum* (Freyn) Misch.), *Oulema erichsonii* (Suffrian, 1841) (на Poaceae), *Chrysolina fastuosa* (Scopoli, 1763) и *Cassida viridis* Linnaeus, 1758 (широкие олигофаги на Lamiaceae), *Chrysolina sturmi* (Westhoff, 1882) (на *Glechoma hederacea* L.), *Derocrepis rufipes* (Linnaeus, 1758) (олигофаг на некоторых родах Fabaceae, под пологом лесов обычен на *Lathyrus vernus* (L.) Bernh.). При этом строго лесных хортобионтных видов на территории заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» нет. Все они встречаются и во влажных травянистых сообществах (луга, опушки, берега водоемов).

Вторым центром видового разнообразия жуков-листоедов (113 видов) в заповеднике «Шайтан-Тау» выступает сравнительно узкая пойма р. Сакмары. Пойменный комплекс неоднороден. С одной стороны, он представлен обитателями водных и прибрежных травянистых биотопов (речные заводи, лесные старицы и их берега), где зарегистрировано 82 вида. С другой, этот комплекс включает умеренные леса (тополевики, ольшаники, прибрежные ивняки) (в общей сложности 34 вида). Подчеркнем, что во влажных тенистых (подгорных) участках поймы сконцентрированы почти все отмеченные выше бореальные и аркто-

бореальные виды, находящиеся здесь на южных пределах своих ареалов.

В целом, состав жуков-листоедов в горной и пойменной частях заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» имеет кардинальные различия (коэффициент Жаккара: 0.32). Если основу комплекса горных сопок и водораздельного плато составляют степные, лугово-степные и широколиственно-лесные виды, то в пойме сконцентрированы околородные формы хорто- и дендро-тамнобионтов, а также несколько видов гидробионтов.

Заключение

Известный состав фауны жуков-листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» включает 180 видов. По числу видов она сопоставима или заметно превосходит другие локальные фауны эталонных ООПТ Южного Урала и несколько беднее фаун крупных ООПТ лесостепи Среднего Поволжья. Другой чертой изученной фауны является ее комплексный состав, определяемый сочетанием степных, неморальных и бореальных форм (многие из которых находятся здесь на границах своих ареалов), а также резко выраженной мозаичностью биотопических комплексов (лесных, степных, луговых, околородных). Специфика фауны заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» как низкогорной фауны Южного Урала подчеркивается тем, что соотношения в ней ареалогических комплексов и экологических групп не находят полных аналогий в зональных фаунах востока Русской равнины. Зоогеографическая структура фауны Chrysomelidae заметно отличается от фауны Curculionoidea заповедника «Шайтан-Тау», в частности, по степени представленности центрально-, западно- и транспалеарктических видов. Это связано с особенностями распространения и экологии этих крупнейших групп жуков-фитофагов. Анализ пространственного распределения жуков-листоедов на территории заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» показал наибольшее разнообразие их в нагорной части ООПТ, где преобладает дубравная лесостепь с пятнами петрофитных степей на ксерофитных склонах и разнотравно-ковыльными степями на высоком плато (в общей сложности 126 видов). Вторым центром

видового богатства Chrysomelidae выступает пойма р. Сакмары, где на околородной растительности, пойменных лугах и в уремных лесах зарегистрировано 113 видов.

Обобщая, можно сделать заключение, что высокий уровень видового богатства и заметное своеобразие фауны листоедов заповедника «Шайтан-Тау» обусловлены не столько высоким уровнем разнообразия этой группы в конкретных растительных сообществах, сколько мозаичным сочетанием на небольшой территории дубравной лесостепи, разнотравных и петрофитных степей в горной части заповедника, лесных, луговых и околородных местообитаний в пойме р. Сакмары. В целом, изученная фауна жуков-листоедов может рассматриваться как эталонная для дубравной лесостепи низкогорий Южного Урала.

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Дополнительная информация

Дополнительная информация к статье Дедюхина (2024) может быть найдена в [Электронном приложении](#).

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FAUNA AND BIOTOPIC DISTRIBUTION OF CHRYSOMELIDAE (COLEOPTERA) IN THE SHAITAN-TAU STATE NATURE RESERVE, RUSSIA

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Research on taxonomically diverse groups of insects are an important component of studying biodiversity in Protected Areas of various ranks. Based on the results of original studies (2017–2020), this paper presents for the first time data on the Chrysomelidae family and its species composition in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, Russia. The study area is located in the south of the forest-steppe zone of the low mountains of the Southern Urals in the Orenburg Region, Russia. Currently, this Chrysomelidae fauna is one of the most studied ones in Protected Areas of the Southern Urals. In the study area, 180 Chrysomelidae species have been registered, which is 51% of the Chrysomelidae family in the Orenburg Region. In addition, 86 recorded species were found for the first time in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve, including eight species recorded for the first time in the Orenburg Region. A new species of the genus *Altica* was discovered in the study area. In terms of the level of species richness, the Chrysomelidae family of the Shaitan-Tau Nature Reserve is comparable with or noticeably richer than other local faunas of the Protected Areas of the Southern Urals. At the same time, this Chrysomelidae fauna has fewer species than of other state nature reserves and national parks in the forest-steppe zone of the Volga Upland. Features of the zoogeographical structure of the Chrysomelidae family in the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve include quite a high number of West-Palaeartic species (23 species; 12.8%), many of which are located there on the eastern limit of their natural ranges, and a low proportion of Central Palaeartic species (3.9%). At the same time, two Siberian species were discovered (*Labidostomis sibirica* and *Gonioctena flavicornis*), which are located on relict island sites of their ranges in the Urals. These findings noticeably distinguish the studied fauna from the Chrysomelidae of the steppe Protected Areas in the south of the Orenburg Region, where a considerable proportion are representatives of the Kazakh-Turanian genesis. The studied Chrysomelidae fauna is characterised by a set of rich groups of steppe, meadow-steppe, nemoral and, to a lesser extent, boreal forms (a large part of which are located on the limits of their ranges in the study area), as well as a pronounced spatial mosaic of biotopic complexes (e.g. forest, steppe, floodplains). In general, the data presented in this study objectively characterise the Chrysomelidae fauna of the Shaitan-Tau State Nature Reserve as a reference for the Ural oak forest-steppe ecosystem, which emphasises its important role for the conservation of natural complexes, as well as the knowledge of the current state and historical stages of the formation of biota of the western macroslope of the South Urals.

Key words: insect community, Orenburg Region, Protected Area, phytophagous beetles, South Urals, species composition, trophic association, zoogeographical analysis

THE VASCULAR FLORA OF THE FORESTE CASENTINESI, MONTE FALTERONA, CAMPIGNA NATIONAL PARK (NORTHERN APENNINES, ITALY): UPDATING THE CHECKLIST

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Plant species inventories are crucial for botanical research and plant conservation, as they provide fundamental data regarding the measurement and distribution of biodiversity. To be effective, floristic lists must be prepared and continuously updated at global and local level. For these reasons, this study was aimed to update and discuss the vascular plant list of the flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, an important Italian Protected Area located in the Northern Apennines (Italy). We implemented the existing checklist published in 2010 (with data updated to 2008) by analysing both published and unpublished data up to 31.12.2023. We also carried out some museum checks on exsiccata in the Central Italic Herbarium of Florence and in other herbaria. The study was also aimed to verify whether the updated native and alien floristic richness of the area resulted to be higher or lower than expected. In total, the number of species recorded are 1415. Of these, 1172 species from 100 families are considered native confirmed by data obtained after 1960, while others can be distinguished as non-native to the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park territory (mostly cultivated), doubtful, or in some cases excluded. There was an increase of 58 species compared to 2010, of which 45 are native. According to the best performing species-area formula with respect to vascular plant species, in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park the native floristic richness resulted to be a little higher than expected (1172 against 1159). At the same time, the alien floristic richness (naturalised and invasive species, as no casuals were detected) resulted to be much lower than expected (24 against 109), reinforcing the already well-known great conservation value of this area. The extent of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park's phytodiversity is confirmed to be very high. This is caused by the fact that this territory hosts forest ecosystems of great value, considered among those best preserved at European level, and has a geographical position that makes it a connection between two very differentiated floristic contingents, one coming from the north (Alps, Northern Apennines) and the other from the south (Italian Peninsula, Central and Southern Apennines). The updated characteristics of the chorology shows in fact that various plants in Italy have their southern or northern distribution limit here. However, the Italian endemism that characterises the flora is essentially north-Apennine and peninsular (3.1%), while the most consistent chorotype, in percentage terms, is the European *sensu lato* (> 25.5%). The life-form spectrum, the presence of rare, conservation-interest, doubtful and alien species are also updated and discussed. The characteristics of all the confirmed flora and of the flora of conservation interest with respect to the various habitats are outlined. The updated checklist provides the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park with an essential database to manage this territory, and quite precisely quantified the plant diversity present here. Moreover, it has highlighted the lacunae in floristic knowledge, towards which future research should be directed, giving information about rare plants, species not reported after 1960, and taxa, which need to be studied taxonomically more in depth, since the flora varies over time and the checklists, like any other information tool, must be implemented and continuously improved.

Key words: chorology, conservation, distribution, floristic inventory, plant taxonomy, Protected Area

Introduction

Plant species inventories are crucial for botanical research and plant conservation, as they provide fundamental data regarding the measurement and distribution of biodiversity (Mace, 2004; Funk, 2006; Smith & Figueiredo, 2010; Peruzzi, 2018; Borsch et al., 2020; Wagensommer, 2023). To be effective, inventories must be prepared and continuously updated at global (e.g. Govaerts et al., 2021; Schellenberger Costa et al., 2023), national (e.g. Buttler & Hand, 2008; Danihelka et al., 2012; Dimopoulos et al., 2013; 2016; Niketić et al., 2018; Bartolucci et al., 2018; 2024; Galasso et al., 2018, 2024;

Baasanmunkh et al., 2022; Odorico et al., 2022) and regional level (e.g. Anzalone et al., 2010; Hand et al., 2019, 2024; Beierkuhnlein et al., 2021).

Also on a local scale, each Protected Area requires a high level of knowledge to be able to best implement the conservation and promotion policies of its territory, and, therefore, species inventories have been carried out in many Protected Areas (e.g. Conti, 1995; Anzalone et al., 1997; Conti et al., 2020; Boychuk, 2021). For this reason, the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park has promoted numerous research initiatives over time regarding the naturalistic components, including the

vascular flora. Since 2005, the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park Authority has in fact commissioned a project to find, gather and update all the information relating to the reports of floristic species in its territory, aimed at creating an updated checklist and a computerised database of the vascular flora. This was done not because the floristic information was poor but, on the contrary, because it was a lot but highly non-homogeneous, in terms of type of source, date, nomenclature, and was therefore difficult to use. This project also led to the publication of a summary study (Viciani et al., 2010), which represented the first comprehensive list of the vascular flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park.

The area named in the past «Foreste Casentinesi», considered in their broadest sense (so only partially coinciding with the current Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park territory), have a very ancient history. The first data date back to 1012, a year, when, according to an uncertain tradition, the first monastic nucleus of the Camaldolesi settled in the area (Padula & Crudele 1988; Padula, 1995; Cavagna & Cian, 2003). However, it is certain that the monks expanded their property to a large part of this area, spread the cultivation of *Abies alba* Mill., prevented the growth of *Fagus sylvatica* L., and took care of the forest and developed a rigorous forestry code. Thus, they can be recognised as the initiators of the traditional *Abies alba* cultivation, considered a model to be followed until recent time. The subsequent events have been a subject of accurate and exhaustive historical reconstruction in various studies, which contain further information and insights (Cacciamani, 1965; Clauser, 1965; Siemoni, 1975; Gabbrielli & Settesoldi, 1977; Gabbrielli, 1978; Padula, 1983; Cavagna & Cian, 2003).

There are numerous scholars, who have carried out excursions and collected specimens in this area. As early as 1557, the famous botanist Ulisse Aldrovandi passed through Mt. Falterona and La Verna while travelling towards the Sibillini mountains (Pampanini, 1924; Pichi Sermolli, 1998), and at least one specimen (*Eryngium amethystinum* L.) in Andrea Cesalpino's Herbarium, probably one of the oldest in the world, dated 1563, comes from La Verna site (Cesalpino, 1583; Pichi Sermolli, 1998). Linnaeus (1753) described *Tozzia alpina* L. on basis of samples coming from this area, expressly citing Micheli (1729), with whom he was in contact (Viciani & Nepi, 2019). Since the list of scholars is very long, we refer to the study by Viciani et al. (2010), which contains an exhaustive examination of the

botanists, studied and/or published reports for this territory until 2009.

In 2010–2024, there have been numerous and important additional floristic reports and new data coming from taxonomic studies (e.g. Gonnelli & Bottacci, 2012; Viciani et al., 2013, 2021; Arrigoni, 2014; Nardi, 2015; Buldrini et al., 2017; Peruzzi et al., 2017, 2018, 2019, 2021; Gestri et al., 2021; Laghi et al., 2023; Pica & Laghi, 2023; Lastrucci et al., 2024). The Authority of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park also continued its policy and promoted the constant updating of data, so new locations were added to the already known flora. Moreover, in this period, species nomenclature has often profoundly changed, passing from that of Pignatti (1982a,b,c) to that of the Portal to the Flora of Italy (2023). The aim of this study was to produce and implement a new commented floristic checklist, updated to 31.12.2023. Moreover, since D'Antraccoli et al. (2024) recently highlighted and adapted for Italy the best performing species-area formula with respect to vascular plant species, another task was to verify if, according to this formula, the updated native and alien floristic richness resulted to be higher or lower than expected.

Material and Methods

The physical environment

The Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park territory covers an area of 368 km², divided more or less equally between Romagna and Tuscany (Fig. 1). It is situated across the Apennines and, therefore, it has a predominantly mountainous and sub-mountainous character. The highest peak is reached on Mt. Falco (1657 m a.s.l.) and Mt. Falterona (1654 m a.s.l.), while the minor altitudes are around 500 m a.s.l., with even lower peaks (see also Fig. S1 in Electronic Supplement 1). The Romagna territory is characterised by narrow, steep, embedded valleys, while the Tuscan territory is characterised by more gentle slopes and includes a small part of Mugello, a part of Casentino (which encompasses the upper River Arno valley, which springs are situated on the southern slopes of Mt. Falterona), and a continuation towards the east reaching the altitudes of the famous Franciscan Sanctuary of La Verna. More detailed information about orography, morphology, hydrography, and other characteristics can be found in Padula & Crudele (1988), Padula (1995), Cavagna & Cian (2003) and on the website of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park (www.parcforestecasentinesi.it).

Fig. 1. Geographical position and limits of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, located in the northern Apennines between Tuscany and Emilia Romagna administrative regions (Italy).

Four main geological formations are present in the study area (Carmignani et al., 2013). Most of the Tuscan side is formed of sandstone (known as «Macigno»), divided in two types, namely Chianti sandstone, particularly at higher altitudes, formed of siliceous sandstone with low percentages of limestone, and Mugello sandstone, formed of silty schists and at lower levels of marl and fine siliceous and calcareous sandstone. The La Verna altitudes in the south-eastern Tuscan part of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park are formed of solid «Alberese» limestone, which emerges above a chaotic series of clayey rocks. The Romagna side is more homogenous because sandstone-marly flysch formations are more widespread, formed of sandstones, siltstones and marls with intercalations of calcareous clasts and marly limestone. In the study area, there are also other geological formations, though with limited surfaces.

At the highest thermos-pluviometrical stations (Campigna and Camaldoli, at an altitude of about 1100 m a.s.l.), the annual average temperature ranges between 8°C and 8.4°C. The annual precipitation is very high, over 1750 mm (Padula & Crudele, 1988). Towards the crests, the difference in altitude accounts for lower temperature values and probably much higher rainfall values, while at lower altitudes there is an opposite trend. In general, the climate of the study area can be defined as a mountain type climate, not distinctly oceanic nor continental, with mesic temperature and heavy rainfall, which both reach their maximum between October and February and their minimum between June and August. Winters are relatively severe. Summers are relatively cool and humid, and the an-

nual temperature range is quite mild, although in recent decades global climate change has led to an increase in temperature in this area, too (Meteoblue, 2023). In terms of bioclimatic approach, the study area mostly falls within the temperate oceanic bioclimate, and only to a minimal extent, at lower altitudes, in the temperate sub-Mediterranean (Pesaresi et al., 2017).

The vegetation of the study area

The vegetation of the entire territory is characterised from a physiognomic point of view by large forest areas, many of which are of high conservation interest. It is well known the case of Sasso Fratino, the first integral Italian nature reserve, included in 2017 by the UNESCO Commission in the World Heritage Site among the old European beech forests, within the serial site «Ancient and Primeval Beech Forests of the Carpathians and Other Regions of Europe». However, there are also various and peculiar non-forest types in the study area, such as grasslands and pastures, shrublands, riparian and aquatic vegetation. Moreover, there are also important reforestations and arboretums in the study area (Crudele et al., 2002). Numerous vegetation-related studies relating to some areas or to some vegetation types of this territory are reported in the literature, from fundamental (e.g. Zangheri, 1966) to many others, referred in Viciani et al. (2010). The Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park has also sponsored, for internal uses, the creation of a vegetation map of its area, with a scale of 1 : 10 000, of which a derived map with a scale of 1 : 50 000 (Verdecchia et al., 2009) and the descriptive notes (Viciani & Agostini, 2009) have been published. Further information is present in some subsequent vegetation studies (e.g. Lelli et al., 2021; Viciani et al., 2022; Lastrucci et al., 2023), that have been taken into account in the present study.

The floristic information included in this study was obtained by analysing both published and unpublished studies, which are reported in the bibliography of the floristic list in Electronic Supplement 1. The data are updated to 31.12.2023. The information was selected when it expressly or reasonably referred to localities that are completely or partly situated within the study area. Further information on the considered floristic data is present in Viciani et al. (2010). The nomenclature of species is given in accordance with the Portal to the Flora of Italy (2023). In agreement with the latter, the published data were generally considered still current, when they were dated after 1960. When it was possible to clarify some doubts, museum checks were carried out. Specifically, we visited the Central Italic Herbarium of Florence (Herbarium

Centrale Italicum, FI; the international abbreviations of herbaria are in accordance with Thiers, 2023), the Herbarium of La Verna (Herbarium Alvernae) preserved at the homonymous Franciscan Sanctuary, and the Herbarium Zangherii, stored in the herbarium of the Civic Museum of Natural History of Verona (VER). When the only information was derived from unpublished sources, like degree theses, phytosociological surveys or other similar sources, and no specimen that could be checked was available, the reports were considered as data to be confirmed. Many clarifications have been specified case by case in the notes to the species in Electronic Supplement 1.

In addition to the scientific name of the plants and the list of locations, the following information has been characterised. Raunkiaer (1934) life form classification is provided according to Pignatti (1982a,b,c) and Pignatti et al. (2017a,b, 2018, 2019), with the following groups: chamephytes, geophytes, hemicryptophytes, hydrophytes, helophytes, phanerophytes, and therophytes. Chorological categories are based on Pignatti (1982a,b,c) and Pignatti et al. (2017a,b, 2018, 2019), simplified as follows: cosmopolitan/wide distribution, boreal, Eurasian, European, European Orophile, South-European, South-European Orophile, South European-Mediterranean, Mediterranean, Mediterranean Orophile, and Apennine Endemic species. Non-native plants were distinguished in cultivated (known only in the culture) and alien species. According to their status in Tuscany and Emilia-Romagna, alien species were sub-divided in alien invasive and alien naturalised (no alien casual was found). The habitats, around which the taxa gravitate primarily, have been distinguished on the following groups: non-acid shrubs and bushes; acidophilic heaths and shrubs; mesophilic woods (e.g. beech woods, mixed woods) and their borders and clearings; humid woods, riparian tree communities and their borders and clearings; relatively thermoxerophilic woods and their borders and clearings; high-altitude semi-mesophilic grasslands; grasslands in the steep rocky areas close to the crest; humid and hay meadows, tall herb edge communities, riparian herbaceous plant communities; dry grasslands; rocks, both heliophilous and sciaphilous rocky environments, walls, stony ground soils, talus slopes; ruderal and sinanthropic environments, including uncultivated land in the first post-cultivation stages and weeds in cultivated land; ponds, water bodies with hydrophytes.

In the list of plant species (Electronic Supplement 1), we indicated, whether the taxon is doubtful, excluded or reported before 1960 and not found again after this year, and whether it is rare in the study area and, if its presence is of phytogeographic importance.

We also indicated, if the taxon is included in some attention lists of local conservation interest (see also Electronic Supplement 1) and/or in the most recent Italian Red Lists (Rossi et al., 2013, 2020). In this case, the national threat status is indicated with the abbreviations accepted by IUCN (2012).

To verify whether the native and alien floristic richness of the study area resulted to be higher or lower than expected, we refer to D'Antraccoli et al. (2024). They compared many formulas and found that the best performing species-area formula with respect to vascular plant species resulted to be the Arrhenius' Power function ($S = c \times A^z$). They calculated the constants for native ($c = 245.2$ and $z = 0.263$) and alien ($c = 10.1$ and $z = 0.404$) species in Italy, so we could apply this formula to our data.

Results and Discussion

The complete floristic list, reported in Electronic Supplement 1, is made up of 1415 taxa. Of them, 77 species are cultivated non-native plants. Eleven species were excluded and 131 species are doubtful or not found after 1960. Without considering excluded, doubtful and cultivated plants, the flora is made up of 1172 native and 24 alien species. The confirmed native taxa are divided into 100 families. The most numerous families are Asteraceae (138 species), Poaceae (107 species) and Fabaceae (89 species). Lamiaceae (55 species), Rosaceae (54 species), Caryophyllaceae (47 species), Apiaceae (46 species), Brassicaceae (46 species) and Orchidaceae (49 species) are also well represented. Compared to Viciani et al. (2010), there was an increase in 58 new taxa, of which 45 species were native due to the inclusion of new floristic records. This is also caused by changes in species status in the opposite direction. For instance, *Ribes petraeum* Wulfen or *Anacamptys laxiflora* (Lam.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase, regarded as confirmed, were recently considered doubtful, as reported in Viciani (2012) and Pica & Laghi (2023). Table 1 shows a summary of the data comparing the 2008 list and the 2023 checklists.

Detected and expected floristic richness

According to the formula proposed by D'Antraccoli et al. (2024), in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park the native floristic richness (Fig. 2) resulted to be a little higher than expected (1172 against 1159 species). At the same time, alien floristic richness (casual, naturalised and invasive species) resulted to be much lower than expected (24 against 109 species). This data reinforce the already well-known great conservation value of the study area.

Table 1. The flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park: data from the floristic lists of 2008 and 2023 compared

Parameters	Viciani et al. (2010)	Present study
Total number of species	1357	1415 (+58)
Confirmed native species	1127	1172 (+45)
Non-native cultivated species	74	77 (+3)
Alien species	18	24 (+6)
Doubtful occurring species at present (including species not confirmed after 1960)	138	131 (-7)
Excluded species	0	11 (+11)
Families	97	100 (+3)

The life-form spectrum

The life-form spectrum (Fig. 3) shows very similar values to those found in 2008 (Viciani et al., 2010). In accordance with the climatic-environmental position of the study area, it shows a clear prevalence of hemicryptophytes (45%). Therophytes account for approximately 23% of the total number of species; they are most likely distributed prevalently in open areas of the lower altitudes. Geophytes and phanerophytes are well represented (15% and 11%, respectively), while chamaephytes remain below 5%. Hydrophytes and helophytes increase slightly (from 0.9% to 1.2%), compared to the previous floristic list (Viciani et al., 2010); although wetlands are very rare, small and fragmented in the study area, recent research has increased the list of aquatic and marsh species (e.g. Buldrini et al., 2017; Viciani et al., 2022; Lastrucci et al., 2023).

As it had already been highlighted previously (e.g. Viciani et al., 2010), if we calculate the life-form spectrum relating to the forest flora alone, in addition to a notable proportion of phanerophytes (26%), we also have a very high proportion of geophytes (28%). In boreal deciduous broadleaf forests, this is an indication of habitat maturity, as the nemoral geophytes are adapted to inhabit fully-developed forest habitats (Ferrari et al., 1979; Walter, 1979; Blasi et al., 1990). In accordance with Midolo et al. (2024), in these forests hemicryptophytes are always dominant (41%), while therophytes decrease strongly (3%).

The chorological spectrum

The general chorological spectrum is shown in Fig. 4. It is very similar to that presented in Viciani et al. (2010), although there are some differences. The most represented chorotype is the European sensu lato species (> 25.5%), within which the South-European Orophiles (5.4%) and the South-Europeans (3.5%) have the largest proportions, followed by the Eurasian (19.1%) and the Boreal (12.4%) ones.

The elements of connection between the Boreal and Tethys sub-kingdoms are also important, among which the South European-Mediterranean one stands out (18%), while the Mediterranean spe-

cies are present in a low proportion (6.1%). The European Orophiles and the South-European Orophiles, together with the Mediterranean Orophiles, despite having not too high proportion (less than 10% in total), characterise the flora of the study area in an orophilous sense. The Apennine endemic taxa (> 3%) constitute a small part compared to the other groups. But they represent a very important component from a phytogeographic point of view. Among Apennine endemic taxa, there are plants with various distributions. For instance, there are punctiform endemisms limited to the study area and Abruzzo (e.g. *Hieracium dentatum* Hoppe subsp. *xanthostylophorum* Furrer & Zahn); taxa common in the whole of Italy and Corsica (e.g. *Robertia taraxacoides* (Loisel.) DC.) or distributed between Northern Italy and the central Apennines (e.g. *Tephrosieris italica* Holub, *Sedum monregalense* Balbis); species centrally distributed in the northern Apennines, which reach their southern or eastern limit in the study area (e.g. *Festuca violacea* Schleich. subsp. *puccinellii* (Parl.) Foggi, Graz., Rossi & Signorini, *Murbeckiella zanonii* (Ball) Rothm., *Sesleria pichiana* Foggi, Graz. Rossi & Pignotti); taxa common between the northern and central Apennines (e.g. *Festuca inops* De Not., *Centaurea arrigonii* Greuter, *C. nigrescens* Willd. subsp. *pinatifida* (Fiori) Dostál), species distributed more or less over the entire Italian Peninsula (e.g. *Polygala flavescens* DC., *Arenaria bertolonii* Fiori, *Viola eugeniae* Parl.). The endemic taxa that characterise this flora are essentially distributed in the Apennines and on the Italian peninsula. Indeed, as already noted previously (Viciani et al., 2010), although several species from the Tuscan-Emilia Apennines and the Alps reach this territory, the study area is phytogeographically closer to the peninsular Apennines than to the more northern Apennines, also because numerous northern Apennine endemic taxa are missing in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park (e.g. *Armeria arenaria* (Pers.) F.Dietr. subsp. *marginata* (Levier) Arrigoni, *Primula apennina* Widmer, *Festuca riccerii* Foggi & Gr.Rossi; see Alessandrini et al., 2003).

Fig. 2. The detected and expected floristic richness of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy based on to the formula proposed by D’Antraccoli et al. (2024).

Fig. 3. The life-form spectrum of the flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy. Designations: Ch – chamephytes, Hy – hydrophytes and helophytes, Ge – geophytes, He – hemicryptophytes, Ph – phanerophytes, Th – therophytes.

Fig. 4. The chorological spectrum of the flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy.

Alien species

The plants considered non-native in the study area amount to 101 taxa, most of which are cultivated in arboretums, reforestations, woods or farming and urbanised environments. Only a small part of them (24 species) reproduces naturally in

the study area, and can be defined as alien plants. According to Richardson et al. (2000), Blackburn et al. (2011) and to the Portal to the Flora of Italy (2023), they can be divided to naturalised and invasive species (see Fig. 5), as no casual species was detected. Amongst the naturalised alien plants, the herbaceous plants to be mentioned are, for example, *Brunnera macrophylla* (Adams) I.M.Johnston, *Oenothera glazioviana* Micheli, *Bromopsis inermis* (Leyss.) Holub, which have been reported more or less recently (see Frignani et al., 2006; Peruzzi et al., 2017, 2021; Laghi et al., 2023). At the same time, among naturalised trees *Pinus nigra* J.F.Arnold often tends to actively reproduce in pastures and open areas on calcareous substrata, *Pinus pinaster* Aiton often colonises open areas and low-altitude degraded forests on siliceous substrates, while *Alnus cordata* (Loisel.) Duby and *Juglans regia* L. sometimes spread in meso-hygrophilous environments and along water courses. Invasive alien plants are not numerous, but they must be carefully monitored. In this respect, the herbaceous plants to be mentioned are *Erigeron canadensis* L. and *Artemisia verlotiorum* Lamotte for ruderal environments, while *Paspalum distichum* L. and *Helianthus tuberosus* L. for riparian and wet habitats. Among trees, *Ailanthus altissima* (Mill.) Swing., *Robinia pseudacacia* L. and *Acer negundo* L. have the ability to spread quickly in various types of environments by transforming them. The relatively few alien taxa in this territory are the result of the further spread of already established invasive species and, again in the last 15 years, of accidental escapes from ornamental, horticulture and reforestation activities, which represent the main primary introduction pathway of alien plants in Europe (Arianoutsou et al., 2021; Galasso et al., 2024).

As above shown in Fig. 4, alien species form only 2% of the confirmed flora, confirming the good naturalness and conservation value of this territory. As for their areas of origin, more than half come from America, particularly North America (Fig. 6).

Rare species, phytogeographical and conservation interest species

The geographical position of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona and Campigna National Park makes this area a connecting territory between two very differentiated floristic contingents. In fact, several species, which presence is of phytogeographical interest, have in Italy their southern or northern distribution limit in the study area.

Fig. 5. The structure of non-native flora in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park (Italy) subdivided in only cultivated, naturalised and invasive species.

Fig. 6. The original distribution of alien species detected in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy.

Among the vascular plant taxa, which are on their southern border in the study area, the following examples can be mentioned: *Alnus incana* (L.) Moench, *Cardamine trifolia* L., *Allium victorialis* L., *Festuca violacea* subsp. *puccinellii*, *Murbeckiella zanonii*, *Sesleria pichiana*, *Tozzia alpina*, and *Vaccinium vitis-idaea* L. Also among ferns and fern allies, some species are situated on their southern border in the study area, namely *Lycopodium clavatum* L., *Spinulum annotinum* (L.) A.Haines, *Phegopteris connectilis* (Michx.) Watt., *Dryopteris expansa* (K. Presl) Fraser-Jenkins et Jermy, and *Matteuccia struthiopteris* (L.) Tod. can be mentioned (Gonnelli, 2005; Landi et al., 2016). On the other hand, some plants (e.g. *Ribes mul-*

tiflorum Kit. ex Roem. & Schult., *Carex macrolepis* DC., *Leucopoa dimorpha* (Guss.) H.Scholz & Foggi) have their northern or north-eastern distributional limit in the study area.

The species considered as rare in the floristic list are numerous. Many of them are rare within the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, but not in Italy and Europe. This is the case of several stenomediterranean species which, due to climate and altitude reasons, are very rare in the study area, but not in other places. Of a similarly relative rarity are those plants belonging to environments that are scarcely present in the study area, like aquatic habitats (e.g. *Potamogeton* spp., *Myriophyllum spicatum* L.) or traditionally agricultural systems, which have now reduced considerably (e.g. *Agrostemma githago* L., *Delphinium consolida* L., *Centaurea cyanus* L.). However, among the latest reports there are also plants of absolute rarity present in aquatic environments (*Hottonia palustris* L., *Utricularia australis* R.Br., *Carex pseudocyperus* L.). The species that are rare both in the study area and in the Apennines are more interesting from the conservation point of view. To the taxa already mentioned as of phytogeographic interest, we can add, for example, *Anemonastrum narcissiflorum* (L.) Holub, *Trollius europaeus* L., *Isopyrum thalictroides* L. There are also a lot of taxa considered rare, at least in the whole of Italy, both because they are naturally not widely spread (e.g. *Streptopus amplexifolius* (L.) DC., *Epipogium aphyllum* Sw., *Neottia cordata* (L.) Rich., *Ruscus hypoglossum* L.) and because of reduction or changes in the preferred habitats (e.g. *Carex strigosa* Huds., typical of mature riparian woods, which are always becoming more rare). The Authority of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park has promoted the setting up and updating of a geodatabase, which collects the list of species considered to be of interest with all the known georeferenced locations (Viciani et al., 2018).

Most of the above-mentioned taxa are also of conservation interest, as they are included in various national and regional lists. Specifically, among the confirmed native species, there are 91 taxa included in the Emilia Romagna regional law 2/1977, 175 species in the annexes of the Tuscany regional law 56/2000 (currently the same as the subsequent law 30/2015), 41 species in the Repertorio Naturalistico Toscano project (Regione Toscana, 2023), and 73 taxa in the old regional Red List (Conti et al., 1997). In addition, 46 taxa are included in the new national red lists, of which 8 species in Rossi

et al. (2013) and 38 species in Rossi et al. (2020). Most of these categories overlap. Some of the taxa are listed in the new national red lists because they are included in European lists, and not all are of particular interest or rarity (e.g. *Ruscus aculeatus* L., *Himantoglossum adriaticum* H.Baumann, *Galanthus nivalis* L.), while others are more or less rare and of conservation relevance (e.g. *Hottonia palustris* L., *Epipactis palustris* (Mill.) Crantz, *E. purpurata* Sm., *Orchis provincialis* L.). Several species are endemic to Italy (e.g. *Arenaria bertoloni*, *Arisarum proboscideum* (L.) Savi, *Tephroseria italica*) but not all of these are particularly rare or of interest at a local level (e.g. *Festuca inops*, *Sesleria italica* (Pamp.) Ujhelyi).

Data on the number of species of conservation interest at European/Italian level and at regional/local level are present in Fig. 7. Various conservation risk categories for the species included in the Italian Red Lists are reported in Fig. 8.

Characteristics of the flora in various environments

When the confirmed native flora has been divided into a percentage basis according to the habitat preferences of species (Fig. 9), we found that, even in this forest context, most of the taxa belong to herbaceous communities, primarily those of dry grasslands and sinanthropic-ruderal environments. Even when the habitats are grouped according to the main types, we can see that species preferring habitats of herbaceous communities are about 66% of the total number, while species preferring forest habitats are about 27%, and species preferring shrubland habitats are about 6%.

Fig. 7. The number of species of conservation interest at European/Italian level and at regional/local level detected in the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy.

Fig. 8. Various conservation risk categories for the species included in the Italian Red Lists of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park, Italy.

Fig. 9. The flora of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park (Italy) subdivided with reference to habitat preferences. Designation of habitats: arb – non-acid shrublands; bru – acidophilic heathlands and shrublands; br – mesophilic woods; bu – humid woods, riparian tree coenoses; bx – relatively thermo-xerophilic woods; pa – high altitude semi-mesophilic grasslands; pd – grasslands in the steep rocky areas close to the crest; pu – humid and hay meadows, tall herb edge communities, riparian herbaceous coenoses; px – dry grasslands; ro – rocky environments, walls, stony ground soils, talus slopes; ru – ruderal and sinanthropic environments; st – ponds, water bodies.

If only the species of conservation importance are considered (in total, i.e. species both of national and local interest), it is interesting to note (Fig. 10) that herbaceous habitats, particularly dry grasslands, upper mountain and altitude mesophilic and humid grasslands, together with rocky environments, have the highest conservation value, containing about 58% of the important plants. The largest number of taxa of conservation interest (27%) belongs to mesophilic forests that confirms the importance of nemoral flora in the study area.

Fig. 10. The flora of conservation interest of the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park subdivided with reference to habitat preferences. Designation of habitats: arb – non-acid shrublands; bru – acidophilic heathlands and shrublands; br – mesophilic woods; bu – humid woods, riparian tree coenoses; bx – relatively thermo-xerophilic woods; pa – high altitude semi-mesophilic grasslands; pd – grasslands in the steep rocky areas close to the crest; pu – humid and hay meadows, tall herb edge communities, riparian herbaceous coenoses; px – dry grasslands; ro – rocky environments, walls, stony ground soils, talus slopes; ru – ruderal and sinanthropic environments; st – ponds, water bodies.

Excluded and doubtful species

Species to be excluded are 11, while doubtful (including not reported after 1960) species are 131 in total. The few species considered excluded (e.g. *Helictochloa praetutiana* (Parl. ex Arcang.) Bartolucci, F.Conti, Peruzzi & Banfi, *Cirsium palustre* (L.) Scop., *C. bertolonii* Spreng., *Oreoselinum nigrum* Delarbre) are the result of some investigations carried out on exsiccata in herbaria (mainly FI and VER), which did not allow us to confirm the identification. Regarding doubtful species, a lot of information refers to problems related to nomenclature, because some names, like *Festuca ovina* L. sensu lato or *Alchemilla vulgaris* L. sensu lato, were previously used to identify plants of the same group, which were later better defined and correctly named. A small part of the species has most probably been reported on the basis of identification errors, but their exsiccata were not found in the herbaria (e.g. *Luzula pedemontana* Boiss. & Reut., *Oloptum miliaceum* (L.) Röser & H.R.Hamasha, *Festuca robustifolia* Mgf.-Dbg., *Ribes petraeum*; see also Viciani, 2012; Viciani & Gonnelli, 2015). Some plants, which are likely to be present in the study area (e.g. *Mentha arvensis* L., *Erysimum pseudorheticum* Polatschek, *Carduus chrysacanthus* Ten.), have been considered doubtful because they have been reported in degree theses or in unpublished data, and specimens could not be verified. The species, which have not been found after 1960, are mostly the result of old reports,

often already quoted by Zangheri (1966) on the basis of specimens from the second half of XIX century or early XX century, or just quoted and not found again recently, and therefore cannot be confirmed. A part of the non-confirmed reports consists of crop commensal plants, which were once present on the upper mountain, where various farming activities took place. Today these activities have disappeared almost completely. However, some data of interest about the presence of taxa of conservation importance can also be taken from this list. For example, the only certain location in Tuscany, even though outdated, of *Arabis auriculata* Lam. was reported by Fiori (1924, 1925) based on his own specimens dated by 1923 and traced and checked at the Herbarium Centrale Italicum (FI).

Conclusions

Even though the floristic importance of this area was well-known, compiling and continuous updating the checklist, provided the Foreste Casentinesi, Monte Falterona, Campigna National Park with an essential database to manage the territory. We could quite precisely quantify the plant diversity present in the study area, which has turned out to be remarkable, and analyse its essential characteristics. Moreover, we highlighted the gaps in floristic knowledge, towards which future research should be directed, giving information about rare plants, species not reported after 1960, and taxa, which need to be studied systematically in more details. In addition, the checklist has also been used as a database in reintroduction projects (Abeli et al., 2017) and for more in-depth spatial analyses on rare and interesting species (Viciani et al., 2018). However, the new data resulting from the updating of the last 15 years demonstrate that the study of the plant species in this territory certainly cannot be considered as finalised. It is because the flora varies over time and the checklist, like any other information tool, must be implemented and continuously improved to keep the knowledge of the vascular flora of this important area updated.

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Supporting Information

Additional data for the paper of Viciani & Alberti (2024) may be found in the **Supporting Information**.

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ФЛОРА СОСУДИСТЫХ РАСТЕНИЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПАРКА «ФОРЕСТЕ-КАСЕНТИНЕЗИ, МОНТЕ-ФАЛЬТЕРОНА И КАМПИНЬЯ» (СЕВЕРНЫЕ АПЕННИНЫ, ИТАЛИЯ): ОБНОВЛЕННЫЙ СПИСОК ВИДОВ

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Инвентаризация видов растений имеет решающее значение для ботанических исследований и сохранения растений, поскольку она предоставляет фундаментальные данные об оценке и распространении биоразнообразия. Для большей эффективности флористические списки должны составляться и постоянно обновляться как на глобальном, так и на локальном уровнях. Поэтому целью данного исследования стало обновление и обсуждение списка сосудистых растений флоры национального парка «Форесте-Касентинези, Монте-Фальтерона и Кампинья», важной особо охраняемой природной территории (ООПТ), расположенной в Северных Апеннинах (Италия). В данной работе представлен актуальный список видов сосудистых растений, опубликованный в 2010 г. (по данным на 2008 г.), дополнив его как опубликованными, так и неопубликованными данными по состоянию на 31.12.2023 г. Также была проведена инвентаризация некоторых музейных экземпляров в Центральном итальянском гербарии Флоренции, а также в других гербариях. Исследование также было направлено на проверку того, оказалось ли обновленное видовое богатство аборигенной и чужеродной флоры территории исследования выше или ниже ожидаемого. Всего было зарегистрировано 1415 видов. Из них 1172 вида, относящихся к 100 семействам, считаются аборигенными, подтвержденными данными, полученными после 1960 года, в то время как другие можно отнести к чужеродным растениям на территории национального парка «Форесте-Касентинези, Монте-Фальтерона и Кампинья» (в основном культивируемым), сомнительным или, в некоторых случаях, исключенных из флоры. По сравнению с 2010 г. количество видов увеличилось на 58, из которых 45 таксонов являются аборигенными. Согласно формуле оценки соотношения видов и площади в отношении видов сосудистых растений, в национальном парке «Форесте-Касентинези, Монте-Фальтерона и Кампинья» видовой богатство аборигенной флоры оказалось несколько выше ожидаемого (1172 против 1159 видов). В то же время видовое богатство чужеродной флоры (натурализовавшиеся и инвазионные виды, поскольку случайно занесенные виды не были обнаружены) оказалось намного ниже ожидаемого (24 против 109 таксонов), что в очередной раз подтверждает высокую природоохранную ценность этой территории. Подтверждено, что фиторазнообразие национального парка «Форесте-Касентинези, Монте-Фальтерона и Кампинья» очень велико. Это обусловлено тем, что на этой территории находятся лесные экосистемы большой природоохранной ценности, считающиеся одними из наиболее сохранившихся на европейском уровне, а также тем, что географическое положение данной ООПТ делает ее связующим звеном между двумя сильно различимыми флористическими комплексами, один из которых происходит с севера (Альпы, Северные Апеннины), а другой – с юга (Итальянский полуостров, Центральные и Южные Апеннины). Характеристики хорологии обновленной флоры данной ООПТ показывают, что различные растения в Италии находятся здесь на своей южной или северной границе ареала. Однако итальянский эндемизм, характеризующий данную флору, в основном североапеннинский и полуостровной (3.1%), в то время как европейский хоротип является наиболее обширным (> 25.5%). Также проведено обсуждение спектра жизненных форм, наличия редких, имеющих природоохранную ценность, сомнительных и чужеродных видов. Представлены характеристики флоры всех достоверно подтвержденных видов и видов, представляющих интерес для сохранения в отношении различных типов местообитаний. Обновленный список видов предоставляет национальному парку «Форесте-Касентинези, Монте-Фальтерона и Кампинья» необходимую базу данных для управления этой территорией и довольно точно количественно определяет разнообразие растений, известных здесь. В данной работе также выявлены пробелы в знаниях о флоре, на устранение которых следует направить будущие исследования, предоставив информацию о редких растениях, видах, не зарегистрированных после 1960 г., и растений, которые необходимо более подробно изучить с таксономической точки зрения, поскольку флора меняется с течением времени, а таксономические списки, как и любой другой источник информации, необходимо использовать и постоянно улучшать.

Ключевые слова: инвентаризация флоры, особо охраняемая природная территория, распространение, сохранение, таксономия растений, хорология

МАРШРУТЫ МИГРАЦИИ И КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ОСТАНОВКИ *ANSER FABALIS FABALIS* (ANSERIFORMES): АНАЛИЗ ПРОБЛЕМ ОХРАНЫ

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Численность *Anser fabalis fabalis* на зимовках продолжает снижаться. Экология миграций *Anser fabalis fabalis*, зимующего в западной Европе, изучена недостаточно. Лишь в общих чертах известно о сроках пролета вида, не описаны места ключевых миграционных остановок, нет данных по продолжительности их использования и природоохранном статусе. Без этих знаний невозможно организовать полноценную охрану любой мигрирующей популяции. Мы проанализировали динамику и фенологию миграций, а также природоохранный статус мест миграционных остановок и предмиграционных стоянок *Anser fabalis fabalis* восточной субпопуляции, гнездящейся в лесной зоне Западной и Центральной Сибири и зимующей в северной Германии и Польше, по данным GPS/GSM передатчиков. Использовали данные по 45 завершённым весенним перелетам от 25 помеченных птиц и 36 завершённым осенним перелетам от 20 птиц за период 2019–2023 гг. Старт с зимовок в большинстве случаев происходит в конце февраля, в среднем 20 февраля \pm 10.9 дней. Прилет в гнездовые районы происходит в конце апреля, в среднем 01 мая \pm 9.4 дня. За период 2019–2023 гг. прослежена тенденция смещения старта (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$) и окончания (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.35$, $p < 0.05$) весенней миграции на более ранние даты. По индивидуальным маршрутам были выделены 1031 миграционная остановка суммарной продолжительностью 3529.7 дней. Из них на территории России располагались 616 (59.8%) остановок, продолжительность которых составила 1831 (51.9%) день. Ключевые остановки, где особи проводят продолжительное время, находятся в Балтийском регионе, Свияго-Вятском междуречье и центральном Приволжье. Старт осенней миграции происходит между 27 сентября и 25 октября, в среднем – 18 октября \pm 7.9 дня, а прилет – на места зимовки между 15 октября и 11 декабря, в среднем – на 8 ноября \pm 13.4 дня. За период 2019–2023 гг. прослеживается тенденция все более позднего прилета на места зимовки (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$), старт осенней миграции также стал происходить позже (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.44$, $p < 0.05$). Для пар особей с выводками характерна более продолжительная осенняя миграция (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.0$, $Z = 2.58$, $p < 0.001$), и они проводят достоверно больше времени на предмиграционной стоянке (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 71.5$, $Z = 2.29$, $p < 0.01$ и миграционных остановках (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.5$, $Z = 2.56$, $p < 0.01$). Скорость миграции у особей с выводками было заметно ниже, чем у птиц без выводков (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 69.0$, $Z = -2.5$, $p < 0.01$). Только 15.3% мест остановок охвачены существующей сетью особо охраняемых природных территорий (ООПТ), на которых птицы проводят всего 19.2% времени. Результаты исследования могут быть использованы для разработки аргументированной стратегии сохранения восточной субпопуляции *Anser fabalis fabalis* в период сезонных миграций, при реализации которой создание ООПТ или ограничение охоты на выявленных ключевых территориях должны быть приоритетом.

Ключевые слова: гусеобразные, дистанционное прослеживание, Западная Сибирь, западный лесной гуменик, Красная книга России, места миграционных остановок, миграция, охрана, предмиграционная стоянка

Введение

Масштаб и интенсивность угроз перелетным птицам, несмотря на все усилия по сохранению, увеличились за последние полвека в связи с быстрым экономическим развитием и ростом населения, изменением климата, утратой и фрагментацией местообитаний, пресом чрезмерного промысла, охоты и браконьерства (Møller et al., 2008; Klaassen et al., 2014; Kamp et al., 2015; Romano et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2023; Guo et al., 2024). Сохранение широко мигрирующих видов является сложной задачей, учитывая расстояния, на которые они перемещаются и разное охотничье и природоохранное законодательство в странах, которые они пересекают на своем пути. Снижение уровня дополнительной смерт-

ности, не связанной с естественными причинами, особенно в критический период миграции – важнейшая задача сохранения редких видов. Недооценка важности этой проблемы ограничивает эффективность текущих усилий по сохранению (Sheehy et al., 2011). Для многих видов гусеобразных, совершающих протяженные миграции, лимитирующим параметром является время, которое они проводят на миграционных остановках. На таких остановках птицы пополняют израсходованные на перелеты внутренние резервы, отдыхают и ожидают благоприятных погодных условий для продолжения миграции. Высокий уровень беспокойства, особенно весенняя охота, на таких стоянках приводит к уменьшению времени, затрачиваемого на кормежку

(Chudzińska et al., 2016), а впоследствии ведет к ухудшению репродуктивных показателей – снижению величины кладки и возрастанию доли разоренных кладок (Mainguu et al., 2002; Féret et al., 2003; Calvert et al., 2007). Так в Квебеке (Канада), снижение уровня беспокойства, в первую очередь прессы охоты, произошедшее в период режима самоизоляции COVID-19, оказало положительное влияние на физическое состояние, кормовое поведение и репродуктивные показатели у *Anser caerulescens atlanticus*, Kennard, 1927 (LeTourneux et al., 2021).

Численность *Anser fabalis fabalis*, Latham, 1787 на европейских зимовках продолжает снижаться, несмотря на принятые рядом стран меры охраны (Fox & Leafloor, 2018; Jensen et al., 2022; Panov et al., 2022). Предполагается, что площадь очагов гнездования существенно сократилась из-за антропогенного воздействия: весенней охоты, незаконной охоты на местах линьки, беспокойства птиц на местах гнездования, трансформации гнездовых биотопов в ходе широкомасштабного освоения нефтегазовых месторождений. *Anser fabalis fabalis* является объектом Международной конвенции по охране мигрирующих видов (Приложение II). В 2012 г. природоохранный статус этого подвида поменялся – перемещен в Колонку А Таблицы 1 Приложения III к Соглашению по охране афро-евразийских мигрирующих водно-болотных птиц и их местообитаний (AEWA) как вид, численность популяций которого составляет менее 100 000 особей и из-за «выявленного долговременного и существенного снижения численности (Marjakangas et al., 2015).

В России гнездятся *Anser fabalis fabalis* трех субпопуляций: восточной, центральной и азиатской (Marjakangas et al., 2015; Розенфельд, Замятин, 2021). На федеральном уровне подвид подлежит охране в республиках Алтай, Бурятия, Саха (Якутия), Тыве, Хакасии, Ханты-Мансийском автономном округе-Югре, Ямало-Ненецком автономном округе, Чукотском автономном округе, Архангельской, Иркутской, Кемеровской, Магаданской, Новосибирской областях, Забайкальском, Камчатском, Красноярском краях (Розенфельд, Замятин, 2021). На региональном уровне *Anser fabalis fabalis* охраняется в Рязанской области, Республике Карелия и Красноярском крае (Артемьев, 2020; Емельянов, Розенфельд, 2022).

В настоящей статье представлен анализ миграционной экологии восточной субпопуляции,

гнездящейся в Западной и Центральной Сибири и зимующей в Северо-Западной Европе. Быстрый прогресс в методах исследования миграций, в первую очередь широкое использование спутниковых и GPS/GSM передатчиков (Jetz et al., 2022), которые предоставляют прекрасную возможность не только детально изучать особенности этого важного этапа годового цикла, но и имеют большое природоохранное значение. Дистанционное прослеживание помогает выявить ключевые места остановок для их последующей охраны (Vangeluwe et al., 2018; Lei et al., 2019; Batbayar et al., 2021; Rozenfeld et al., 2021; Erdenechimeg et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2023).

Целью исследования было выяснение особенностей миграционных маршрутов *Anser fabalis fabalis* весной и осенью, закономерностей географического распределения миграционных стоянок, оценка эффективности особо охраняемых природных территорий (ООПТ). Благополучие большинства перелетных птиц зависит от качества мест миграционных остановок, которые существенно влияют на динамику численности популяций. Кроме того, знание сроков миграции и прибытия на места гнездования позволяет скорректировать сроки охоты таким образом, чтобы вывести из-под ее прессы редкие таксоны. После периода линьки *Anser fabalis fabalis* собираются на предмиграционные стоянки, которые, если размножение было удачным, располагаются вблизи гнездовых районов. Пары, потерявшие кладку или выводок, покидают гнездовые районы и улетают на линьку в Арктику: на полуострова Таймыр и Гыдан. После подъема на крыло такие особи возвращаются на предмиграционные стоянки, присоединяясь к размножавшейся части популяции. Предмиграционная стоянка – важный этап в годовом цикле жизни многих видов гусеобразных, в т.ч. *Anser fabalis fabalis*. При анализе, мы выделяем этот этап в отдельную категорию.

Материал и методы

Отлов и мечение проводили в ноябре 2018 г. и октябре – ноябре 2021 г. (Электронное приложение 1) на территории национального парка «Нижняя дельта Одера» (Германия) (52.984° N, 14.161° E). Особей *Anser fabalis fabalis* ловили традиционным методом с помощью живых подсадных птиц и сетевой ловушки. Всего в 2018 г. передатчиками GPS-GSM помечено 19 особей, в 2021 г. – 36 особей. Частота сигнала варьировала

от 10 мин. до 1 ч. в зависимости от текущего заряда батареи прибора (Электронное приложение 1). Данные депонированы на сайте Movebank (<https://www.movebank.org/>). Политика доступа к данным проекта разрешает их свободное использование в природоохранных целях.

Для анализа миграции *Anser fabalis fabalis* были использованы следующие параметры: продолжительность миграции, продолжительность перелета, расстояние миграции, длительность стоянок, количество миграционных остановок, скорость полета (соотношение суммарного расстояния, преодоленного в ходе миграции, ко времени затраченному на перелеты), скорость миграции (соотношение суммарного расстояния, преодоленного в ходе миграции, к суммарному времени, потраченному на данный маршрут) и индекс прямолинейности (соотношение протяженности реального маршрута миграции и ортодрома между точкой старта и окончанием миграции). Протяженность миграционного маршрута рассчитывали как сумму суточных перемещений между крайними точками перелета, без учета локальных кормовых перемещений на стоянках. Суточные перемещения рассчитаны как сумма расстояний между последовательными точками в течение одних суток с использованием функции `distHaversine` в пакете «`geosphere`» (Hijmans et al., 2017) программы R (R Core Team, 2021). Для расчета расстояния миграционных маршрутов использовали только полные маршруты. Выделенные остановки ранжировали по пяти категориям в зависимости от продолжительности: < 1 дня (1), 1.0–3.9 дня (2), 4.0–9.9 дня (3), 10.0–14.9 дней (4) и > 15 дней (5). В большинстве случаев для анализа использовали только длительные остановки (четыре дня и более). Наличие тенденций во временных рядах данных оценивали с помощью критерия Манн-Кендалла (Mann-Kendall test), пакет «`trend`» (Pohler, 2018). Для проверки сходства нескольких выборок использовали непараметрический критерий Краскала-Уоллиса (Kruskal-Wallis test). При сравнении сходства двух выборок применяли критерий Манна-Уитни (Mann-Whitney test). Для сравнения характеристик миграций весной и осенью из-за небольшой выборки применяли непараметрический Т-критерий Уилкоксона (Wilcoxon Pairs Test). ГИС-слой по расположению ООПТ на территории России был взят из Всемирной базы данных (UNEP-WCMC & IUCN, 2024), которая является наиболее полной глобальной базой данных по морским и наземным ООПТ.

Результаты

От 43 помеченных птиц в 2019–2023 гг. мы получили данные о 45 весенних и 36 осенних полных (завершенных) маршрутах. Восемнадцать передатчиков (41.9%) прекратили работу во время зимовки или в ходе миграции. Старт с зимовок в большинстве случаев происходит в конце февраля, но у отдельных особей может затягиваться до конца марта (табл. 1). Средняя многолетняя дата начала весенней миграции: 20 февраля \pm 10.9 дней ($n = 56$). Различий в датах начала и окончания миграции, продолжительности перелетов и остановок у самцов и самок не обнаружено. Прилет в гнездовые районы происходит в конце апреля, в среднем 01 мая \pm 9.4 дня ($n = 45$). Начало (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$) и окончание (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.35$, $p < 0.05$) весенней миграции за период 2019–2023 гг. имеют тенденцию смещения на более ранние даты.

Протяженность миграционного маршрута у разных особей варьировала от 3300 км до 6300 км (табл. 1, рис. 1), в среднем -4600 ± 700 км ($n = 45$). Продолжительность миграции не имеет межгодовых различий (Kruskal-Wallis test: $H_{4,45} = 7.04$, $p > 0.05$).

Пути миграции

Весенняя миграция у *Anser fabalis fabalis* длится в среднем не меньше двух месяцев. Покидая зимовку, птицы делают первую продолжительную остановку на балтийском побережье Польши, Литвы, Латвии и Калининградской области России (рис. 1). В отдельных случаях они задерживаются в регионе до 25–28 дней, но обычно остаются здесь 10–14 дней. В зависимости от темпов весеннего потепления, большая часть птиц к концу первой декады марта перемещается восточнее и юго-восточнее: в Беларусь, восточные районы Латвии и Литвы, а во второй декаде марта появляются в Псковской, Брянской, Смоленской и Орловской областях. Начиная с середины марта, *Anser fabalis fabalis* постепенно продвигаются восточнее, до Курской, Липецкой и Воронежской областей (рис. 1). В дальнейшем, направление перемещений особей расширяется, и к концу марта птицы появляются в Нечерноземье и Поволжье. В апреле начинает преобладать северо-восточное направление миграции, птицы достигают Коми, Пермского края, Ханты-Мансийского автономного округа-Югры, Ямало-Ненецкого и Ненецкого автономных округов.

Таблица 1. Характеристика сезонных миграций *Anser fabalis fabalis* в 2019–2023 гг. по еропейско-западносибирскому пролетному пути

Table 1. Characteristics of spring and autumn migration of *Anser fabalis fabalis* in 2019–2023 along Europe-Western Siberian flyway

Переменные	Характеристики				p-уровень значимости различий*
	весенняя миграция, n = 45		осенняя миграция, n = 36		
	M ± SD	min–max	M ± SD	min–max	
Дата начала миграции	20.02 ± 11	29.01–21.03	18.10 ± 7	27.09–25.10	–
Дата окончания миграции	10.05 ± 9	16.04–26.05	8.11 ± 13	15.10–11.12	–
Расстояние миграции, км	4621.1 ± 739.2	3364.5–6325.9	3464.7 ± 329.5	2875.1–4445.7	< 0.0001
Дистанция ортодрома, км	2940.1 ± 236.1	2513.1–3506.8	2922.2 ± 137.4	2656.5–3199.9	p > 0.05
Индекс прямолинейности	1.57 ± 0.22	1.29–2.21	1.18 ± 0.09	1.08–1.44	< 0.0001
Продолжительность миграции, дни	70.3 ± 2.9	36.2–99.9	20.7 ± 11.7	3.5–49.3	< 0.0001
Продолжительность перелетов, минуты	4803 ± 750.8	3180–6984	3923 ± 773.5	2742–6061	< 0.0001
Число миграционных остановок	19.9 ± 6.1	10.0–38.0	7.8 ± 3.03	3–18	< 0.0001
Длительность остановок, дни	66.6 ± 12.9	33.3–96.3	17.7 ± 11.5	0.9–46.1	< 0.0001
Скорость миграции, км/день	67.6 ± 14.5	43.6–112.9	255.9 ± 210.61	69.0–1054.8	< 0.0001
Скорость полета, км/час	58.1 ± 7.2	37.4–71.3	54.1 ± 7.35	34.6–69.4	< 0.01

Примечание: * – различия оценены по Wilcoxon pairs test («–» – сравнение выборок не проводили; ns – p > 0.05); M – среднее значение, SD – стандартное отклонение, min – минимальное значение, max – максимальное значение.

Рис. 1. Маршруты весенней (а), осенней (б) миграции и распределение миграционных остановок *Anser fabalis fabalis*. Красными прямоугольниками выделены ключевые районы, где сконцентрированы наиболее важные миграционные остановки: 1 – Балтийский регион; 2 – Центрально-Черноземный регион; 3 – Свияго-Вятское междуречье.

Fig. 1. Spring (a) and autumn (b) migration routes and arrangement of stopovers of *Anser fabalis fabalis*. Red rectangles indicate key areas with the most important stopovers: 1 – Baltic Region; 2 – Central Black Earth Region; 3 – Sviyaga-Vyatka interfluvium.

Особям *Anser fabalis fabalis*, гнездящимся в Западной Сибири, на пути к местам гнездования необходимо пересечь Уральские горы, для чего они используют три основных маршрута (рис. 1). Большая часть птиц пролетает широким фронтом через Северный и Средний Урал – наиболее низкие участки горного массива между 63° N и 58° N, а затем поворачивает к северу и северо-западу. Около 10% особей, покинув миграционные остановки в Поволжье, летят вдоль Уральского хребта до Приполярного Урала, переваливая через горы по Печорской и Воркутинской впадинам. Также около 10% особей преодолевают Уральские горы самым южным маршрутом между 57° N и 55° N, в частности по Уфимско-Соликамской впадине.

По индивидуальным маршрутам была выделена 1031 миграционная остановка суммарной продолжительностью 3529.7 дней. Из них на территории России располагались 616 (59.8%) оста-

новок, продолжительность которых составила 1831 (51.9%) день. Распределение миграционных остановок имеет выраженный географический тренд – по мере продвижения на восток, ближе к гнездовым районам, их продолжительность сокращается (r = -0.099, p < 0.0001, n = 1031). Анализ географического распределения миграционных остановок позволяет обозначить наиболее важные для вида регионы (рис. 1) в весенний период – Балтийский регион, Свияго-Вятское междуречье и центральное Поволжье.

Общая характеристика осенней миграции

Отлет птиц с предмиграционных стоянок происходит между 27 сентября и 25 октября (табл. 1), средняя многолетняя дата – 18 октября ± 7.9 дня (n = 36). Прилет на места зимовки происходит между 15 октября и 11 декабря, в среднем – 8 ноября ± 13.4 дня (n = 36). Протяженность осенней

миграции в среднем 3464.7 ± 329.5 км (min-max: 2875.1–4445.7 км, $n = 36$); продолжительность осенней миграции составила в среднем 21 ± 11.7 день с разбросом от 4 до 49 дней (табл. 1). За период 2019–2023 гг. прослеживается тенденция все более позднего прилета на места зимовки (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$). Начало осенней миграции также стало происходить позже (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.44$, $p < 0.05$).

Отличия миграций птиц с выводками и без выводков

Было прослежено 35 маршрутов: 22 – для птиц, гнездившихся неуспешно (потерявших кладку или выводок) и 13 – для успешно вырастивших птенцов. Для пар с выводками характерна более продолжительная осенняя миграция (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.0$, $Z = 2.58$, $p < 0.001$), и они проводят достоверно больше времени на предмиграционной стоянке (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 71.5$, $Z = 2.29$, $p < 0.01$) и миграционных остановках на пути пролета (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.5$, $Z = 2.56$, $p < 0.01$). Скорость миграции у птиц с выводками заметно ниже, чем у птиц без выводков (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 69.0$, $Z = -2.5$, $p < 0.01$). Перечисленные закономерности обусловлены тем, что птенцы гораздо слабее взрослых птиц: им требуется больше времени на подготовку к миграции и на восстановление сил после перелета. Соответственно, пары с выводками прибывают на места зимовок достоверно позже птиц без выводков (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.0$, $Z = 2.58$, $p < 0.01$). При этом даты начала осенней миграции, расстояние миграции и количество остановок не отличается между выборками птиц с выводками и без них.

Предмиграционные стоянки

После окончания линьки птицы перемещаются на предмиграционные стоянки, на которых проводят до двух месяцев. Мы специально отделяем этот этап от осенней миграции и гнездового сезона, так как он критически важен для многих видов гусеобразных, поскольку во многом определяет последующую выживаемость птенцов (Сыроечковский, 2013). Именно в этот период происходит накопление внутренних резервов, необходимых для успешного завершения осенней миграции взрослыми птицами, а также рост птенцов и развитие у них мышц, отвечающих за полет. Средняя продолжительность предмиграционной стоянки у *Anser fabalis fabalis* длится 58.5 ± 9.7 дней ($n = 35$). Продолжительность пребывания

особей на стоянке не зависит ни от пола (Mann-Whitney test, $p > 0.1$, $n = 35$), ни от года (Kruskal-Wallis test: $H_{4,35} = 8.1$, $p = 0.13$), но на нее сильно влияет наличие выводка; так, пары с птенцами достоверно проводят больше времени на предмиграционной стоянке (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.0$, $Z = 2.58$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 35$). За период 2019–2023 гг. прослеживается четкая тенденция увеличения продолжительности предмиграционной стоянки (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.35$, $p < 0.01$) и смещения на более поздние даты ее окончания, т.е. начала осенней миграции (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.44$, $p < 0.05$). Даты начала образования предмиграционных стоянок остались прежними, выраженных межсезонных тенденций не обнаружено (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.05$, $p > 0.05$).

Миграции *Anser fabalis fabalis* весной принципиально отличаются от осенних перелетов по всем основным переменным (табл. 1). На осеннюю миграцию особи *Anser fabalis fabalis* затрачивают значительно меньше времени. Кроме того, сокращается расстояние миграции и количество миграционных остановок, а маршрут становится более прямолинейным. Это требует разных подходов к охране *Anser fabalis fabalis* весной и осенью.

Эффективность существующей сети ООПТ

Наложение распределения весенних миграционных остановок и предмиграционных стоянок на карты ООПТ в слоях ГИС показало, что существующая сеть ООПТ не обеспечивает охрану подвида во время миграций (рис. 2; Приложение 1). Показатели обеспеченности варьируют по регионам. В лучшем случае сеть ООПТ охватывает 20–30% весенних остановок (Республика Татарстан, Республика Коми, Пермский край, Калининградская область, Ярославская область) – в среднем по миграционному маршруту около 15%. В 23 из 40 регионов, в том числе ключевых для вида Псковской, Новгородской, Курской, Пензенской, Нижегородской областях, ни одна из остановок не находится на ООПТ (Приложение 1, рис. 2).

Другой важный показатель – время, проведенное на ООПТ. В среднем по маршруту он составляет 19.2%, но в большинстве регионов гораздо меньше (Приложение 1). Только в Татарстане *Anser fabalis fabalis* почти половину времени проводят на ООПТ. Критическая ситуация с охраной *Anser fabalis fabalis* на весенних миграционных остановках сложилась в Ханты-Мансийском автономном округе-Югре, Рязанской и Свердловской областях: в каждом из этих регионов особи *Anser*

fabalis fabalis проводят 5–7% времени в период весенней миграции. При этом лишь 0.4–0.7% (Приложение 1) территорий остановок находится на ООПТ. Не лучше обстоит дело и с охраной предмиграционных стоянок *Anser fabalis fabalis* в критический период взросления птенцов и подготовки к осеннему перелету (рис. 3), только 11.5% из них находятся на ООПТ.

Обсуждение

Точные данные отслеживания маршрутов пролета позволили выяснить закономерности миграции особей *Anser fabalis fabalis*, размножающихся в Западной Сибири и на севере Европейской России и выявить факторы угроз. Современные технологии в сочетании с инструментами дистанционного зондирования Земли обеспечивают уровень детализации, необходимый для выявления и характеристики закономерностей в использовании пространства птицами, а также поиске критически важных мест обитания.

Рис. 2. Распределение весенних миграционных остановок *Anser fabalis fabalis* в 2019–2023 гг. и сеть ООПТ. Обозначения: а – Центрально-Черноземный регион, б – Свияго-Вятское междуречье.

Fig. 2. Protected Areas and distribution of spring stopovers of *Anser fabalis fabalis* in Central Black Earth Region (a) and Sviyaga-Vyatka interfluvium (b) in 2019–2023.

Рис. 3. Распределение предмиграционных стоянок *Anser fabalis fabalis* и сети ООПТ в 2019–2023 гг. в Республике Коми, Ямало-Ненецком автономном округе и Ханты-Мансийском автономном округе-Югре.

Fig. 3. The location of Protected Areas and pre-migration stopovers of *Anser fabalis fabalis* in 2019–2023 in the Komi Republic, Yamalo-Nenetsky Autonomous Okrug and Khanty-Mansi Autonomous Okrug.

Эффективность сети ООПТ и меры охраны

В настоящее время лишь 15.3% мест остановок, на которых *Anser fabalis fabalis* проводят всего 19.2% времени, входят в состав ООПТ. Сроки весенней и осенней охоты планируются регионами без учета характера миграции *Anser fabalis fabalis*, который летит весной на 10–15 дней раньше массовых охотничьих видов гусеобразных, гнездящихся в Арктике: *Anser fabalis rossicus* Buturlin, 1933 и *A. albifrons*, Scopoli, 1769. Учитывая мощное охотничье лобби, полностью запретить весеннюю охоту на гусей в России не удастся. Однако перенести сроки охоты на более поздние и ввести запрет или ограничения на выявленных местах ключевых миграционных остановок и предмиграционных стоянок необходимо (табл. 2).

Изменение фенологии

В период 2019–2023 гг. выражено проявляется тенденция смещения сроков начала весенней миграции на более ранние даты, такая же тенденция отмечена и для дат прибытия *Anser fabalis fabalis* на места гнездования. Подобные изменения фенологии весенней миграции отмечены у многих видов птиц в Северном полушарии как следствие потепления климата (Volkov et al., 2017; Cohen et al., 2018; Lehikoinen et al., 2019; Ryzhanovskiy & Gilev, 2020; Бурский, 2020). Весенняя миграция *Anser fabalis fabalis* длится в среднем около 70 дней. Но в холодные сезоны время, затрачиваемое на путь от зимовки до мест

гнездования, может составлять более трех месяцев. В годы с затяжной весной возрастает как расстояние миграции, так и число миграционных остановок. Пары, потерявшие кладки, мигрируют на линьку на юго-западный Таймыр или Гыданский полуостров. Можно было бы ожидать, что как у тундрового подвида *Anser fabalis rossicus* у *Anser fabalis fabalis* есть различия в фенологии осенней миграции у успешных и неуспешных пар. Так, особи *Anser fabalis rossicus*, оставшиеся без выводков, мигрируют на Новую Землю, где проводят три месяца и начинают осеннюю миграцию позже, чем успешно гнездившиеся птицы (Piironen et al., 2021). У *Anser fabalis fabalis* выявлена противоположная тенденция: миграция пар с выводками длится дольше, и они прилетают на зимовку достоверно позже.

Прослеживается тенденция все более позднего прилета на места зимовки. При этом начало осенней миграции также достоверно сдвигается на более поздние даты. Похожие тенденции отмечены для южной Финляндии, где за последние 40 лет сроки начала весенней миграции сдвинулись почти на месяц, а начало осенней миграции на две недели. Отмечается, что сдвиг в весенний период хорошо коррелирует с потеплением и индексом Североатлантического колебания (NAO), но осенью такая тенденция не прослеживается (Kortessalmi et al., 2023).

Сравнение осенней и весенней миграции

Весенние миграционные маршруты *Anser fabalis fabalis*, который не летит Беломоро-балтийским пролетным путем, как и сроки миграции, значительно отличаются от маршрутов других видов трибы Anserini, зимующих в Северной

Европе. Поскольку весенняя миграция у *Anser fabalis fabalis* начинается раньше (птицы сталкиваются с более жесткими погодными условиями), их маршрут проходит гораздо южнее, по территориям, раньше освобождающимся от снега. Осенняя миграция относительно короткая. Стартуя с предмиграционной стоянки, особи преодолевают расстояние до зимовки в среднем за три недели, но в отдельных случаях миграция может длиться всего 3.5 дня. На осенней миграции сокращается число миграционных остановок, а кроме того, маршрут миграции более прямолинейен, чем весной. Эти наблюдения дают основание к изменению подхода к охране *Anser fabalis fabalis*: на длительных миграционных остановках необходим полный запрет охоты весной.

Заключение

С середины 1990-х гг. восточная субпопуляция *Anser fabalis fabalis*, зимующего в Европе (Польша, Германия) неуклонно сокращала свою численность. Однако данные по маршрутам миграции, местах миграционных остановок, предмиграционным стоянкам, необходимые для разработки эффективной программы сохранения *Anser fabalis fabalis*, отсутствовали. По данным изучения птиц, помеченных GPS/GSM передатчиками в 2019–2023 гг, мы выяснили, что на территории России только 15.3% известных остановок, на которых *Anser fabalis fabalis* проводит всего 19.2% времени весенней миграции, охвачены существующей сетью ООПТ. Для эффективной охраны *Anser fabalis fabalis* в выявленных ключевых местах мы предлагаем запретить охоту (создать сезонные зоны покоя дичи) и/или создать ООПТ с режимом запрета охоты на водоплавающую дичь.

Таблица 2. Предложения по ограничению (запрету) весенней охоты на водоплавающую дичь по результатам анализа маршрутов миграции и времени пребывания *Anser fabalis fabalis* в регионах

Table 2. Region-wise proposals for spring hunting ban (restriction) based on the results of an analysis of migration routes and time of stay of *Anser fabalis fabalis*

Сроки ограничения (запрета) охоты	Регионы
10 февраля – 10 марта	Калининградская область
10 марта – 10 апреля	Брянская область, Смоленская область
20 марта – 10 апреля	Белгородская область, Воронежская область, Калужская область, Курская область, Липецкая область, Республика Мордовия, Новгородская область, Орловская область, Пензенская область, Псковская область, Саратовская область, Тамбовская область, Тульская область, Владимирская область, Ивановская область, Республика Марий Эл, Московская область, Нижегородская область, Рязанская область, Республика Татарстан, Тверская область, Ульяновская область, Чувашская Республика
01 апреля – 10 мая	Республика Башкортостан, Кировская область, Свердловская область, Тюменская область, Челябинская область
10 апреля – 10 мая	Архангельская область, Вологодская область, Костромская область, Пермский край, Республика Удмуртия, Ханты-Мансийский автономный округ, Ярославская область
20 апреля – 10 мая	Республика Коми, Ямало-Ненецкий автономный округ

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Приложение 1. Распределение по регионам, число, длительность и характер использования весенних миграционных остановок *Anser fabalis fabalis* по регионам.

Appendix 1. Region-wide distribution, number, duration and pattern of use of spring stopovers by *Anser fabalis fabalis*.

Регион	Статус	Остановки			Время, проведенное в регионе				Количество остановок по продолжительности, в днях					Присутствие в регионе		
		количество	%	на ООПТ	дней	%	на ООПТ	%	< 1.0	1.0–3.9	4.0–9.9	10.0–14.9	> 15	с	по	дней
Прибалтийский регион																
Калининградская область	НОВ	10	1.6	2	12.0	0.7	0.8	6.7	8	1	1	0	0	11.02	10.03	28
Западные области Европейской России																
Смоленская область	НОВ	8	1.3	1	6.8	0.4	0.0	0.0	7	0	1	0	0	06.03	10.04	35
Брянская область	НОВ	18	2.9	3	72.6	4.0	1.1	1.5	9	0	5	4	0	10.03	03.04	24
Регионы центра Европейской России																
Орловская область	НОВ	41	6.7	5	118.9	6.5	19.7	16.6	25	7	4	4	1	17.03	14.04	28
Рязанская область	РКК	25	4.1	2	98.4	5.4	0.4	0.4	14	3	5	1	2	22.3	04.05	43
Тамбовская область	НОВ	26	4.2	3	49.6	2.7	2.0	4.0	17	6	1	2	0	20.3	07.04	18
Ивановская область	НОВ	6	1.0	0	44.4	2.4	0.0	0.0	3	1	0	2	0	21.03	23.04	33
Псковская область	НОВ	11	1.8	0	36.1	2.0	0.0	0.0	4	4	3	0	0	20.03	09.04	20
Новгородская область	НОВ	10	1.6	0	33.4	1.8	0.0	0.0	4	2	3	0	1	25.03	15.04	21
Курская область	НОВ	11	1.8	0	33.2	1.8	0.0	0.0	7	1	2	1	0	19.03	04.04	16
Липецкая область	НОВ	17	2.8	2	32.9	1.8	0.3	0.9	13	0	3	1	0	21.03	07.04	17
Республика Мордовия	НОВ	21	3.4	1	23.9	1.3	3.1	13.0	15	4	2	0	0	22.03	13.04	22
Московская область	НОВ	5	0.8	1	17.6	1.0	0.6	3.4	3	0	1	1	0	24.03	05.05	42
Тульская область	НОВ	6	1.0	0	14.9	0.8	0.0	0.0	4	1	0	1	0	21.03	07.04	17

Регион	Статус	Остановки			Время, проведенное в регионе				Количество остановок по продолжительности, в днях					Присутствие в регионе		
		количество	%	на ООПТ	дней	%	на ООПТ	%	< 1.0	1.0–3.9	4.0–9.9	10.0–14.9	> 15	с	по	дней
Пензенская область	НОВ	15	2.4	0	12.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	12	2	1	0	0	22.03	08.04	17
Белгородская область	НОВ	1	0.2	0	10.7	0.6	0.0	0.0	0	0	1	0	0	21.03	04.04	14
Владимирская область	НОВ	5	0.8	0	8.3	0.5	0.0	0.0	2	2	1	0	0	23.03	20.04	28
Тверская область	НОВ	2	0.3	0	5.5	0.3	0.0	0.0	1	0	1	0	0	21.03	06.05	46
Воронежская область	НОВ	2	0.3	0	5.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	1	0	1	0	0	20.03	07.04	18
Приволжье																
Республика Татарстан	НОВ	90	14.6	29	462.1	25.2	218.3	47.2	36	9	26	12	7	23.03	13.05	51
Кировская область	НОВ	49	8.0	3	174.1	9.5	12.7	7.3	24	10	10	2	3	28.03	14.05	47
Нижегородская область	НОВ	10	1.6	0	60.9	3.3	0.0	0.0	3	4	1	0	2	26.03	21.04	26
Республика Марий Эл	НОВ	5	0.8	0	2.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	5	0	0	0	0	23.03	13.05	51
Ульяновская область	НОВ	5	0.8	0	1.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	5	0	0	0	0	26.04	03.05	38
Саратовская область	НОВ	1	0.2	0	6.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0	0	1	0	0	22.03	08.04	17
Чувашская Республика	НОВ	6	1.0	0	1.7	0.1	0.0	0.0	6	0	0	0	0	23.04	11.05	49
Калужская область	НОВ	5	0.8	0	1.3	0.1	0.0	0.0	5	0	0	0	0	24.03	10.04	17
Зауралье																
Свердловская область	НОВ	17	2.8	2	84.2	4.6	0.6	0.7	8	3	3	1	2	30.03	27.04	28
Башкортостан	НОВ	4	0.6	0	7.5	0.4	0.0	0.0	3	0	1	0	0	27.03	21.04	25
Челябинская область	НОВ	1	0.2	0	3.8	0.2	0.0	0.0	0	1	0	0	0	30.03	27.04	28
Тюменская область	НОВ	1	0.2	1	0.2	0.0	0.2	100.0	1	0	0	0	0	30.03	27.04	28
Предуралье, северные регионы Европейской России и Западной Сибири																
Ханты-Мансийский автономный округ	ФКК	45	7.3	3	136.4	7.4	1.0	0.7	28	6	6	3	2	14.04	11.05	27
Республика Коми	НОВ	64	10.4	16	92.1	5.0	11.3	12.3	49	6	8	0	1	22.04	26.05	34
Пермский край	НОВ	26	4.2	14	88.1	4.8	64.7	73.4	13	7	3	1	2	06.04	05.05	29
Вологодская область	НОВ	10	1.6	2	35.8	2.0	13.2	36.9	6	0	3	1	0	12.04	07.05	25
Ярославская область	НОВ	10	1.6	3	8.1	0.4	1.4	17.3	7	3	0	0	0	08.04	06.05	28
Костромская область	НОВ	5	0.8	1	10.6	0.6	0.1	0.9	4	0	0	1	0	07.04	17.05	40
Республика Удмуртия	НОВ	10	1.6	0	10.2	0.6	0.0	0.0	8	2	0	0	0	09.04	14.05	35
Архангельская область	ФКК	4	0.6	0	4.5	0.2	0.0	0.0	2	2	0	0	0	12.04	07.05	25
Ямало-Ненецкий автономный округ	ФКК	8	1.3	0	3.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	7	0	1	0	0	20.04	11.05	21

Примечание: НОВ – не охраняемый вид; РКК – региональная красная книга; ФКК – Красная книга Российской Федерации.

MIGRATION ROUTES AND KEY STOPOVERS OF *ANSER FABALIS FABALIS* (ANSERIFORMES): CRITICAL PROTECTION GAPS

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The population of *Anser fabalis fabalis* wintering in Europe have shown decline in recent decades. At the same time, the population dynamic of most migratory birds largely depends on the quality of migratory stopover sites, which are necessary to replenish internal reserves. The migration ecology of *Anser fabalis fabalis* wintering in Europe has not been sufficiently studied. Only in general terms we know about the timing of migration, while the places of key stopovers in Russia are not described. There is no information about conservation status of key sites and the intensity and duration of their use by *Anser fabalis fabalis* individuals. Without this knowledge, it is impossible to organise effective protection of any migrating population. We have analysed the dynamics and phenology of migrations, as well as the conservation status of stopover and pre-migration sites of *Anser fabalis fabalis* nesting in the forest zone of Western and Central Siberia and wintering in Northern Germany and Poland, based on data from GPS/GSM transmitters. We used data from 45 completed spring migrations from 25 tagged birds and 36 completed autumn migrations from 20 birds over the period 2019–2023. The migration start from wintering sites occurs in late February, on average 20 February \pm 10.9 days. Arrival of the birds in the breeding areas occurs in late April, on average 01 May \pm 9.4 days. Over 2019–2023, we found a trend for a shift in the dates of spring migration start (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.22$, $p < 0.05$) and finish (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = -0.35$, $p < 0.05$) to earlier dates. Based on data from individual bird's migration routes, 1031 migration stopovers with a total duration of 3529.7 days were allocated. Of these, 616 (59.8%) stopovers were located in Russia, where the birds spent 1831 (51.9%) days. Key stopovers are located in the Baltic Region, the Sviyaga-Vyatka interfluvium and the centre of the River Volga Region. The start of the autumn migration occurs between 27 September and 25 October, on average 18 October \pm 7.9 days. The arrival at wintering sites occurs between 15 October and 11 December, on average 8 November \pm 13.4 days. Over 2019–2023, there was a trend of an increasingly later arrival on wintering sites (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.45$, $p < 0.05$). The start of the autumn migration occurred also later (Mann-Kendall test: $\tau = 0.44$, $p < 0.05$). Pairs with broods are characterised by a longer autumn migration (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.0$, $Z = 2.58$, $p < 0.001$), and they spend significantly more time on the pre-migration sites (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 71.5$, $Z = 2.29$, $p < 0.01$) and autumn stopovers (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 67.5$, $Z = 2.56$, $p < 0.01$). The migration speed of pairs without broods was higher than of pairs with broods (Mann-Whitney test: $U = 69.0$, $Z = -2.5$, $p < 0.01$). Only 15.3% of stopovers are covered by the existing network of Protected Areas, where the *Anser fabalis fabalis* individuals spend only 19.2% of the total time. The results of this study can be used to develop an effective strategy for the *Anser fabalis fabalis* conservation during the period of migrations. We propose a hunting ban and/or the creation of Protected Areas within the main key stopover sites in Russia.

Key words: Anseriformes, migration, pre-migration site, protection, Red Data Book of the Russian Federation, remote sensing, stopover sites, Western Siberia, Western taiga bean goose

HEMATOLOGICAL ANALYSIS AS A METHOD OF MONITORING PHYSIOLOGICAL STATUS OF MEDIUM CARNIVOROUS MAMMALS IN THE RUSSIAN FAR EAST

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Clinical blood analysis is considered not only a method of assessing the health status of individuals, but also their fitness and welfare, although the interpretation of the obtained data is complicated by the combined influence of various factors. For most wild carnivore species, there is insufficient information about the effect of environmental factors on hematological parameters. Mammals in the Far East are exposed to hard seasonal climate changes, and therefore have physiological adaptations that enable them to survive the cold season. The aim of this study was to estimate the hematological parameters of three widespread species of medium carnivorous mammals in this region, namely *Meles leucurus amurensis*, *Prionailurus bengalensis euptilura*, and *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis*, taking into account such factors as sex, age and season in the Ussuriysky State Nature Reserve (Russia), as well as to identify the most informative blood indicators of the animal physiological status. In spring and autumn of 2014–2023, blood samples were collected from 103 individuals of the studied carnivores. The animals were captured, immobilised, blood-sampled and released in the wild at the capture site. The number of leucocytes was counted in the field, and their ratio was detected on the blood smears in the lab. The absence of sex differences and the presence of age differences in the studied species were revealed, which corresponds to the already known data on the parameters of mammalian blood. In spring, *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* had higher leucocyte count (14.77 ± 1.76 mln/ml and 12.33 ± 1.08 mln/ml (hereinafter, in spring vs. autumn, respectively)), the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes (4.87 ± 0.47 and 3.02 ± 0.28), and the percentage of segmented neutrophils ($73.12 \pm 1.77\%$ and $62.95 \pm 2.29\%$), and the lower percentage of lymphocytes ($20.35 \pm 1.45\%$ and $25.64 \pm 1.49\%$) compared to autumn. Similar blood patterns were observed in two other species. This may be the result of a decrease in body mass and poor condition of animals, i.e. physiological stress after a long winter period and a lack of food resources. In addition, *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* had higher percentages of eosinophils, basophils, and band neutrophils ($7.85 \pm 1.61\%$, $3.69 \pm 1.26\%$, $2.15 \pm 0.34\%$, respectively) than *Meles leucurus amurensis* ($2.55 \pm 1.09\%$, $0.45 \pm 0.17\%$, $0.55 \pm 0.18\%$, respectively) and *Prionailurus bengalensis euptilura* ($1.48 \pm 0.59\%$, $0.30 \pm 0.16\%$, $1.74 \pm 0.47\%$, respectively). These differences are probably determined by the biological characteristics of *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis*, since this species is an ideal host and carrier of various diseases, and it also has specific morphological features of blood cells. Thus, our results demonstrate the importance of systematic blood tests and the necessity of considering both species-specific characteristics and environmental factors for assessing animal health.

Key words: Amur leopard cat, Asian badger, immune system, leucogram, raccoon dog, red blood cells, white blood cells

Introduction

The wildlife health monitoring has recently gained great importance due to the growing number of emerging problems that affect not only animals but also humans (Rahman et al., 2020; White & Razgour, 2020; Ellwanger & Chies, 2021). Almost all organisms are exposed to a wide range of potential pathogens in the environment, and therefore have developed complex physiological responses, including innate and adaptive immunity to counteract pathogens (Demas & Nelson, 2012). Variability in immune parameters can determine the population dynamics of diseases, which is becoming increasingly essential in the context of changes in environmental conditions, especially due to anthropogenic factors (Herrera & Nunn, 2019; Becker et al., 2020).

One of the priorities in ecological and zoological research is the assessment of the adaptive potential of individuals and populations, which has recently taken on increasing practical significance for the conservation of threatened animal species (Davis et al., 2008; Weiss & Wardrop, 2011; Davis & Maney, 2018). Traditionally, veterinarians are responsible for diagnosing animal health, but ecoimmunology suggests that conservation biology scientists can also raise wildlife health issues using some basic diagnostic procedures (Demas & Nelson, 2012; Maceda-Veiga et al., 2015). Particularly, clinical blood analysis is considered not only a method of assessing the health status of individuals, but also their fitness and welfare. Based on the quantitative and qualitative composition of blood cells, one can estimate the level of innate (neutro-

phils) and adaptive (lymphocytes) immunity (Weiss & Wardrop, 2011; van Lieshout et al., 2020), and the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes serves as one of the indicators of stress (Dhabhar et al., 1996; Davis et al., 2008; Davis & Maney, 2018; Pavlova et al., 2018). Additionally, examining blood smears can reveal the first signs of infection (e.g. an increase in the neutrophil count) or parasitosis (e.g. an increase in the eosinophil count) (Kirk et al., 2010b; Kido et al., 2011; Maceda-Veiga et al., 2015).

Nevertheless, the successful application of hematological analysis when working with wild animal species is challenging, especially in the wild, since the interpretation of the obtained data is complicated by the influence of many factors on individual blood parameters. Studies conducted on various systematic mammal groups have shown the relationship of blood cell composition with sex and age (Pastor et al., 2009; Manjerovic & Waterman, 2012; Stannard et al., 2016; van Lieshout et al., 2020; Soboleva et al., 2021), reproductive and social status (Macdonald et al., 1998; Kirk et al., 2010a), mating system (Nunn et al., 2000, 2003; Tian et al., 2015), presence of parasites, viral and bacterial infections (Kirk et al., 2010b; Pérez et al., 2015), method of collecting blood samples (Kusak et al., 2005; Davis et al., 2008; Pavlova et al., 2018), season (Gaspar-López et al., 2011; Pérez et al., 2015; Stannard et al., 2016; Xu & Hu, 2020), body size and mass (Downs et al., 2020; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020). However, for most wild species of carnivores, there is insufficient information about the effect of environmental factors on hematological parameters, making it difficult to objectively assess the fitness indicators of individuals and populations.

The Russian Far East, especially its southern part, including Primorsky Krai, is a region of unique biological diversity (Shvarts et al., 1995; Uphyrkina, 1996; Zhuravlev, 1997). Local animal species are exposed to hard seasonal climate changes that may lead to significant environmental consequences, in particular fires and floods (Korytny et al., 2007; Heim et al., 2019; Prikhodko et al., 2020). Changes in ecosystems result in habitat degradation and a sharp reduction in the number and distribution of forest-dependent species (Uphyrkina, 1996). Meanwhile, many animal species are endemic to this area and have physiological adaptations that enable them to survive the cold season (Zhuravlev, 1997).

Especially, members of three families are widespread among medium carnivorous mammals, namely *Meles leucurus amurensis* Schrenck, 1859 (hereinafter – Asian badger) (Mustelidae), *Prionailurus bengalensis euptilura* Elliot, 1871 (hereinafter

– Amur leopard cat) (Felidae) and *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* Matschie, 1907 (hereinafter – raccoon dog) (Canidae). These species also differ in their overwintering methods and reproductive strategies. Asian badgers hibernate in winter and use various breeding strategies depending on population density (Rozhnov et al., 2014; Zhou et al., 2017). Raccoon dogs are monogamous and hibernate in winter, but they often wake up and move, if necessary (Mulder, 2012; Mustonen & Nieminen, 2018). Amur leopard cats, like most Felidae species, demonstrate a promiscuous mating system and do not hibernate in winter, although their activity and movement patterns change (Erofeeva & Naidenko, 2020; Kovalzon et al., 2022; Erofeeva et al., 2023; Tkachenko, 2023). However, studies of the immune system for carnivores in this area are limited due to the presence and spread of various diseases (Goncharuk et al., 2012; Naidenko et al., 2018, 2019a,b; Gilbert et al., 2020; Seryodkin et al., 2020, 2023), which prevents a comprehensive understanding their health status.

Thus, the aim of this study was to estimate the hematological parameters of three species of carnivorous mammals in the Russian Far East, considering such factors as sex, age and season, as well as to identify the most informative blood indicators of the animal physiological status. We assumed that immune activity may be reduced in spring following a period of low activity during winter (the winter immunoenhancement hypothesis) (Martin et al., 2008; Xu & Hu, 2020), and immune activity in autumn may be higher due to frequent interactions with conspecifics and heterospecifics (Nunn, 2002; Nunn et al., 2003; Tian et al., 2015).

Material and Methods

The study was conducted in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve and the Land of the Leopard National Park (Primorsky Krai, Russia) (43.677778° N, 132.545555° E) in 2014–2023. The average altitude of this area is 300–400 m a.s.l. (rarely up to 600–700 m a.s.l.). The monsoon climate is characterised by low winter temperatures (with average January temperature of -17.9°C) and high summer temperatures (with average August temperature of +19.7°C). Annual precipitation varies from 500 mm to 1200 mm, averaging at 700–800 mm, with an average annual humidity ranging from 70% to 80%. The objects of this study were representatives of three families of carnivorous mammals: Asian badger (Mustelidae), Amur leopard cat (Felidae), and raccoon dog (Canidae). Animals were caught in spring (late March – early April) and autumn (late September – early October) using trapeze

wooden or all-metal live traps with lures of fish or meat products. The summer seems to be an ineffective period for the capturing due to the high variety of prey for the target species and, consequently, low capture rate. Winter is unacceptable due to low air temperatures and, consequently, the risk of animal death, as well as low activity of target species (especially, Asian badger and raccoon dog). Traps were checked daily in the morning during the periods of animal capturing.

We chemically immobilised the captured individuals with a mixture of tiletamine hydrochloride and zolazepam hydrochloride (Zoletil, Virback, France, by estimated dose 10 mg/kg of body mass). Blood samples for hematologic analysis were collected from the femoral vein into a tube with K3 EDTA (MiniCollect, Greiner Bio-One, Austria) (0.25 ml). We weighted the animals on an electronic scale with 5-g precision and determined their sex and age. After all procedures were completed, the animals were administered atipamezole hydrochloride (Antisedan, Orion Pharma, Finland), ensuring a fast and safe recovery of the animals. The animal handling protocol was approved by the Regulatory Commission of Experimental Research (Bioethics Commission) of A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the RAS, Russia (permission №67 of 16.03.2023). The study was conducted in accordance with the laws of the Russian Federation, the country where the research was performed. A total of 103 blood samples were collected, including 28 samples of Asian badgers (18 males, 10 females; 22 adults, 3 subadults), 26 samples of Amur leopard cats (18 males, 8 females; 16 adults, 10 subadults), and 49 samples of raccoon dogs (22 males, 26 females; 38 adults, 10 subadults). The sex and age of one raccoon dog, as well as the age of three Asian badgers, could not be determined. The animals were divided into subadults and adults according to the external condition of their teeth and the size of their canines (Mbizah et al., 2016; White & Belant, 2016).

We counted the total number of erythrocytes and leucocytes in a hemocytometer according to the standard microscopy method (Harvey, 2012) in the field to avoid time-dependent post-sampling changes. For the definition of leucocyte type counts, we also prepared blood smears, air-drying and fixing them with 100% methanol. The percentage ratio of various types of leucocytes was evaluated by identifying and classifying 100 leucocytes into specific morphologic types (lymphocytes, segmented and band neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils, and basophils) after Romanovsky staining with a Leica CTR5000D microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany/Switzerland) at a magnification of $\times 1000$ (Harvey, 2012) at the Joint Usage Cen-

tre «Live collection of wild species of mammals» at the A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the RAS (Russia). We determined leucocyte type counts as percentages to provide a differential profile for each individual and calculated absolute counts using the following formula: leucocyte number (counted by hemocytometer) \times percentage of leucocyte types / 100. The differential profile reveals the relative abundance of each cell type, while the absolute number expresses how many cells of each type are present per volume (ml) of blood.

Statistical analysis was performed with STATISTICA ver. 10 (StatSoft, Tulsa, OK, USA). All means are given as a mean \pm SE; significance level was set at $p < 0.05$. However, in some exceptional cases, p -values between 0.05 and 0.07 were also considered to be tendencies. Of the 15 hematological parameters, 11 ones were normally distributed based on Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($p > 0.05$). As ANOVA is relatively robust to small departures from normality (Dillon & Goldstein, 1984), this was not an obstacle to applying parametrical tests. We used a factorial design of ANOVA with Tukey HSD post-hoc test (T) for each hematological parameter. Due to the heterogeneity of the available sample, the following methods were used for analysis of 84 values of the erythrocyte count (red blood cells, RBC), 89 values of the leucocyte count (white blood cells, WBC), 68 values of the absolute counts of various types of leucocytes, and 82 values of the percentages of various types of leucocytes and the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes (Neu:Lym). Preliminary analysis revealed no sex differences in hematological parameters (44 females, 58 males; ANOVA, not significantly), which allowed us to combine the samples for further analysis. We considered the effects of predictor factors such as age (subadults/adults), season (spring/autumn), and species (badger/cat/dog).

Results

The results showed that the total erythrocyte count did not differ depending on the species ($F_{(2,77)} = 1.58$, $p = 0.21$) (Table 1), age ($F_{(1,77)} = 0.07$, $p = 0.79$) or season ($F_{(1,77)} = 0.21$, $p = 0.65$). The total leucocyte count was significantly related to the species ($F_{(2,82)} = 4.09$, $p = 0.020$), namely raccoon dogs had more cells than Asian badgers (T: $p = 0.037$), especially in spring (T: $p = 0.028$) (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, the effect of age was observed as a tendency ($F_{(1,82)} = 3.40$, $p = 0.069$) for all the studied species, namely, the presence of 1.44 times on average more leucocytes in adults compared with subadults (T: $p = 0.047$).

Table 1. Hematological parameters in three species of medium carnivorous mammals captured in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve, Russia

Parameters	Asian badger			Amur leopard cat			Raccoon dog		
	N	M ± SE	Min–Max	N	M ± SE	Min–Max	N	M ± SE	Min–Max
Erythrocytes, mlrd/ml	24	11.32 ± 1.22	4.00–30.08	22	10.63 ± 1.04	3.26–26.88	38	9.05 ± 0.75	2.00–21.60
Leucocytes, mln/ml	24	9.78 ± 1.64	1.60–36.95	24	12.12 ± 1.61	3.75–34.65	41	14.69 ± 1.24	4.90–48.55
Lymphocytes, mln/ml	16	2.23 ± 0.43	0.46–5.70	21	3.29 ± 0.61	0.67–12.44	31	2.98 ± 0.29	0.69–7.62
Monocytes, mln/ml	16	0.06 ± 0.04	0.00–0.59	21	0.07 ± 0.02	0.00–0.35	31	0.07 ± 0.03	0.00–0.53
Eosinophils, mln/ml	16	0.48 ± 0.26	0.00–3.89	21	0.33 ± 0.21	0.00–4.49	31	1.12 ± 0.26	0.00–5.72
Basophils, mln/ml	16	0.11 ± 0.07	0.00–1.11	21	0.03 ± 0.02	0.00–0.26	31	0.39 ± 0.16	0.00–3.60
Segmented neutrophils, mln/ml	16	8.41 ± 1.67	2.21–28.08	21	8.57 ± 1.17	2.44–25.29	31	10.47 ± 1.36	2.48–42.24
Band neutrophils, mln/ml	16	0.07 ± 0.02	0.00–0.29	21	0.24 ± 0.11	0.00–2.42	31	0.27 ± 0.05	0.00–0.96
Lymphocytes, %	20	23.15 ± 2.05	7.00–48.00	23	25.70 ± 2.35	11.00–48.00	39	21.05 ± 1.41	7.00–42.00
Monocytes, %	20	0.50 ± 0.27	0.00–5.00	23	0.52 ± 0.16	0.00–3.00	39	0.46 ± 0.18	0.00–5.00
Eosinophils, %	20	2.55 ± 1.09	0.00–22.00	23	1.48 ± 0.59	0.00–13.00	39	7.85 ± 1.61	0.00–37.00
Basophils, %	20	0.45 ± 0.17	0.00–3.00	23	0.30 ± 0.16	0.00–3.00	39	3.69 ± 1.26	0.00–41.00
Segmented neutrophils, %	20	72.80 ± 2.22	51.00–91.00	23	70.26 ± 2.57	43.00–88.00	39	64.79 ± 2.51	36.00–92.00
Band neutrophils, %	20	0.55 ± 0.18	0.00–3.00	23	1.74 ± 0.47	0.00–9.00	39	2.15 ± 0.34	0.00–9.00
Neu:Lym	20	3.93 ± 0.57	1.06–13.14	23	3.60 ± 0.43	1.06–8.00	39	4.25 ± 0.50	0.86–13.14

Note: N – number of blood samples, M – mean value, SE – standard error of mean, Min – minimum value, Max – maximum value, Neu:Lym – ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes.

Fig. 1. The total leucocyte count in three species of medium carnivorous mammals captured in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve (Russia) in spring and autumn. Histogram bars represent mean values; vertical lines («whiskers») indicate standard errors of the means.

As a rule, the number of various types of leucocytes did not differ depending on the species, age and season. Nevertheless, there were some tendencies in the eosinophil count depending on the species and season ($F_{(2, 62)} = 2.90, p = 0.062$), namely raccoon dogs had more cells than Amur leopard cats ($T: p = 0.068$), while the differences were significant in autumn ($T: p = 0.015$). In addition, the segmented neutrophil count tended to be more abundant in adults compared to subadults ($T: p = 0.054$).

However, some differences have been identified in percentages of various types of leucocytes. The percentage of lymphocytes varied depending on age ($F_{(1, 72)} = 8.38, p = 0.005$), where it was 1.43 times on average higher in subadults than in adults ($T: p = 0.0004$). The percentage of lymphocytes was also associated with the season ($F_{(1, 72)} = 4.09, p = 0.047$), since it was 1.31 times on average lower in spring than in autumn ($T: p = 0.003$). At the same time, the percentage of monocytes (a second type of agranulocytes) did not

depend on the species ($F_{(2, 72)} = 0.23, p = 0.79$), age ($F_{(1, 72)} = 0.19, p = 0.66$) or season ($F_{(1, 72)} = 2.27, p = 0.14$).

The percentage of eosinophils was influenced by species ($F_{(2, 72)} = 6.35, p = 0.003$) and season ($F_{(1, 72)} = 9.26, p = 0.003$), as well as their combined effect ($F_{(2, 76)} = 5.00, p = 0.009$) (Fig. 2). In raccoon dogs, the percentage of these granulocytes was higher in autumn than in spring ($T: p = 0.0008$) and in Asian badgers ($T: p = 0.0005$), and higher than in Amur leopard cats in both autumn ($T: p = 0.0002$) and spring ($T: p = 0.018$). The percentage of basophils did not depend on age and season, but differed as a tendency depending on the species ($F_{(2, 76)} = 3.06, p = 0.053$). The percentage of these granulocytes in raccoon dogs was slightly higher than in Amur leopard cats ($T: p = 0.059$) (Fig. 3).

The percentage of segmented neutrophils was influenced by the species as a tendency ($F_{(2, 72)} = 3.03, p = 0.055$) and season ($F_{(1, 72)} = 10.80, p = 0.002$), and also as a tendency by the combined effect of species and season ($F_{(2, 76)} = 2.92, p = 0.060$). The percentage of these granulocytes in raccoon dogs in autumn was 1.31 times on average less than in spring ($T: p = 0.0007$). These differences were also significant for Amur leopard cats ($T: p = 0.021$) and Asian badgers ($T: p = 0.001$). In addition, the percentage of band neutrophils also differed depending on the species ($F_{(2, 72)} = 4.52, p = 0.014$); e.g. raccoon dogs had a higher percentage than Asian badgers ($T: p = 0.023$).

The ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes significantly differed between seasons ($F_{(1, 72)} = 9.24, p = 0.003$) (Fig. 4). The values of this parameter were higher in spring compared with autumn ($T: p = 0.001$), especially in raccoon dogs ($T: p = 0.008$). In addition, although the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes did not depend on the age ($F_{(1, 72)} = 2.18, p = 0.14$), adults had more than subadults ($T: p = 0.022$).

Fig. 2. Eosinophil percentage in three species of medium carnivorous mammals captured in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve (Russia) in spring and autumn. Histogram bars represent mean values, vertical lines («whiskers») indicate standard errors of the means.

Fig. 3. Basophil percentage in three species of medium carnivorous mammals captured in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve (Russia) in spring and autumn. Histogram bars represent mean values. Vertical lines («whiskers») indicate standard errors of the means.

Fig. 4. Ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes in three species of medium carnivorous mammals captured in the Ussuriisky State Nature Reserve (Russia) in spring and autumn. Histogram bars represent mean values; vertical lines («whiskers») indicate standard errors of the means.

Discussion

Even though various parameters of immunity are actively studied in carnivorous mammals, information on hematological parameters remains insufficient. Moreover, often only the values of blood parameters are described, without considering the influence of any factors, which may be especially important when assessing the physiological status of animals in wild populations.

Particularly, data on the hematology of the three species of medium carnivores studied by us are extremely fragmentary. There are no complete data for the Asian badger, but the blood parameters of *Meles meles* Linnaeus, 1758 in the wild (Winnacker et al., 2008) and in a wildlife rehabilitation facility (Gelli et al., 2024) were previously described. Compared with these data, the counts of erythrocytes, leucocytes, neutrophils, lymphocytes, and eosinophils in Asian badgers in our study were higher, while the monocyte count and the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes, on the contrary, were lower. Such significant differences both with individuals in the wild and in captivity suggest the presence of not only interspecific differences, but also immune reactions associated with the habitat conditions of the Asian badger (Becker et al., 2020; van Lieshout et al., 2020). For the Amur leopard cat, only the counts of erythrocytes and leucocytes, as well as the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes in captive individuals are known (Pavlova et al., 2018). In addition, since the Amur leopard cat is a subspecies of *Prionailurus bengalensis* Kerr, 1792 (hereinafter – Bengal cat), it is also possible to consider the hematological parameters described for this species in zoos (Salakij et al., 2010; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020). According to these studies, the erythrocyte count in Amur leopard cats in our study corresponds to the already available data (Salakij et al., 2010; Pavlova et al., 2018; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020). The leucocyte count and their various types, primarily neutrophils and lymphocytes, on the contrary, vary significantly. For example, the leucocyte count in the Amur leopard cat, both in captivity and in the wild, is higher than in the Bengal cat (Salakij et al., 2010; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020), which may be related to the body size (Downs et al., 2020; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020), since Amur leopard cats are larger than Bengal cats (5.0 kg (3.4–7.4 kg, our data) and 3.2 kg (3.0–3.5 kg, Salakij et al., 2010), respectively)

or with the former adaptation to more severe living conditions (Becker et al., 2019). The ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes in Amur leopard cats in the wild is 1.4 times higher than in individuals in captivity (Pavlova et al., 2018), and more than 2.5 times higher than in Bengal cats in captivity (Salakij et al., 2010; Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020). This implies a significant shift towards neutrophils in individuals in the wild, which we consider below. As for raccoon dogs, hematological parameters have already been described in subadults on the farm and in adults in the zoo (Kido et al., 2011; Rui et al., 2011). However, in the individuals in our study captured in the wild, the counts of erythrocytes, leucocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils, and basophils, as well as the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes are significantly higher than in individuals in the zoo (Kido et al., 2011). An increased number of red blood cells may be associated either with exposure to frequent and prolonged stressors, or with the presence of blood parasites or ectoparasites (Johnstone et al., 2017). The possible causes of the increased leucocyte and granulocyte counts seem to reflect the living conditions of raccoon dogs in the wild and are listed below.

It should also be considered that the common procedure of collecting blood samples (handling time) in wild animals can be extremely stressful and involves immobilising animals with trapping and anesthesia for extended period, which can also affect blood parameters (Dhabhar et al., 1996; Kusak et al., 2005; Davis & Maney, 2018; Pavlova et al., 2018). If an increase in glucocorticoids level plays the role of a «messenger» for such stress reaction, then a change in the circulating leucocyte count and, accordingly, an increase in the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes is a «response» (or at least one of many physiological reactions) to this stress (Davis & Maney, 2018). This may explain the existing differences in hematological parameters in individuals in captivity and in the wild, however, using the same method of trapping animals and collecting blood samples in our study allows us to compare the obtained data considering sex, age, season and species.

Even though many studies describe differences in hematological parameters in males and females of various mammal species (Kusak et al., 2005; Pastor et al., 2009; Manjerovic & Waterman, 2012; Standard et al., 2016; van Lieshout et al., 2020), the effect of sex is not so clear. There are also many studies indicat-

ing the absence of sex differences (e.g. Chang et al., 2006; Barnes et al., 2008; Castellanos et al., 2010; Kirk et al., 2010a; Gelli et al., 2024), like in our case. The variability in the available data is likely related to the reproductive status of individuals. For example, Kirk et al. (2010a) have described differences between males and lactating females, but not non-lactating ones in *Ursus maritimus* Phipps, 1774. In addition, sex differences in blood parameters may be related to the biological characteristics of specific species (Hufschmid et al., 2014).

One of the indicators of animal health is the erythrocyte count and indices, in particular the concentration of hemoglobin and hematocrit (Johnstone et al., 2017). Erythrocytes can provide insight into aspects of physiology (e.g. aerobic function) that are quite difficult to investigate, especially in individuals in the wild. There is also some evidence that erythrocytes can perform direct functions in ensuring the immunocompetence of vertebrates, especially when they are formed throughout the life of an animal (Morera & MacKenzie, 2011). Particularly, some mammals, birds, reptiles and fish exhibit antimicrobial reactions based on erythrocytes, such as the formation of immune complexes and the production of reactive oxygen forms (Morera & MacKenzie, 2011). However, we found no differences in the number of red blood cells in carnivores depending on the species, age, or season in this study. Probably, this is likely due to the fact that mammals adapted or acclimatised to cold environments exhibit higher blood viscosity, defined as the ratio of blood plasma volume to blood cell volume, primarily erythrocytes, compared to species inhabiting a warmer climate (Deveci et al., 2001; Palenske & Saunders, 2002), and this viscosity is maintained at a relatively constant level. In this regard, the number of red blood cells does not change significantly during the year either, and in subadults it already seems to reach the level of adults. Definitely, this suggestion needs to be tested and the data on hematocrit values are obviously needed to confirm this assumption.

Nevertheless, the leucocyte count and the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes in subadults were lower than in adult carnivores. On the contrary, the percentage of lymphocytes was higher in subadult animals in our study. A similar blood pattern reflects the formation of the immune system in mammal ontogenesis, and it is typical not

only for carnivorous mammals (Winnacker et al., 2008; Pastor et al., 2009; Kirk et al., 2010a; Græsli et al., 2014; Soboleva et al., 2021), but also for other species (Weiss & Wardrop, 2011; Harvey, 2012; Stannard et al., 2016; Xu & Hu, 2020). Accordingly, at the earlier stage of ontogeny, the percentage of lymphocytes is higher than in older animals and it affects the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes.

Animals in the temperate zone confront seasonal environmental fluctuations and experience changes in resource availability, climatic conditions, and the threat of infection throughout the year (Nelson, 2004; Martin et al., 2008). Immune function is usually enhanced to compensate for the immunosuppressive effects of stressors that occur in winter, such as low ambient temperature and limited feed availability (Demas, 2004; Martin et al., 2008). According to our assumption, the highest differences in the hematological parameters of carnivores in this study were revealed precisely in relation to the season and species. Particularly, individuals had a higher leucocyte count and the proportion of segmented neutrophils, and there was also a lower percentage of lymphocytes in spring compared to autumn. Accordingly, the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes was also higher in spring than in autumn. These patterns in seasonal changes in blood parameters relate primarily to raccoon dogs. In addition, this species had a higher percentage of eosinophils, basophils and band neutrophils compared to Asian badgers and Amur leopard cats. Moreover, the percentage of basophils in raccoon dogs was significantly higher than in the other two species in both seasons of the year, while the percentage of eosinophils was significantly higher in autumn than in spring. The raccoon dog is an omnivorous mammal which often scavenging large carnivores' prey. It may increase the contact of the animals with various pathogens (contained in meat) and, accordingly, increase the counts of neutrophils and eosinophils, which has been described in large cats (Naidenko & Alshinetskiy, 2020). This reasonable explanation, taking into account seasonal differences and an increase in the count of leucocytes (e.g. eosinophils) in autumn, confirms the assumption that the temperature in autumn was higher than in early spring that change the kill features faster.

It is believed that a similar blood pattern in some species may be associated with reproduc-

tive efforts during the breeding season (Fancourt & Nicol, 2019) or seasonal morphological changes (Gaspar-López et al., 2011). However, for animals in the temperate climate zone, the winter immunoenhancement hypothesis is more expected, suggesting that activation of immunity in the cold season helps animals to resist pathogens and, consequently, increases their survival (Martin et al., 2008; Xu & Hu, 2020). Nevertheless, the results of our study did not confirm this assumption and rather indicate the activation of the immune system to the weakened status of the animal organism after winter. A long period of forced rest (i.e. hibernation or a similar condition) and a shortage of food supply can lead to a decrease in body mass and poor condition of animals (Johnstone et al., 2012; Naidenko et al., 2014; Pérez et al., 2015; Xu & Hu, 2020). Thus, the presence of physiological stress and an increase in physical (muscular) activity in spring is characterised by an increase in leucocytes and neutrophils (Weiss & Wardrop, 2011), which were identified in our study, primarily in raccoon dogs. In addition, with the onset of warm weather, the number of contacts between conspecifics and heterospecifics increases, which implies a more active transmission of pathogens between individuals (Korenberg, 2000; Nunn et al., 2003; Lindenfors et al., 2007). The reproduction of pathogens may also increase under higher temperature and altogether it is probably the reason for the increase in the percentage of eosinophils and lymphocytes in autumn, since these cell types are responsible for fighting against parasitic and viral infections, respectively (Weiss & Wardrop, 2011; Harvey, 2012).

Special attention should be paid to the fact that most of the seasonal differences in hematology described by us primarily relate to raccoon dogs. Individuals of this species have a smaller percentage of segmented neutrophils and a larger percentage of eosinophils, basophils, and band neutrophils compared with Asian badgers and Amur leopard cats. It is considered that the biological characteristics of the raccoon dog make this carnivore an ideal host and carrier of various diseases (Sutor et al., 2014; Myśliwy et al., 2022), which probably affects the blood parameters of this species and may indicate inflammatory processes, as well as viral and parasitic infections. On the other hand, it was previously described that eosinophils in raccoon dogs have several morphological features compared

to other mammal species (Kalinina et al., 2023). Probably, similar properties may also be characteristics of other types of leucocytes in this species, which causes the differences we found between the three species of carnivores and requires further study.

Conclusions

The use of clinical blood analysis to study wildlife is still not the most widespread method. However, it helps to expand the set of non-lethal procedures useful for monitoring the physiological status of wild animals. Systematic blood tests, particularly, can serve as early indicators of non-welfare of individuals in wild mammal populations due to stress or pathogens, significantly impacting reproduction and survival of animals. According to our study, the most informative hematological parameters are not only the leucocyte count, but also the percentage of lymphocytes, neutrophils, and eosinophils, and, consequently, the ratio of neutrophils to lymphocytes. Moreover, the most reliable results for individuals in the wild are provided precisely by the percentage of various types of leucocytes, which is estimated using blood smears. However, when analysing the data obtained, careful consideration of species, age, and seasonal differences in blood parameters is essential. Additionally, the role of diseases and infections in seasonal changes in hematological parameters requires further detailed study.

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ГЕМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ КАК МЕТОД МОНИТОРИНГА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ СРЕДНИХ ХИЩНЫХ МЛЕКОПИТАЮЩИХ ДАЛЬНЕГО ВОСТОКА РОССИИ

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Клинический анализ крови считается методом оценки не только состояния здоровья животных, но также их приспособленности и благополучия, хотя интерпретация полученных данных осложняется совместным влиянием разнообразных факторов. Для большинства диких видов хищных млекопитающих отсутствует информация о влиянии факторов окружающей среды на гематологические показатели. Млекопитающие Дальнего Востока подвержены резким сезонным изменениям климата, в связи с чем обладают физиологическими адаптациями, позволяющими им пережить холодное время года. Целью данного исследования было оценить гематологические показатели трех широко распространенных в этом регионе видов средних хищных млекопитающих, а именно *Meles leucurus amurensis*, *Prionailurus bengalensis euptilura* и *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* с учетом таких факторов, как пол, возраст и сезон, в Уссурийском государственном природном заповеднике (Россия), а также выявить наиболее информативные параметры крови, отражающие физиологическое состояние животных. Весной и осенью в 2014–2023 гг. были собраны образцы крови у 103 особей исследуемых видов хищных. Животные были отловлены, обездвижены и после получения проб крови выпущены в дикую природу на месте отлова. Количество лейкоцитов подсчитывали в полевых условиях и определяли их соотношение на мазках крови в лабораторных условиях. Было выявлено отсутствие половых различий и наличие возрастных различий у всех трех видов, что соответствует уже известным данным о параметрах крови млекопитающих. Весной у *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* было более высокое количество лейкоцитов (14.77 ± 1.76 млн/мл и 12.33 ± 1.08 млн/мл (здесь и далее – весной и осенью, соответственно)), соотношение нейтрофилов и лимфоцитов (4.87 ± 0.47 и 3.02 ± 0.28) и доля сегментоядерных нейтрофилов ($73.12 \pm 1.77\%$ и $62.95 \pm 2.29\%$), а также более низкая доля лимфоцитов ($20.35 \pm 1.45\%$ и $25.64 \pm 1.49\%$) по сравнению с осенью. Сходные изменения параметров крови наблюдались у двух других видов. Это может быть результатом снижения массы тела и худшего состояния животных, то есть физиологического стресса после длительного зимнего периода и нехватки пищевых ресурсов. Кроме того, у *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis* были более высокие доли эозинофилов, базофилов и палочкоядерных нейтрофилов ($7.85 \pm 1.61\%$, $3.69 \pm 1.26\%$, $2.15 \pm 0.34\%$, соответственно), чем у *Meles leucurus amurensis* ($2.55 \pm 1.09\%$, $0.45 \pm 0.17\%$, $0.55 \pm 0.18\%$, соответственно) и *Prionailurus bengalensis euptilura* ($1.48 \pm 0.59\%$, $0.30 \pm 0.16\%$, $1.74 \pm 0.47\%$, соответственно). Вероятно, данные различия определяются биологическими особенностями *Nyctereutes procyonoides ussuriensis*, поскольку этот вид является идеальным хозяином и переносчиком различных заболеваний, а также обладает специфическими морфологическими особенностями клеток крови. Таким образом, наши результаты демонстрируют важность систематических анализов крови и необходимость учитывать как видоспецифичные характеристики, так и факторы окружающей среды для оценки здоровья животных.

Ключевые слова: азиатский барсук, дальневосточный лесной кот, енотовидная собака, иммунная система, лейкограмма, лейкоциты, эритроциты

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

КРАТКИЕ СООБЩЕНИЯ

***ODOBENUS ROSMAREUS DIVERGENS* (ODOBENIDAE) GROUPS IN THE WATERS ADJACENT TO COASTAL HAULOUTS (CHUKCHI PENINSULA, RUSSIA)**

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The distance between individuals is one of the key characteristics of the spatial structure of a group. Here, we investigated inter-individual distances in *Odobenus rosmarus divergens* (hereinafter – walrus) aggregations in waters adjacent to four coastal haulouts in the Chukchi Sea, Russia. The analysis of aerial images showed that the majority of the individuals in water were in tight groups (binomial $z > 11.37$, $p < 0.001$), in which the distances between walruses were significantly shorter than those outside such groups (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.14 ± 0.03 ; $p < 0.001$). The number of individuals within the groups did not influence the inter-individual distances (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.05 ± 0.05 ; $p = 0.376$) and the density of them was similar across haulouts studied (omnibus $\chi^2(3) = 7.78$, $p = 0.051$). The water areas adjacent to haulouts may provide optimal conditions for social interactions of walruses and potentially play an important role in their social life. The investigation of walrus aggregations in water may become increasingly important in the context of the reducing Arctic ice cover.

Key words: aggregation, Chukchi Sea, inter-individual distance, Pacific walrus, pinnipeds, social behaviour

Introduction

The spatial proximity between individuals of the same species depends on a variety of factors, such as the risk of predation, the spatial distribution of resources, intraspecific relationships, and the type of animal activity (Muroyama, 2017). External threats, such as predators, contribute to the mutual attraction of individuals, as this reduces individual risks (Hamilton, 1971). At the same time, a high density of individuals increases competition for food and other resources, so their scarcity leads to an increase in the distance between individuals (Janson & Goldsmith, 1995). The balance of these effects, depending on the set of external conditions (e.g. predator pressure and the availability of resources), determines the spatial structure of the groups; one of their key parameters is the distance between individuals (Mogilner et al., 2003).

Odobenus rosmarus Linnaeus, 1758 (hereafter – walrus) tends to maintain a close proximity between individuals regardless of the group size (Krushinskaya & Lisitsyna, 1983), aiming to maintain constant visual and tactile contact with conspecifics (Miller & Kochnev, 2021). Walruses are probably the most social pinnipeds (Pinnipedia), as they form large aggregations and are gregarious throughout the year, both when in water and on land, regardless of the activity type (Fay, 1982; Miller & Kochnev, 2021). Walruses aggregate on sea ice and come ashore at

hauling-out sites, both on islands and on mainland capes (Fay, 1982). On land, walruses form aggregations that reach hundreds of thousands of individuals (Chakilev & Kochnev, 2014). The composition and number of haulouts change constantly, with some animals coming ashore and others leaving to sea. Some individuals can stay near the haulout for a long time, leaving it for feeding and coming back, while others only stop for a short rest and move to other areas (Jay et al., 2002; Kochnev et al., 2008). As a result, a large number of walruses are constantly in the water area close to the hauling-out sites. The average number of walruses in water near the coastal haulouts of the Chukchi Peninsula can range from 9% to 13% of the total number of walruses hauling out (Kryukova, 2012). The probability of a walrus being in water and not hauling out increases with wind speed, decreases with air temperature, and is related to a diurnal cycle, the reasons for which are not fully understood. However, energy conservation has been proposed to play a major role (Jay et al., 2017).

Walruses display various behavioural types in the waters adjacent to haulouts, namely resting, grooming, playing, as well as suckling in case of young animals (Kryukova, 2016). During resting in the water, individuals of various sexes and age form groups, in which they maintain close physical contact with each other. It is assumed that this helps walruses not to lose

contact with each other and better stabilise their location during strong waves (Kryukova, 2016). The need for thigmotactic thermoregulation (due to the warmth of neighbours' bodies) may also play an important role in cold waters (Miller & Kochnev, 2021). In general, little is known about the social behaviour of walrus in the waters near haulouts in addition to certain aspects of mother-infant interactions (Miller & Boness, 1983; Giljov et al., 2018; Kryukova, 2018).

Compared to tightly packed haulouts, in water, walrus can much more freely control the distance to conspecifics. Therefore, aggregations in the water near haulouts provide a unique opportunity to investigate walrus group behaviour. The aim of this study was to study the spatial relationships between individuals in water near coastal haulouts in *Odobenus rosmarus divergens*. In particular, we investigated the cohesion of individuals by comparing inter-individual distances in groups and outside them.

Material and Methods

For the analysis of the spatial relationships between individuals in the water aggregations, we used drone photo-images taken during walrus population counts in the coastal haulout areas of the Chuk-

chi Peninsula (Altukhov et al., 2020; Kozlov et al., 2020; Pereverzev et al., 2020). The age-sex structure of walrus aggregations at these haulouts is mixed and includes males and females of various ages, females with a dependent calf and juveniles. Aerial photography at the haulouts and adjacent waters was carried out using a small DJI Phantom or Phantom 4 Pro (Da-Jiang Innovations Science and Technology Co., China) unmanned aerial vehicle at an altitude of about 60 m a.s.l., depending on the weather conditions. During the trial flights at these operating altitudes, the animals showed no visible signs of disturbance.

We used the footage obtained during one flight per haulout on four study sites (see Fig. 1). Photographs from Kolyuchin Island (part of the Beringia National Park, Russia) and natural monuments of regional level «Vankarem Cape» and «Kozhevnikov Cape» (Kozhevnikov Cliffs of the Schmidt Cape) were made in September 2017. Images from a proposed natural monument of regional level «Serdtsse-Kamen Cape» were obtained in September – October 2019. From the footage, we analysed orthomosaics compiled with AgiSoft Metashape (Agisoft LLC, Russia) or individual frames (in the case of non-overlapping images) of water areas adjacent to haulouts.

Fig. 1. Study area location at the Chukchi Peninsula, Russia. Designations: A – general view; B – map of the Chukchi Peninsula with four studied haulout sites indicated, namely Kozhevnikov Cape (1), Vankarem Cape (2), Kolyuchin Island (3), Serdtse-Kamen Cape (4); C – aggregation of *Odobenus rosmarus* individuals in waters near the haulout at Kolyuchin Island with group (red line) and non-group (yellow line) areas outlined along the boundary.

The images were analysed using photogrammetric methods in the ImageJ program (National Institutes of Health, USA). Each image was scaled according to the longitudinal length of an adult walrus on each photo, which was fully visible on the surface and stretched out. Given the average length of a walrus (Kastelein, 2009), this roughly corresponds to 2.7–3.2 m.

The inter-individual distances were investigated in groups (Fig. 2) and outside them. A group was defined as an aggregation of three or more walruses, where each individual had two or more neighbours at a distance of one length from the adult walrus body. Pairs of animals, which are usually a female and its dependent calf (Kryukova, 2018), were excluded because they represent long-term social units rather than short-term aggregations of individuals studied in the present study. On each image, all the groups are outlined (red line in Fig. 1C). The total number of individuals in the groups was scored.

The distances between each walrus and all other individuals in the group were measured. The distance between the centres of the walrus backs was considered the inter-individual distance. An additional simple script specially written for the automatic measurement of the distances between individuals was used (see Fig S1). The subsample of three groups per study site was analysed both by the program and by the human rater. The measurements were further compared with the Mann-Whitney test and Spearman rank cor-

relation. High program-rater reliability was revealed ($p < 0.001$) with both approaches.

To investigate the inter-individual distances between walruses in water outside the groups, on each image, the outlined group contours were transferred to the parts of the water area on the image where the groups were absent (yellow line in Fig. 1C), and the distances were measured within these contours («non-groups»). Thus, inter-individual distances for walruses in groups and outside groups were measured within equal water areas.

In the analysis, each outlined group (or «non-group») was a sampling unit, for which we computed a median value of inter-individual distances by pooling the data from all individuals. This approach was successfully applied previously in a study on group cohesion in *Dama dama* Linnaeus, 1758 (Focardi & Pecchioli, 2005). We performed a mixed linear model (LMM) that generalises an ANOVA with the use of random-effects parameters, which may impact the variability of the data (Table S1). To model the data, the median distances were used as a variable, group/non-group was used as a factor, the haulout site as a cluster variable, the number of individuals and the area occupied by the group/non-group as covariates. The areas occupied by the groups/non-groups were measured in «square walrus lengths» with the ROI (regions of interest) tool in ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, USA). Log transformation of the data was applied for normalisation of the residuals.

Fig. 2. A typical group of the *Odobenus rosmarus* individuals in water off Kolyuchin Island haulout (Chukchi Sea, Russia).

The density of walrus in water was estimated using the index, calculated as the area occupied by the group divided by the number of animals in the group. The same index was calculated for the «non-groups» (Table S2, Table S3). The areas occupied by the groups and their corresponding «non-groups» were equal (Fig 1C), and the index scores represented the density of individuals within the groups and outside them. For these data, we used a binomial logistic regression with aggregation type (group/non-group) as a variable. The walrus/area index was used as a covariate and the study site (haulout area) was used as a factor. Data processing and statistical analysis were performed in Jamovi v. 2.3 software (Jamovi project, 2022).

Ethical statement

All applicable international, national, and institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed. All procedures performed in the study were in accordance with the ethical standards of the Saint Petersburg State University ethical committee (Permit №131-03-3).

Results

The analysis of aerial photographs revealed that on all four study sites, the majority of individuals ($n = 2755$) in the waters adjacent to the haulouts were aggregated in groups (77–85% per haulout site; binomial $z > 11.37$, $p < 0.001$). In total, inter-individual distances were obtained for 115 groups and corresponding 115 «non-groups». The largest group scored consisted of 418 animals. The LMM was used to test the effects of the median inter-individual distance on the aggregation metrics (group/non-group, area occupied by it, number of associates) and accounted for the haulout variation (Table S1, Table S2, Table S3). The model explained 65% of the variance in the data (R -squared = 0.65). On all the haulout sites, the inter-individual distances were related to whether the animals were in groups or outside them, with significantly shorter distances in groups (groups: median = 1.63, IQR = 1.10; non-groups: median = 2.44, IQR = 2.15; LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.14 ± 0.03 ; $p < 0.001$).

Larger inter-individual distances were associated with larger areas occupied by the group/non-group (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.47 ± 0.04 ; $p < 0.001$), whereas there was no effect of the number of individuals in the group/non-group on the median inter-individual distance (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.05 ± 0.05 ; $p = 0.376$). There was no relationship between the median inter-individual distance and the haulout site ($p > 0.05$).

The density of walrus in water was examined with binomial logistic regression. The overall model was significant ($\chi^2(4) = 79.3$, $p < 0.001$; Table S2 in Electronic Supplement 1). Unsurprisingly, the density of walrus in the groups was greater than that in the non-groups (groups: median = 0.82, IQR = 0.43; non-groups: median = 1.59, IQR = 1.92; omnibus $\chi^2(1) = 79.34$ $p < 0.001$). The walrus density did not differ significantly between the haulout sites (omnibus $\chi^2(3) = 7.78$ $p = 0.051$).

Discussion

The analysis of the spatial relationships between walrus in the waters adjacent to coastal haulouts showed that the majority of individuals (up to 85%) were aggregated in groups. The distance between individuals was significantly shorter and their density in the groups was greater than within the water areas of the same size outside such groups. Our results are in line with the previous knowledge about strong tendency for social aggregation in walrus (Fay, 1982; Miller & Kochnev, 2021). However, it should be noted that we studied a specific state of walrus aggregating near the coast, while aggregations on ice, which are more typical for these mammals, play a more important role in their social behaviour (Miller & Kochnev, 2021).

The distance between individuals is one of the key characteristics of the group spatial structure (Mogilner et al., 2003). A certain distance between animals in a group can be species-specific, but only under stable conditions. In the natural environment, typical inter-individual distance can be influenced by a set of intrinsic and external factors (Muroyama, 2017). For instance, walrus attacked by *Orcinus orca* Linnaeus, 1758 are united in more dense groups (Kryukova et al., 2012). Therefore, it can be assumed that the distance between individuals in walrus groups in water can vary under various conditions. However, our results did not show any significant difference among the four studied haulout sites. It is important to note though that the weather conditions on all study sites were similarly calm and animals were resting. A different result may be observed during walrus migration off shore, near ice haulouts, when animals are disturbed, for example by a predator, or when fast ice is present near the shore. Thus, multiple factors may influence the distance between individuals in walrus groups. Therefore, the results obtained in this study may be not applicable to different study conditions.

A study of walrus resting in water showed that the occurrence of various resting poses depended on

the size of the group (Kryukova, 2016). It might be that the larger the group, the more relaxed the walrus are, and therefore the animals adopt a more comfortable horizontal posture but have less control over the environment in comparison with vertical one. The distance between individuals, as it is shown in the present study, was not affected by the group size. In line with this, it has been previously suggested that walrus form tight groups regardless of the number of individuals (Krushinskaya & Lisitsyna, 1983). This result also agrees with studies on birds (Miller & Stephen, 1966) and fish (Breder, 1951), which showed that the distance between individuals is independent of the flock size.

The formation of tight groups (Fig. 2) suggests that the aggregations of walrus in the waters near the haulouts (Kryukova, 2012) are not just the individuals approaching and leaving the haulout. Grouping may help walrus stabilise themselves in waters during strong waves (Kryukova, 2016). Moreover, within a group, particularly in its centre, animals face less risk of predation (Morrell & Romey, 2008). However, it is widely assumed that the formation of tight groups in walrus is primarily associated with social attraction (Miller & Kochnev, 2021). The maintenance of close contact with conspecifics, particularly tactile contact, known as thigmotaxis, is an inherent feature of this species. It was indicated that being in such rafting groups close to the haulout provide walrus the greatest opportunity for repeated and prolonged social interactions (Miller & Boness, 1983). We hypothesise that the water areas adjacent to haulouts may play the role of so-called «social arenas» described for other mammals (e.g. Fishlock & Lee, 2013; Giljov & Karegina, 2024), where a large number of various social interactions among walrus occur. However, to test this hypothesis it is important to study walrus behaviour near ice haulouts where these animals spend a considerable part of their life cycle.

In waters away from haulouts, the probability of meeting conspecifics of various sex and age is considerably lower. A shallow bay protected from strong waves and winds where the haulout forms, with warmer water, also facilitate more comfort behaviour, including positive social engagement. On land, walrus have limited mobility, and the variety and intensity of social contacts are limited. Thus, the water areas near haulouts provide optimal conditions for social interactions of walrus. The formation of tight groups in water suggests that water aggregations may be as important for walrus social behaviour as terrestrial haulouts. In addition,

a major reduction in Arctic ice cover, along with prolonged periods of open water in the Chukchi Sea (Wang & Overland, 2015), may increase the importance of social aggregations in water for the walrus.

Conclusions

Our study has highlighted the importance of water aggregations for walrus in waters adjacent to coastal haulouts. Walrus display a strong tendency for social aggregation observed in water, with tight group formations and absence of agonistic competition for a piece of land. This may suggest that these water areas **potentially serve as crucial areas for various social interactions among individuals**. The stability of inter-individual distances across various group sizes and haulout sites emphasises the robustness of these **aggregations in walrus**. As the Arctic environment continues to change, with reduced ice cover and extended open water periods, the role of water aggregations may become even more important for the species survival and adaptation. Future research should focus on understanding the specific social dynamics within these groups, as well as the potential impacts of changing environmental conditions on walrus social behaviour and overall population health.

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Supporting Information

Additional data to the paper of Giljov et al. (2024) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

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ГРУППЫ *ODOBENUS ROSMARUS DIVERGENS* (ODOBENIDAE) В АКВАТОРИЯХ, ПРИЛЕГАЮЩИХ К ЛЕЖБИЩАМ (ЧУКОТСКИЙ ПОЛУОСТРОВ, РОССИЯ)

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Расстояние между особями – одна из ключевых характеристик пространственной структуры группы. В данной работе описаны особенности пространственных отношений между особями в скоплениях *Odobenus rosmarus divergens* (далее – морж) в акваториях, прилегающих к четырем прибрежным лежбищам в Чукотском море (Россия). Анализ аэрофотоснимков показал, что большинство моржей в воде находилось в плотных группах (binomial $z > 11.37$, $p < 0.001$), в которых расстояния между особями были значительно меньше, чем вне таких групп (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.14 ± 0.03 ; $p < 0.001$). Количество особей в группах не влияло на расстояния между ними (LMM coefficient \pm SE: 0.05 ± 0.05 ; $p = 0.376$), и плотность групп особей была сходна на всех исследованных лежбищах (omnibus $\chi^2(3) = 7.78$, $p = 0.051$). Акватории, прилегающие к лежбищам, могут обеспечивать оптимальные условия для социальных взаимодействий моржей и играть важную роль в их общественной жизни. Исследование скоплений моржей в воде приобретает все большее значение в условиях сокращения ледового покрова Арктики.

Ключевые слова: ластоногие, межиндивидуальное расстояние, скопление, социальное поведение, тихоокеанский морж, Чукотское море

RESEARCH NOTES

НАУЧНЫЕ ЗАМЕТКИ

FIRST FINDING OF *MACYELLA APODEMI* (DIGENEA, PLEUROGENIDAE) IN RUSSIA

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This paper presents data on the trematode *Macyella apodemi* recorded for the first time in Russia. Three mature specimens have been found in the diverticula of the small intestine of *Apodemus uralensis* (Rodentia, Muridae) in the Mordovia State Nature Reserve (European Russia) in 2022. Here, a detailed morphological and morphometrical description of this digenean species is provided. *Apodemus uralensis* is noticed as a new host for *Macyella apodemi*.

Key words: *Apodemus*, Mordovia State Nature Reserve, parasitic worms, rodents, trematodes, Ural field mouse

The trematode *Macyella apodemi* Jourdan & Triquell, 1973 (Digenea, Pleurogenidae) is a very rare parasite of wood rodents, mainly mice. This species was first described by Jourdan & Triquell (1973) from the wood-dwelled species *Apodemus sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Previously, findings of *Macyella apodemi* were known only from rodents in the Pyrenees (Jourdan & Triquell, 1973; Montoliu & Feliu, 1986; Ribas et al., 2005). Another species of the genus *Macyella* from rodents, *M. vassilevi* Jancev, 1974, was described from *Apodemus sylvaticus* in the Balkan Mountains (Jancev, 1974). Due to the high morphological similarity of these two species, Montoliu & Feliu (1986) proposed their synonymy. Kanarek et al. (2017) also agree with this opinion because they believe that morphological and morphometrical features of these *Macyella* species do not considerably differ. Unfortunately, molecular data have not been obtained from these digenean species yet.

The complex parasitological surveys of small mammals in the Mordovia State Nature Reserve were conducted in May and July of 2022–2023. In July 2022, three mature *Macyella apodemi* specimens were collected from the diverticula of the small intestine of one male of *Apodemus uralensis* (Pallas, 1811) in the vicinity of Taratinskiy cordon (54.746334° N, 43.085931° E) in the Mordovia State Nature Reserve (Republic of Mordovia, Russia). The prevalence of infection was 7.1% (one of 14 rodents), with mean an intensity of 0.21.

Trematodes were recovered from the small intestine of *Apodemus uralensis* and immobilised

by heating in a saline solution. Then, the trematode specimens were stained with acetic carmine, dehydrated, cleared in clove oil and mounted in Canada balsam. The line drawing of *Macyella apodemi* was made using a Levenhuk M500 BASE Digital Camera and RA-7 drawing tube attached to an MBI-9 light microscope. Morphological identification of this digenean species was carried out according the keys of Genov (1984) and Jourdan & Triquell (1973). A voucher specimen was deposited at the Institute of Ecology of the Volga River Basin RAS (Togliatti, Russia).

A morphological description of *Macyella apodemi* from *Apodemus uralensis* (based on three mature specimens) is provided below (see Fig. 1). Mean values are provided in parentheses. The body is pear-shaped with a length of 0.626–0.684 (0.653) mm and maximum width of 0.412–0.433 (0.422) mm at the level of the testes. Tegument is armed with small spines. Oral sucker is round, subterminal; its size is 0.083–0.087 (0.085) × 0.087–0.091 (0.089) mm. Prepharynx is indistinguishable. Pharynx size is 0.037–0.040 (0.039) × 0.034–0.038 (0.036) mm. Ventral sucker is pre-equatorial, slightly larger than the oral one; its size is 0.095–0.100 (0.097) × 0.099–0.112 (0.105) mm. Esophagus is short, with length of 0.067–0.079 (0.072) mm, almost reaching the ovary. Intestinal bifurcation is located at the level of the ovary. Intestinal branches are located laterally, reaching the level of the testes. The ends of the intestinal branches are indistinguishable, because they are hidden by the uterus loops filled with eggs.

Fig. 1. The trematode *Macyella apodemi* from *Apodemus uralensis*; general view.

Testes are oval, located laterally at the posterior edge of ventral sucker, approximately at the same level. Sinistral testis size is 0.135–0.150 (0.144) × 0.119–0.133 (0.126) mm, dextral testis size is 0.141–0.152 (0.145) × 0.122–0.135 (0.129) mm. Sinister testis is more or less overlapped by the posterolateral edge of ventral sucker. Cirrus sac is elongated (0.283–0.315 (0.298) × 0.067–0.073 (0.070) mm), passes from the left body edge to the anterior edge of the left testis, by curving in an S-shape. Proximal end of cirrus sac may be more or less overlapped by posterolateral edge of ventral sucker. Seminal vesicle is convoluted and occupies all proximal part of cirrus sac. Genital pore opens ventrally at the left edge of body in its posterior third. Ovary is lobed; its size is 0.100–0.110 (0.105) × 0.087–0.112 (0.097) mm, located slightly anterior and lateral to ventral sucker. Vitellarium consists of irregularly shaped follicles located laterally in two compact groups. Vitelline fields extend from the pharynx level to the anterior edge of ventral sucker and on the dorsal side of the body they joined. Uterus

forms numerous loops and occupies the whole space from ventral sucker to the posterior body end. Uterus loops can rise to the level of vitellarium. Eggs are numerous and oval; their size is 0.024–0.029 (0.026) × 0.011–0.015 (0.013) mm.

All three *Macyella apodemi* specimens are similar in morphological and morphometric characteristics. The characteristic features of the species were always present. In general, these *M. apodemi* specimens correspond very well to the previous descriptions of this digenean species in the main morphological and morphometric characteristics (Jourdane & Triquell, 1973; Jancev, 1974; Montoliu & Feliu, 1986).

The finding of mature trematodes in *Apodemus uralensis* indicates that this rodent species is the final host for *Macyella apodemi*. The animal species become infected with this parasite by eating terrestrial insects (Genov, 1984). Thus, *M. apodemi* is recorded for the first time from rodents in Russia, while *A. uralensis* is noticed as a new trematode host.

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ПЕРВОЕ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЕ *MACYELLA APODEMI* (DIGENEA, PLEUROGENIDAE) В РОССИИ

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Трематода *Macyella apodemi* впервые зарегистрирована у грызунов фауны России. Три половозрелых экземпляра *M. apodemi* обнаружено в дивертикулах тонкого кишечника вида *Apodemus uralensis* в Мордовском государственном заповеднике (Европейская Россия) в 2022 г. В данной статье приведены морфологическое и морфометрическое описание этого вида дигеней. *Apodemus uralensis* отмечен в качестве нового хозяина для *M. apodemi*.

Ключевые слова: *Apodemus*, грызуны, малая лесная мышь, Мордовский государственный заповедник, паразитические черви, трематоды

***EPIPACTIS PERSICA* (ORCHIDACEAE), A NEW TAXON FOR THE FLORA OF KAZAKHSTAN, KYRGYZSTAN AND CHINA**

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The paper provides information about *Epipactis persica*, a new species for the flora of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and China. New localities of this species are based on herbarium material stored in herbarium collections AA, KUZ, LE, MW, NUR, and TASH, personal field records, and observations published on iNaturalist. Localities in Kazakhstan represent the northernmost records of *E. persica*, but its possible presence in Russian Siberia is discussed. In China, *E. persica* is currently reported based only on historical herbarium collections dated by 1877–1879.

Key words: Central Asia, Kazakh Altai, new records, orchids, Tarbagatai, Western Tien Shan

The genus *Epipactis* Zinn (Orchidaceae: Epidendroideae: Neottieae) is taxonomically one of the most complicated genera of orchids. The exact number of taxa in the genus *Epipactis* is still unclear, being estimated from 50 to 80 species worldwide according to various sources (Delforge, 2016; Fateryga & Fateryga, 2018; Łobas et al., 2021). Three *Epipactis* species were known in Kazakhstan, namely *E. atrorubens* (Hoffm.) Besser, *E. helleborine* (L.) Crantz, and *E. palustris* (L.) Crantz (Abdulina, 1998; Sumbembayev et al., 2020; Kubentayev et al., 2023). In Kyrgyzstan, the following three *Epipactis* species have been reported so far: *E. helleborine*, *E. palustris*, and *E. royleana* Lindl. (Lazkov & Sultanova, 2014). Ten species (*E. alata* Aver. & Efimov, *E. helleborine*, *E. humilior* (Tang & F.T.Wang) S.C.Chen & G.H.Zhu, *E. mairei* Schltr., *E. palustris*, *E. papillosa* Franch. & Sav., *E. royleana*, *E. tangutica* Schltr., *E. thunbergii* A.Gray, *E. veratrifolia* Boiss. & Hohen., and *E. xanthophaea* Schltr.) were known in China (Grubov, 1977; Wu et al., 2008; Efimov & Verkhovina, 2014).

Epipactis persica (Soó) Hausskn. ex Nannf. is a well-known species, belonging to the *E. helleborine* aggregate. It is autogamous (Fateryga & Ivanov, 2012; Sramkó et al., 2019). Its main habitats are deciduous and coniferous forests. *Epipactis persica* has been recorded in the Balkans, Crimea, the Caucasus, Western Asia (except south of the Arabian Peninsula), Central Asia (Tajikistan, Turkmenistan), and Southern Asia (Afghanistan, Pakistan) (Fateryga et al., 2020), and recently reported also from Uzbekistan (Verkhovina et al., 2024). The main characters distinguishing *E. per-*

sica from other related *Epipactis* species are leaves equal in length to internodes or only slightly exceeding them in length, almost glabrous or sparsely pubescent rachis of inflorescence and ovaries, epichilium with well-defined smooth tubercles at the base, and rostellum with well-developed, but not sticky viscidium (Fateryga et al., 2018).

As the result of an ongoing detailed taxonomic inventory of orchids of Kazakhstan, started in 2020, the following two species were added to the Kazakhstan flora: *Neottia cordata* (L.) Rich. and *Hammarbya paludosa* (L.) Kuntze (Kubentayev et al., 2021). Recently, Kubentayev et al. (2023) published a detailed review of all orchids of the northern part of Kazakhstan. In the course of taxonomic inventory of mountainous areas of southern and eastern Kazakhstan, we came across one more species, *Epipactis persica* (Fig. S2), which has not previously been reported for either Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, nor China (Abdulina, 1998; Wu et al., 2008; Lazkov & Sultanova, 2014; Fateryga et al., 2020; Sumbembayev et al., 2020; Kubentayev et al., 2023). We analysed herbarium collections in AA, KUZ, LE, MW, NUR, and TASH, personal field records, and observations published on iNaturalist (Electronic Supplement 1). As the result, *Epipactis persica* proved to be widely distributed in Central Asia, and it also occurs in China (Xinjiang) (Fig. S1), from where only old (1877–1879) herbarium collections kept in LE are available.

Earlier, almost all of the above-mentioned *Epipactis persica* herbarium specimens were mis-determined as *E. helleborine*. According to our knowledge, only very few true *E. helleborine*

herbarium collections are known in Central Asia, giving evidence that *E. persica* largely displaces *E. helleborine* in this area. In Europe, in contrast with Central Asia, these species either co-occur or only *E. helleborine* is present.

According to the geographical distribution of *Epipactis persica* outlined in the present study, it may be supposed that this species also occurs in Russian Siberia, which needs further studies. In herbarium collections, we came across specimens similar to *E. persica* collected in the south parts of Altaysky Krai, Irkutsk Region, and the Republic of Buryatia. However, in Irkutsk Region and the Republic of Buryatia, another species, *E. tangutica*, superficially similar to *E. persica* was reported (Efimov & Verkhozina, 2014). *Epipactis persica* and *E. tangutica* are very similar when herbarium-dried, and their safe delimitation is often possible only in living state or being based on high-quality photographs. The population of *E. persica* discovered in Kazakhstan was small and included only 2–5 individuals. Additional data are needed for correct assessing the conservation status of *E. persica*. The existing data make the impression that *E. persica* is not very rare and we preliminary treat it as LC both in Kazakhstan and in Central Asia in general. Additionally, it should be noted that 28 of 36 known localities are situated within Protected Areas.

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Supporting Information

Additional data for the paper of Kubentayev et al. (2024) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

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***EPIPACTIS PERSICA* (ORCHIDACEAE) – НОВЫЙ ТАКСОН ДЛЯ ФЛОРЫ КАЗАХСТАНА, КЫРГЫЗСТАНА И КИТАЯ**

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В статье приведены сведения об *Epipactis persica* – новом виде для флоры Казахстана, Кыргызстана и Китая. Новые местонахождения этого вида основаны на гербарных материалах, хранящихся в AA, KUZ, LE, MW, NUR, and TASH, а также на материалах полевых исследований и наблюдений на iNaturalist. Установлено, что самая северная граница общего ареала *E. persica* находится в Казахстане, однако возможно его нахождение на юге Сибири в России. Из Китая *E. persica* приводится по историческим гербарным коллекциям, собранным в 1877–1879 гг., которые хранятся в LE.

Ключевые слова: Западный Тянь-Шань, Казахстанский Алтай, новые находки, орхидеи, Тарбагатай, Центральная Азия

FIRST RECORD OF *EPIDENDRUM* × *DOROTEAE* (ORCHIDACEAE) IN SOUTH AMERICA

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Epidendrum × *doroteae* (Orchidaceae), a natural hybrid between *Epidendrum ciliare* and *Epidendrum nocturnum*, was hitherto known only from a few specimens collected during the 1940s–1990s in Honduras, Central America. *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* is recorded here for the first time in Nicaragua and in South America, in Brazil. We found three clusters of individuals of the hybrid in sympatry with the parental species on Marajó Island, state of Pará, in the Brazilian Amazon, and we recognised two specimens from Nicaragua deposited in the herbaria AMO and MO as *E. ×doroteae*. *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* and the parental taxa have star-shape flowers with yellowish-green sepals and petals. However, *E. ×doroteae* differs from the parental species when fertile by the lateral lobes of the lip, which have an irregularly serrate-dentate, rarely slightly fimbriate margin vs. entire to slightly undulate margin in *E. nocturnum* and distinctly fimbriate margin in *E. ciliare*.

Key words: botanical collection, Brazilian Amazon, Laeliinae, Marajó Island, natural hybrid, Nicaragua, orchids

Epidendrum L. counts around 1900 species and is one of the largest genera of orchids in the Neotropical region, occurring in several types of vegetation (Hágsater & Soto-Arenas, 2005; POWO, 2024). Hybridisation is relatively common in Orchidaceae, resulting mainly from weak or permeable reproductive barriers, and has been intensively investigated in *Epidendrum* (e.g. Vega et al., 2013; Marques et al., 2014; Pinheiro et al., 2016). The genus encompasses 12 natural hybrids (POWO, 2024), including *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* P.H. Allen, which has *Epidendrum ciliare* L. and *Epidendrum nocturnum* Jacq. as putative parental species (Allen, 1958). *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* was described from only one specimen collected in the Department of Francisco Morazán, Honduras (Allen, 1958), but other specimens were collected in the locality and also in the neighbouring department, El Paraíso, in the 1940s–1990s. *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* has been treated as endemic to Honduras until now (Hágsater & Sánchez-Saldaña, 2008; Vega et al., 2022; POWO, 2024).

During field expeditions to the Brazilian Amazon in the state of Pará, we found three clusters of individuals of *E. ×doroteae* and several individuals of its parental species growing in sympatry. Specimens of the three taxa were photographed *in situ*, collected, herborised according to usual taxonomic techniques, and later deposited at the herbarium MG. Here, we report the first record of the hybrid in South America and the first record in the XXI century. This finding led us to analyse digital images of specimens of *E. ×doroteae* (most of them were primarily misidentified as *E. ciliare*) deposited at

the herbaria AMES, AMO, EAP, LL, MEXU, MIN, MG, MO, NY, PH, SEL, UC and US (acronyms are given according to Thiers et al., 2024), which also revealed the occurrence of the hybrid in Nicaragua.

Epidendrum × *doroteae*, previously reported as an epiphytic or rupicolous orchid in pine-oak woods at altitudes of 900–1000 m a.s.l. in Honduras (Hágsater & Sánchez-Saldaña, 2008), occurs at slightly higher altitudes in Nicaragua (920–1300 m a.s.l.), also in a pine forest. In Brazil, it was found at about 20 m a.s.l. in terra firme forests on Marajó Island, the largest river-sea island in the world, where it grows on angiosperm species at 4–10 m above the ground. This shows that *E. ×doroteae* does not exhibit habitat specificity. *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* is treated as a taxon of «Preocupación Especial» (Special Concern) in Honduras (SERNA, 2008), and considering that the most recent previous global record dates from 1996, the hybrid can be considered rare.

Epidendrum ciliare and *E. ×doroteae* belong to the *Coilostylis* group *sensu* Hágsater & Sánchez-Saldaña (2008). This group is characterised by the caulomes thickened into heteroblastic and fusiform pseudobulbs, racemose and distichous inflorescences; the peduncle is covered by large non-spathaceous bracts, and large star-shaped flowers are with long, narrow sepals and petals. In turn, *E. nocturnum* belongs to the *E. nocturnum* group *sensu* Hágsater & Sánchez-Saldaña (2008), which has short, racemose or pluri-racemose inflorescences, the peduncle without spathaceous bracts, and usually large star-shaped flowers with

morphologically similar sepals and petals. Thus, the three taxa have star-shaped flowers with yellowish-green sepals and petals that are close in size. However, *E. ×doroteae* differs from the parental species when fertile by the lateral lobes of the lip, which have an irregularly serrate-dentate, rarely slightly fimbriate margin vs. entire to slightly undulate margin in *E. nocturnum* and distinctly fimbriate margin in *E. ciliare* (Fig. 1).

Further, *E. ×doroteae* differs from *E. nocturnum* by the inflorescence, which generally has three or more flowers and very evident bracteoles, covering about half of the pedicellate ovary vs. inflorescence with 1(–2)-flowers and short bracteoles, restricted to the base of the pedicellate ovary. Since *E. ×doroteae* is morphologically similar to *E. ciliare*, it is possible that there are other specimens of *E. ×doroteae* deposited in herbaria and misidentified as *E. ciliare*. Therefore, a more careful analysis of Neotropical collections is necessary.

Fig. 1. *Epidendrum ×doroteae* and its parental species. Designations: A – *Epidendrum ciliare*, flower in central view (D.S. Ferreira, E.G. Nascimento 112, MG, Brazil); B – *Epidendrum nocturnum*, flower in lateral view (D.S. Ferreira, E.G. Nascimento 222, MG, Brazil); C – *Epidendrum ×doroteae*, flower in lateral view (D.S. Ferreira, E.G. Nascimento 149, MG, Brazil); D – *Epidendrum ×doroteae*, details of the column and lip (D.S. Ferreira, E.G. Nascimento 149, MG, Brazil).

Examined specimens of *E. ×doroteae* are listed below. 1. Brazil: 1.1. Pará, Cachoeira do Arari, Vila de Retiro Grande, 01.05.2023, D.S. Ferreira, E.G. Nascimento 149 (MG).

2. Honduras: 2.1. El Paraíso, hills near Las Mesas, 900 m a.s.l., 20.07.1946, L.O. Williams, A. Molina 10077 (AMES barcode 02174872, digital image!, PH barcode 00590983, digital image!, MEXU barcode 87175, digital image!, UC barcode 729279, digital image!); 2.2. Francisco Morazán, along junction of Jicarito and Gallo creeks, 1000 m a.s.l., 19.06.1947, fl., A. Molina 142 (AMES barcode 02174854, digital image!, MEXU barcode 87168, digital image!); 2.3. Francisco Morazán, along junction of Jicarito and Gallo creeks, 1000 m a.s.l., 19.06.1947, fl., A. Molina 144 (AMES barcode 02174853, digital image!, MEXU barcode 87178, digital image!, US barcode 00316018, digital image!); 2.4. Drainage of the Rio Yeguaré, Las Mesas, 3600 ft, 06.11.1948, S.F. Glassman 1551 (MIN barcode 1310316, digital image!, NY barcode 04076989, digital image!); 2.5. Hills East of the Yeguaré Valley, 3200 ft, 28.10.1957, P. Allen, D. Allen 6786 (EAP barcode 3777, holotype, digital image!); 2.6. Barranco Las Mesas, 900 m a.s.l., 07.07.1964, A. Molina 14434 (NY barcode 04076983, digital image!); 2.7. Quebrada El Naranjo, ca. 4 km southeast of Zamorano, 03.07.1996, fl., J.L. Linares, F.J. Hubbard 3451 (MEXU barcode 833239, digital image!, MEXU barcode 1061693, digital image!); 2.8. Without locality, 1959, P.H. Allen s.n. (mounted 17.10.1975, fl., Fritz Hamer A5) (SEL barcode 030887, digital image!, MO barcode 478892, digital image!); 2.9. Without locality, s.d., P.H. Allen s.n. (mounted 18.10.1971, fl., Fritz Hamer s.n.) (AMES barcode 01539729, digital image!).

3. Nicaragua: 3.1. Estelí, Salto de Estanzuela, Rio Estanzuela, ca 6 km south of Estelí, 920–1020 m a.s.l., 31.07.1981, W.D. Stevens, B.A. Krukoff 20568 (MO barcode 269733, digital image!); 3.2. Jinotega, Southwest of Jinotega, along road to La Cantera and Los Pinos, in region of pine forest, 1050–1350 m a.s.l., 25.06.1947, P.C. Standley 10103 (AMO 003649, xerox!).

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ПЕРВАЯ НАХОДКА *EPIDENDRUM* × *DOROTEA*E (ORCHIDACEAE) В ЮЖНОЙ АМЕРИКЕ

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Epidendrum × *doroteae* (Orchidaceae), естественный гибрид между *Epidendrum ciliare* и *Epidendrum nocturnum*, был до сих пор известен только по нескольким образцам, собранным в 1940–1990-х годах в Гондурасе (Центральная Америка). В данной работе *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* впервые отмечен в Никарагуа и в Южной Америке (в Бразилии). Было обнаружено три кластера особей гибрида, находящихся в симпатрии с родительскими видами на острове Маражо (штат Пара, бразильская Амазония), и два образца из Никарагуа, хранящихся в гербариях АМО и МО, определены как *E. ×doroteae*. *Epidendrum* × *doroteae* и родительские таксоны имеют звездчатые цветки с желтовато-зелеными чашелистиками и лепестками. Однако *E. ×doroteae* отличается от родительского вида в цветущем состоянии по боковым долям губы, которые имеют нерегулярно пильчато-зубчатый, редко слегка бахромчатый, край по сравнению с цельным или слегка волнистым краем губы у *E. nocturnum* и отчетливо бахромчатым краем губы у *E. ciliare*.

Ключевые слова: Laeliinae, ботаническая коллекция, бразильская Амазония, естественный гибрид, Никарагуа, орхидеи, остров Маражо

Contents

RESEARCH ARTICLES

- CYCLICITY IN ONTOGENY AND AGE DETERMINATION OF *FLEXOPECTEN GLABER* (BIVALVIA, PECTINIDAE) IN THE BLACK SEA 1
I.P. Bondarev
- POPULATION, NESTING CHARACTERISTICS, AND BREEDING ECOLOGY OF THE CRITICALLY ENDANGERED *GYPUS INDICUS* IN MUDUMALAI TIGER RESERVE, SOUTH INDIA 9
A. Samson, J.L. Princy, B. Ramakrishnan
- OPTIMISING *JUNIPERUS EXCELSA* (CUPRESSACEAE) GERMINATION FOR SUSTAINABLE ECOSYSTEM RESTORATION IN THE PRESPA AREA (WESTERN MACEDONIA, GREECE) 21
G. Varsamis, S. Tsiftsis, I. Koutseri, T. Merou
- WOLF-UNGULATE INTERACTIONS WITHIN THE CONTEXT OF WOLF'S MAIN PREY POPULATION DECLINE IN CENTRAL RUSSIAN UPLAND 32
A.O. Viricheva, E.M. Litvinova, M.D. Chistopolova, A.D. Poyarkov, J.A. Hernandez-Blanco
- FAUNA AND BIOTOPIC DISTRIBUTION OF CHRYSOMELIDAE (COLEOPTERA) IN THE SHAITAN-TAU STATE NATURE RESERVE, RUSSIA 47
S.V. Dedyukhin
- THE VASCULAR FLORA OF THE FORESTE CASENTINESI, MONTE FALTERONA, CAMPIGNA NATIONAL PARK (NORTHERN APENNINES, ITALY): UPDATING THE CHECKLIST 66
D. Viciani, D. Alberti
- MIGRATION ROUTES AND KEY STOPOVERS OF *ANSER FABALIS FABALIS* (ANSERIFORMES): CRITICAL PROTECTION GAPS 80
S.B. Rozenfeld, E.G. Strelnikov, S.V. Volkov
- HEMATOLOGICAL ANALYSIS AS A METHOD OF MONITORING PHYSIOLOGICAL STATUS OF MEDIUM CARNIVOROUS MAMMALS IN THE RUSSIAN FAR EAST 93
G.S. Alekseeva, M.N. Erofeeva, J.A. Hernandez-Blanco, M.N. Litvinov, M.D. Chistopolova, M.D. Kim, V.V. Rozhnov, S.V. Naidenko
- SHORT COMMUNICATIONS**
- ODOBENUS ROSMARUS DIVERGENS* (ODOBENIDAE) GROUPS IN THE WATERS ADJACENT TO COASTAL HAULOUTS (CHUKCHI PENINSULA, RUSSIA) 105
A.N. Giljov, M.V. Serebinskaya, N.V. Kryukova, D.O. Skorobogatov, K.A. Karenina
- RESEARCH NOTES**
- FIRST FINDING OF *MACYELLA APODEMI* (DIGENEA, PLEUROGENIDAE) IN RUSSIA 112
N.Yu. Kirillova, A.A. Kirillov
- EPIPACTIS PERSICA* (ORCHIDACEAE), A NEW TAXON FOR THE FLORA OF KAZAKHSTAN, KYRGYZSTAN AND CHINA 115
S.A. Kubentayev, P.G. Efimov, A.V. Fateryga
- FIRST RECORD OF *EPIDENDRUM* × *DOROTEAE* (ORCHIDACEAE) IN SOUTH AMERICA 118
D.F. da Silva, E.G. do Nascimento, F.F.V.A. Barberena

Содержание

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ

- ЦИКЛИЧНОСТЬ В ОНТОГЕНЕЗЕ И ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ВОЗРАСТА *FLEXOPESTEN GLABER* (BIVALVIA, PESTINIDAE) В ЧЕРНОМ МОРЕ 1
И.П. Бондарев
- ПОПУЛЯЦИЯ, ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГНЕЗДОВАНИЯ И ЭКОЛОГИЯ РАЗМНОЖЕНИЯ НАХОДЯЩЕГОСЯ ПОД УГРОЗОЙ ИСЧЕЗНОВЕНИЯ *GYPIS INDICUS* В ТИГРОВИКОМ ЗАПОВЕДНИКЕ МУДУМАЛАЙ, ЮЖНАЯ ИНДИЯ 9
А. Самсон, Дж.Л. Принси, Б. Рамакришнан
- ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ПРОРАЩИВАНИЯ *JUNIPERUS EXCELSA* (CUPRESSACEAE) ДЛЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОСИСТЕМ В РЕГИОНЕ ПРЕСПА (ЗАПАДНАЯ МАКЕДОНИЯ, ГРЕЦИЯ) 21
Г. Варсамис, С. Цифцис, И. Куцери, Т. Меру
- ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ВОЛКА И КОПЫТНЫХ В УСЛОВИЯХ СНИЖЕНИЯ ЧИСЛЕННОСТИ ОСНОВНОГО ВИДА ДОБЫЧИ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ СРЕДНЕРУССКОЙ ВОЗВЫШЕННОСТИ 32
А.О. Виричева, Е.М. Литвинова, М.Д. Чистополова, А.Д. Поярков, Х.А. Эрнандес-Бланко
- ФАУНА И БИОТОПИЧЕСКОЕ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ЖУКОВ-ЛИСТОЕДОВ (COLEOPTERA: CHRYSOMELIDAE) ЗАПОВЕДНИКА «ШАЙТАН-ТАУ» (РОССИЯ) 47
С.В. Дедюхин
- ФЛОРА СОСУДИСТЫХ РАСТЕНИЙ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПАРКА «ФОРЕСТЕ-КАСЕНТИНЕЗИ, МОНТЕ-ФАЛЬТЕРОНА И КАМПИНЬЯ» (СЕВЕРНЫЕ АПЕННИНЫ, ИТАЛИЯ): ОБНОВЛЕННЫЙ СПИСОК ВИДОВ 66
Д. Вичани, Д. Альберти
- МАРШРУТЫ МИГРАЦИИ И КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ОСТАНОВКИ *ANSER FABALIS FABALIS* (ANSERIFORMES): АНАЛИЗ ПРОБЛЕМ ОХРАНЫ 80
С.Б. Розенфельд, Е.Г. Стрельников, С.В. Волков
- ГЕМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ КАК МЕТОД МОНИТОРИНГА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ СРЕДНИХ ХИЩНЫХ МЛЕКОПИТАЮЩИХ ДАЛЬНЕГО ВОСТОКА РОССИИ 93
Г.С. Алексеева, М.Н. Ерофеева, Х.А. Эрнандес-Бланко, М.Н. Литвинов, М.Д. Чистополова, М.Д. Ким, В.В. Рожнов, С.В. Найдено
- КРАТКИЕ СООБЩЕНИЯ**
- ГРУППЫ *ODOBENUS ROSMARUS DIVERGENS* (ODOBENIDAE) В АКВАТОРИЯХ, ПРИЛЕГАЮЩИХ К ЛЕЖБИЩАМ (ЧУКОТСКИЙ ПОЛУОСТРОВ, РОССИЯ) 105
А.Н. Гилёв, М.В. Серединская, Н.В. Крюкова, Д.О. Скоробогатов, К.А. Каренина
- НАУЧНЫЕ ЗАМЕТКИ**
- ПЕРВОЕ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЕ *MASYELLA APODEMI* (DIGENEA, PLEUROGENIDAE) В РОССИИ 112
Н.Ю. Кириллова, А.А. Кириллов
- EPRACTIS PERSICA* (ORCHIDACEAE) – НОВЫЙ ТАКСОН ДЛЯ ФЛОРЫ КАЗАХСТАНА, КЫРГЫЗСТАНА И КИТАЯ 115
С.А. Кубентаев, П.Г. Ефимов, А.В. Фатерыга
- ПЕРВАЯ НАХОДКА *EPIDENDRUM ×DOROTEAE* (ORCHIDACEAE) В ЮЖНОЙ АМЕРИКЕ 118
Д.Ф. да Силва, Э.Г. ду Насименту, Ф.Ф.В.А. Барберена

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